

D1.2

Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels

WR - WFBR

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1. INTRODUCTION.....	8
2. COLLATION OF SUSTAINABILITY PRINCIPLES AND CRITERIA.....	9
2.1 Reviewed documents	9
2.1.1 Legislation.....	12
2.1.2 Standards.....	15
2.1.3 Sustainability certification schemes.....	15
2.1.4 Projects/Reports/Studies.....	16
2.2 Environmental Principles and Criteria.....	16
2.3 Circularity Principles and Criteria.....	21
2.4 Social Principles and Criteria	22
2.5 Economic Principles and Criteria	25
3. IDENTIFICATION AND SELECTION OF EXISTING SUSTAINABILITY CERTIFICATION SCHEMES AND LABELS FOR BIOBASED SYSTEMS.....	28
3.1 Sustainability systems, certification schemes and labels.....	28
3.2 Development of sustainability certification in the bioeconomy	28
3.3 Creation of a Long list	29
3.4 Further screening to a Short list	32
4. REVIEW AND ANALYSIS OF SELECTED SCHEMES AND LABELS.....	34
4.1 Approach	34
4.2 Factsheet Sections and Description of Items	35
5. CONCLUSIONS	39
6. FACTSHEETS	40
6.1 Factsheet ISCC PLUS.....	40
6.2 Factsheet RSB Advanced Products.....	46
6.3 Factsheet Better Biomass.....	52
6.4 Factsheet Textile Exchange GRS.....	58
6.5 Factsheet FSC.....	64
6.6 Factsheet RSPO	70
6.7 Factsheet Bonsucro	76
6.8 Factsheet Better Cotton	81
6.9 Factsheet EU Ecolabel	88
6.10 Factsheet Blue Angel	97
6.11 Factsheet Nordic Swan Ecolabel	104

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Overview of the reviewed sources in terms of document type and applications	12
Figure 2. Shortlisted sustainability certification schemes and labels	33

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 Reviewed legislation, standards, certification schemes and studies	9
Table 2 Compilation of environmental principles and criteria from review of documents	16
Table 3 Compilation of circularity principles and criteria from review of documents	21
Table 4 Compilation of social principles and criteria from review of documents	23
Table 5 Compilation of economic principles and criteria from review of documents	26
Table 6: Sustainability certification schemes in Long list	31
Table 7: Type-I Ecolabels in Europe	32
Table 8: Description of the items of a factsheet	35
Table 9 Factsheet ISCC Plus	40
Table 10 Factsheet RSB Advanced Products	46
Table 11 Factsheet Better Biomass	52
Table 12 Factsheet Textile Exchange GRS	58
Table 13 Factsheet FSC	64
Table 14 Factsheet RSPO	70
Table 15 Factsheet Bonsucro	76
Table 16 Factsheet Better Cotton	81
Table 17 Factsheet EU Ecolabel	88
Table 18 Factsheet Blue Angel	97
Table 19 Factsheet Nordic Swan Ecolabel	104

ABBREVIATIONS

CB	Certification Body
CEN	The European Committee for Standardization
EN	European Standard
EU	European Union
FAO	The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FSC	Forest Stewardship Council
GBEP	The Global Bioenergy Partnership
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GRS	Global Recycled Standard (of Textile Exchange)
ILUC	Indirect Land Use Change
ISBWG	The International Sustainable Bioeconomy Working Group
ISCC	International Sustainability & Carbon Certification
ISO	The International Organization for Standardization
LULUCF	Land Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry
NEN	The Netherlands Standardization Institute
NTA	Netherlands Technical Agreement
PEFC	Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification
RED II	Recast of the Renewable Energy Directive, 2018/2001
RSB	Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials
RSPO	Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil
RTRS	Round Table on Responsible Soy Association
TE	Textile Exchange

Executive Summary

In this report, a collation of sustainability principles and criteria applicable to biological resources and to biobased materials and products were made, reviewing relevant EU legislation (RED II, Taxonomy), standards (ISO 13065, EN 16751 and NTA 8080-1), selected certification schemes and studies (STAR-ProBio, S2BIOM, GBEP, FAO Sustainable Bioeconomy) in the field of sustainable bioeconomy. Besides the documents that are specifically developed for biobased products, also prominent examples of the ones developed for bioenergy/biofuels and food were taken into consideration to incorporate the longer experience in sustainability assessment and certification in these sectors. In order to ensure the contribution of biobased products to circular economy, circularity was considered with its own principles and criteria including aspects such as resource efficiency, renewable resource use and recycling of biobased products. Principles and criteria were defined accordingly under 4 sections: environmental, circularity, social and economic.

In order to identify existing sustainability certification schemes and labels for biobased systems, a list of criteria was compiled for screening. Schemes specifically developed for food/feed and biofuel/bioenergy sector were excluded. Global geographical scope and full life cycle coverage were considered. ITC Standards Map was the main source used for the identification of relevant schemes/labels and preparation of the long list. Following this, a further screening was done to identify the most relevant schemes for industrial biobased systems, also considering coverage of different type of feedstock and sectors and prominence in the market. This resulted in 11 shortlisted sustainability certification schemes and labels:

- Sustainability certification schemes for Biobased products and materials:
 1. ISCC Plus
 2. RSB Advanced Products
 3. Better Biomass
 4. Textile Exchange Global Recycled Standard
- Sustainability certification schemes specific for biological feedstocks for industrial biobased systems:
 5. FSC (wood)
 6. RSPO (palm)
 7. Bonsucro (sugarcane)
 8. Better Cotton (cotton)
- Ecolabels:
 9. EU Ecolabel
 10. Blue Angel Ecolabel
 11. Nordic Swan Ecolabel

Factsheets were prepared for these shortlisted sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems with the goal to provide a quick overview of them. The factsheets include different sections providing, besides general information and scope, also information on the governance of the schemes and their sustainability principles. Such factsheets have been prepared for schemes concerning biofuels and bioenergy value chains, yet such an overview is currently lacking for schemes applicable to biobased products. The goal is increased awareness on the existing schemes for biobased products which can promote the adoption of sustainability schemes in general for these products. These factsheets can also support industrial biobased system actors in selecting a scheme fitting to their value chain and organization.

1. Introduction

This deliverable is a combination of the output of two tasks of Work Package 1: Task 1.2 Setting up a methodology for reviewing schemes and labels, and Task 1.3 Identifying and reviewing existing sustainability certification schemes and labels relevant to biobased value chains.

The aim of T1.2 is the preparation of a template for the review of schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems and description of each item. This includes a collation of sustainability principles and criteria by reviewing relevant documents with equal consideration made for environment, social and economic dimensions of sustainability. In this project, it was considered to have circularity as an additional dimension where a set of principles and criteria for circularity is also prepared. In the preparation of the template, also a description of other information to be reviewed and documented such as scope (geographical, feedstock and product/sector coverage), as well as governance aspects is provided.

The aim of T1.3 is the identification of the most relevant sustainability certification schemes and labels for the biobased products and the biological resources intended for these products. This is to be followed by a review of the selected ones using the template prepared in T1.2. The outcome of this review is a set of factsheets prepared for each of the schemes, providing an overview of essential information.

The report is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 provides information on the review of the relevant legislation, standard, schemes and studies for collation of sustainability principles and criteria applicable for industrial biobased systems.
- Chapter 3 describes the identification of sustainability certification schemes and labels applicable for industrial biobased systems and selection of the ones for preparation of the factsheets.
- Chapter 4 presents the approach used in the review of the selected schemes and labels and describes the factsheet template prepared including the scope, governance and sustainability aspects.
- Conclusions of the report are given in Chapter 5 followed by Factsheets in Chapter 6 of the eleven shortlisted sustainability certification schemes and labels.

2. Collation of sustainability principles and criteria

In order to outline sustainability requirements applicable to biological resources and to biobased materials and products, a collation of principles and criteria was made reviewing relevant legislation, standards, certification schemes and studies in the field of sustainable bioeconomy. A holistic approach was followed, with equal consideration of all three pillars of sustainability (environment, social and economic). Furthermore, attention was paid to ensure the contribution of biobased products to circular economy including aspects such as resource efficiency, renewable resource use and recyclability of biobased products. Therefore, principles and criteria were defined under 4 sections: environmental, circularity, social and economic. The scope is global, considering the full life cycle and all value chain actors.

2.1 Reviewed documents

Information on the relevant reviewed legislation, standards, certification schemes and studies is presented in Table 1. Besides the documents that are specifically developed for biobased products, also prominent examples of the ones developed for bioenergy/biofuels and food were taken into consideration to incorporate the longer experience in sustainability assessment and certification in these sectors.

Table 1 Reviewed legislation, standards, certification schemes and studies

Name	Description
Legislation:	
Renewable Energy Directive Recast (RED II) ¹	The RED II defines sustainability criteria that liquid biofuels used in transport, as well as solid and gaseous biomass fuels for power, heating and cooling production, must comply with to be eligible for financial support by public authorities within the EU.
Taxonomy Regulation ²	The Taxonomy Regulation establishes a classification system which provides businesses and investors with a common language to identify whether or not a given economic activity should be considered "environmentally sustainable".
Standards:	
ISO 13065:2015 Sustainability criteria for bioenergy ³	This International Standard specifies principles, criteria and indicators for the bioenergy supply chain to facilitate the reporting of environmental, social and economic aspects of sustainability. It is applicable to the whole supply chain, parts of a supply chain or a single process in the supply chain.
EN 16751:2016 Biobased products - Sustainability criteria ⁴	The European standard lists horizontal sustainability aspects to the biobased part of all biobased products, excluding food, feed and energy, covering all three pillars of sustainability: environmental, social and economic aspects. It can be used to provide sustainability information about the biomass production only or in the supply chain for the biobased part of the biobased product.

¹ European Commission 2018. Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources (recast).

² European Commission 2021. Commission delegated Regulation 2800/2021, supplementing Regulation 2020/852 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment, [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=PI_COM:C\(2021\)2800](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=PI_COM:C(2021)2800)

³ ISO 2015. ISO 13065 Sustainability criteria for bioenergy

⁴ CEN. 2016. EN 16751 Bio-based products – Sustainability criteria.

Name	Description
NTA 8080-1 ¹ Sustainably produced biomass for bioenergy and biobased products	The Dutch standard describes the requirements for sustainably produced biomass for application in bioenergy (electricity, heating, cooling, and transport fuel) and biobased products. The Better Biomass ² certification scheme describes the rules for certification against the requirements of NTA 8080-1 and NTA 8080-2 (chain of custody).
Sustainability certification schemes	
RSB Advanced Products ³ RSB Principles & Criteria ⁴	The RSB Global Advanced Products Certification enables the certification of non-energy products like plastics, textiles, pharmaceuticals, packaging, tableware, cosmetics, nutritional supplements, food, feed, pulp, paper and many others. Besides biobased feedstock, scheme also includes as feedstock end-of-life products and production residues (either biobased or non-biobased). The RSB principles and criteria apply to biobased industrial value chain actors (apart from the specific requirements provided in the RSB Global Advanced Products document). RSB has for biofuel producers in the EU, or selling into the EU, RSB EU RED Standard and the RSB Global Standard for biofuel producers in other regions.
ISCC Plus ⁵ ISCC Sustainability Requirements ⁶	ISCC PLUS is a certification system for all markets and sectors not regulated by the RED or Fuel Quality Directive, such as the food, feed, chemical and energy markets and for technical applications. Under ISCC PLUS, all types of agricultural and forestry raw materials, waste and residues, non-bio renewables and recycled carbon materials and fuels are covered. The ISCC EU System Documents (for biofuels in the EU) lay down the general ISCC Sustainability Requirements which are (apart from the different requirements specified in the ISCC PLUS document) also valid under ISCC PLUS.
Forest Stewardship Council® (FSC®) ⁷	The Forest Stewardship Council A.C. (FSC) is an international non-profit, multistakeholder organization established in 1993. As the pioneer of forest certification, FSC sets the standard for responsible forest stewardship. FSC standards include safeguards to ensure that stakeholders throughout the forest supply chain live up to the principles that protect healthy and resilient forests for all.
GlobalG.A.P. IFA ⁸ GLOBALG.A.P. GRASP ⁹	GLOBALG.A.P. Integrated Farm Assurance (IFA) is a program translating consumer requirements into Good Agricultural Practices (GAP). It is the internationally recognized standard for farm production. The IFA standard includes three scopes containing multiple product categories that cover agriculture, floriculture, aquaculture, and livestock. Most European customers for agricultural products demand the GlobalG.A.P. certification as a prerequisite for doing business. The standard was developed using the Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points guidelines published by the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization and is governed according to the ISO/IEC 17065 for product certification schemes. The GLOBALG.A.P. risk assessment on social practice (GRASP) is a voluntary, farm-level social/labor management tool for global supply chains, to be used in combination with GlobalG.A.P. IFA.

¹ NEN. NTA 8080-1:2015 Sustainably produced biomass for bioenergy and biobased products - Part 1: Sustainability requirements.

² NEN. Better Biomass certification scheme. NCS 8080:2018-08.

³ RSB Standard for Advanced Products. RSB-STD-02-001 (version 2.0).

⁴ The RSB Principles & Criteria for the Sustainable Production of Biomass, Biofuels and Biomaterials (RSB-STD-01-001 version 3.0)

⁵ ISCC Plus System Document v3.3.

⁶ ISCC 202 Sustainability Requirements v3.1.

⁷ FSC Principles and Criteria for Forest Stewardship, FSC-STD-01-001 v5-2.

⁸ GlobalG.A.P. Integrated Farm Assurance, Guideline for Fruit and Vegetables, v6.0.

⁹ GlobalG.A.P. GRASP Principles and Criteria, v2.0.

Name	Description
Fair Trade ¹	Fair trade is an arrangement designed to help producers in growing countries achieve sustainable and equitable trade relationships. The fair trade movement combines the payment of higher prices to with improved social and environmental standards. The movement focuses in particular on commodities, or products that are typically exported from developing countries to developed countries but is also used in domestic markets. The Fairtrade certification system covers a growing range of products, most notably bananas, cocoa, coffee, flowers, tea, sugar, cotton, dried and fresh fruits, and vegetables. Fairtrade has a separate standard for textiles ² which applies to operators employing hired workers in the textile supply chain processing Fairtrade certified cotton and other responsible fibres.
Projects/Reports/Studies:	
STAR-ProBio ³	The main objective of STAR-ProBio is to promote a harmonised policy framework through the development of fit-for-purpose sustainability monitoring policy schemes for biobased products, including standards, certifications and labels. The results were discussed in the context of a general certification scheme organized finally into a STAR-ProBio proposal of principles, criteria and indicators for the three pillars of sustainability. ⁴
S2Biom ⁵	The project aimed to develop comprehensive sustainability requirements for all non-food biomass in the broader bioeconomy. A proposal on sustainability criteria and indicators for bioeconomy was presented considering the three sustainability dimensions: environment, social and economic. ⁶
GBEP ⁷	The Global Bioenergy Partnership (GBEP) established the Task Force on Sustainability to promote the sustainable production and use of bioenergy. The report presents 24 voluntary sustainability indicators for bioenergy intended to guide any analysis undertaken of bioenergy at the domestic level with a view to informing decision-making and facilitating the use of bioenergy as a means towards meeting national goals of sustainable development.
FAO sustainable bioeconomy ⁸	The International Sustainable Bioeconomy Working Group (ISBWG) established in the context of FAO's project on sustainable bioeconomy guidelines, has proposed a set of Aspirational Principles and Criteria for Sustainable Bioeconomy. They are complementary as they encompass the social, economic, environmental and governance dimensions of sustainability.

Figure 1 shows the categorisation of the reviewed documents in terms of type of document (i.e., legislation, standard, certification scheme or study) and the type of applications it is used for (i.e., biobased products, biofuels/bioenergy, food).

¹ Fairtrade Standard scale for Small Producer Organizations (v2.5) & Fairtrade Trader Standard (v1.7)

² Fairtrade Textile Standard v1.2.

³ Sustainability Transition Assessment and Research of Biobased Products (STAR-ProBio) available at <http://www.star-probio.eu/>.

⁴ STAR-ProBio 2019, Deliverable D8.1: Recommendations concerning current sustainability standards associated with biobased products and amendments to current standards of biobased products.

⁵ The S2Biom project - Delivery of sustainable supply of non-food biomass to support a "resource-efficient" Bioeconomy in Europe, available at <https://s2biom.wenr.wur.nl/home>.

⁶ S2Biom 2015, D5.4 Consistent Cross-Sectoral Sustainability Criteria & Indicators.

⁷ GBEP 2011, The Global Bioenergy Partnership Sustainability Indicators for Bioenergy.

⁸ FAO. 2021. Aspirational principles and criteria for a sustainable bioeconomy. Rome.

Figure 1. Overview of the reviewed sources in terms of document type and applications

2.1.1 Legislation

RED II

The Renewable Energy Directive (RED II)¹, Directive (EU) 2018/2001 sets environmental sustainability criteria regarding the use of biomass for bioenergy and biofuels. This legal basis for bioenergy/biofuels can be a reference for biobased products.

The environmental sustainability criteria are included in RED II article 29, paragraphs 2 to 7.

Paragraph 2 – Effect on soil quality from the extraction of waste and residues from agricultural land (not from forestry)

RED II requires that operators or national authorities have monitoring or management plans in place in order to address the impacts on soil quality and soil carbon.

Paragraph 3 - Land with a high biodiversity value

RED II requires that biofuels, bioliquids and biomass fuels produced from agricultural biomass are not made from raw material obtained from land with a high biodiversity value, namely land that had one of the following statuses in or after January 2008: primary forest and other wooded land, protected areas and highly biodiverse grassland.

Paragraph 4 – Land with high-carbon stock

RED II requires that biofuels, bioliquids and biomass fuels produced from agricultural biomass are not made from raw material obtained from land with high-carbon stock, namely land that had one of the following statuses in January 2008 and no longer has that status: wetlands, continuously forested areas, and other (sparsely) forested areas.

Paragraph 5 – Peatland

RED II requires that biofuels, bioliquids and biomass fuels produced from agricultural biomass are not made from raw material obtained from land that was peatland in January 2008, unless evidence

¹ European Commission 2018. Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources (recast).

is provided that the cultivation and harvesting of that raw material does not involve drainage of previously undrained soil.

Paragraph 6 – Sustainable forest management and Paragraph 7 – LULUCF

RED II includes two sets of sustainability criteria for forest biomass: one to minimise the risk of using forest biomass derived from unsustainable production; and another to ensure compliance with land use, land-use change and forestry (LULUCF) requirements. The first set of criteria considers ensuring the following:

- Legality of harvesting;
- Forest regeneration;
- Protection of high conservation value areas, including wetlands and peatlands;
- Minimising impact on soil quality and biodiversity;
- Maintaining or improving the long-term production capacity.

LULUCF criteria checks:

- a) The country, (i) is a Party to the Paris Agreement; (ii) has submitted a nationally determined contribution to UNFCCC, covering emissions and removals from agriculture, forestry and land use; or (iii) has national or sub-national laws in place to conserve and enhance carbon stocks and sinks, and providing evidence that reported LULUCF-sector emissions do not exceed removals;
- b) that management systems are in place at forest sourcing area level to ensure that carbon stocks and sinks levels in the forest are maintained or strengthened over the long term.

Paragraph 10 – Greenhouse gas emission savings

Additionally, RED II article 29, paragraph 10 sets minimum greenhouse gas (GHG) emission saving requirements for bioenergy and biofuels.

Indirect land use change

Furthermore, RED II includes consideration of high and low indirect land use change (ILUC) risk. The ILUC risk is considered as high if biofuels are produced from food and feed crops for which a significant expansion of the production area into land with high-carbon stock is observed. In order to limit the risk of ILUC, RED II included a measure that the contribution of high ILUC-risk biofuels is limited to the 2019 level and their contribution will be gradually phased out by 2030, unless they are certified to be low ILUC-risk biofuels. After RED II, the Commission published Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/807¹ which defines high ILUC-risk biofuels, as well as criteria for the certification of low ILUC-risk biofuels.

REDIII

In RED II, the overall EU target for Renewable Energy Sources consumption by 2030 has been set to 32%. The new proposed directive for the use of energy from renewable sources (RED III) considers increase in the target share of renewables in final energy consumption to 45% as well as dedicated sectoral measures for heating and cooling, buildings, industry, transport and bioenergy. The draft of REDIII, which was submitted by the European Commission in July 2021, proposed to strengthen the sustainability criteria with especially additional limitations on the use of primary woody

¹ European Commission, 2019. Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/807 supplementing Directive (EU) 2018/2001 as regards the determination of high indirect land-use-change-risk feedstock for which a significant expansion of the production area into land with high carbon stock is observed and the certification of low indirect land-use change-risk biofuels, bioliquids, and biomass fuels.

biomass e.g., no harvesting of roots or stumps and no degradation of primary or old-growth forest. Additional requirements exist on stopping subsidies power only production from forest biomass and requiring woody biomass use is aligned with the “cascading principle.” In line with the cascading principle, woody biomass should be used according to its highest economic and environmental added value in the following order of priorities: 1) wood-based products, 2) extending their service life, 3) re-use, 4) recycling, 5) bioenergy and 6) disposal.¹

Taxonomy

The EU taxonomy is a classification system, establishing a list of environmentally sustainable economic activities. The Taxonomy Regulation² establishes the basis for the EU taxonomy by setting out three cumulative conditions that an economic activity has to meet in order to qualify as environmentally sustainable:

- Making a substantial contribution to at least one of the 6 environmental objectives in the Taxonomy Regulation
- Not causing significant harm to any of the 5 others
- Complying with minimum social safeguards

The Taxonomy Regulation establishes six environmental objectives

1. Climate change mitigation
2. Climate change adaptation
3. The sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources
4. The transition to a circular economy
5. Pollution prevention and control
6. The protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems

A delegated act on sustainable activities for climate change adaptation and mitigation objectives was published in 2021 and amended in 2022 to include additional economic activities.

This first delegated act³, sets criteria under which an economic activity ‘qualifies as contributing substantially to climate change mitigation or climate change adaptation and for determining whether that economic activity causes no significant harm to any of the other environmental objectives. Relevant for bio-based industries in the EU are the manufacture of plastics in primary form (3.17) and for the manufacture of organic based chemicals (3.14). The Annex of the regulation defines technical screening criteria for substantial contribution to climate change mitigation. One of these criteria is that the life cycle GHG emissions of the plastic or organic chemical, which is produced wholly or partially from renewable feedstock, are lower than the life-cycle GHG emissions of the equivalent plastic in primary form or chemical manufactured from fossil fuel feedstock. Lifecycle GHG

¹ Proposal for a directive of the European parliament and the Council amending Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council, Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Directive 98/70/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the promotion of energy from renewable sources, and repealing Council Directive (EU) 2015/652

² European Commission 2021. Commission delegated Regulation 2800/2021, supplementing Regulation 2020/852 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment, [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=PI_COM:C\(2021\)2800](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=PI_COM:C(2021)2800)

³ Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/2139 of 4 June 2021 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2020/852 of the European Parliament and of the Council by establishing the technical screening criteria for determining the conditions under which an economic activity qualifies as contributing substantially to climate change mitigation or climate change adaptation and for determining whether that economic activity causes no significant harm to any of the other environmental objectives

emissions are calculated using Recommendation 2013/179/EU or, alternatively, using ISO 14067:2018 or ISO 14064-1:2018. Quantified life cycle GHG emissions are verified by an independent third party. Additionally, the “Agricultural biomass used for the manufacture complies with the criteria laid down in Article 29, paragraphs 2 to 5, of Directive (EU) 2018/2001. Forest biomass used for the manufacture complies with the criteria laid down in Article 29, paragraphs 6 and 7 of that Directive.” Thereby, the sustainability criteria set in RED II are all covered.

A delegated act concerning the remaining four environmental objectives defined in the Taxonomy regulation is under preparation. The manufacture of plastic packaging goods, relevant to the biobased industry is one of the activities in the draft annex focusing on economic activities potentially making a substantial contribution to the transition to a circular economy.

2.1.2 Standards

ISO 13065 (International)

International organizations are working on sustainability standards, most notably the International Organization for Standardization (ISO). This standard ISO 13065:2015 is dedicated to sustainability criteria for bioenergy.

EN 16751 (European)

CEN Technical Committee 411 for biobased products has been developing European standards for biobased products. The standard related to sustainability criteria for biobased products is EN 16751:2016.

NTA 8080-1 (National)

The Netherlands Standardization Institute (NEN) developed with a diverse group of Dutch stakeholders the National Technical Agreement NTA 8080 Sustainability criteria for biomass. NTA 8080-1:2009 was for application in bioenergy and in NTA 8080-1:2015 the scope was extended to include application in biobased products. As member of CEN and ISO, NEN will ensure that the sustainability criteria and conformity assessment processes are and will remain aligned with the relevant European (EN) and international (ISO) standards.

2.1.3 Sustainability certification schemes

RSB, ISCC, Better Biomass, FSC, GlobalG.A.P, Fair Trade

Recently, several scheme owners have created new schemes or extended their scope to biobased products. These include RSB Advanced Products, ISCC Plus and REDCert² for biobased products. Additionally, the Better Biomass scheme providing certification against the requirements of Dutch standards NTA 8080-1:2015 (described above) is for application of biomass in both bioenergy and biobased products. For this review the RSB Advanced Products and ISCC Plus were selected as certifications specific for biobased products and Better Biomass that is applicable for both biofuels and biobased products. FSC provides certification of woody biomass which can be utilized both in energy and product applications. Additionally, prominent schemes that are mainly related to food production were reviewed: GLOBALG.A.P. which is the internationally recognized standard for farm production for food/feed and Fair Trade which is mostly for food products. Fair Trade also covers cotton, which is relevant for the textile industry and has a standard for textiles.

2.1.4 Projects/Reports/Studies

STAR-ProBio, S2Biom, GBEP and FAO Sustainable Bioeconomy

Studies which looked at monitoring sustainability of bioeconomy were also reviewed which include STAR-ProBio and S2Biom projects, GBEP indicators and FAO principles and criteria for sustainable bioeconomy. Recently, the STAR-ProBio project proposed sustainability principles, criteria and indicators for biobased products in environmental, social, economic and circular dimensions.¹ The S2Biom project developed comprehensive sustainability requirements for all non-food biomass in the broader bioeconomy.² Additionally, the Global Bioenergy Partnership (GBEP) developed a set of sustainability indicators for bioenergy under three pillars: environmental, social and economic.³ The International Sustainable Bioeconomy Working Group (ISBWG) established in the context of FAO's project on sustainable bioeconomy guidelines, has proposed a set of Aspirational Principles and Criteria for Sustainable Bioeconomy.⁴

2.2 Environmental Principles and Criteria

The environmental dimension is addressed in most detail by all of the reviewed documents. The comprehensive collation of the environmental principles and criteria addressed in the reviewed documents is presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Compilation of environmental principles and criteria from review of documents

Principle	Criteria
Reduce GHG emissions	<p><i>Lifecycle GHG emissions</i> The economic operator provides information on how greenhouse gas emissions and removals related to their operations are managed.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify GHG emissions and removals related to their operations Describe measures to reduce these GHG emissions Meet all applicable GHG reduction requirements set by national and/or regional and/or local regulations. Quantify net lifecycle GHG emissions
Conserve land with high carbon stock and peatland	<p><i>Protection of land with high carbon stock</i> Raw material shall not be obtained from land with high-carbon stock, namely land that had one of the following statuses in January 2008 and no longer has that status: wetlands, continuously forested areas, and other (sparsely) forested areas.</p>
	<p><i>Protection of peatland</i> Raw material shall not be obtained from land that was peatland in January 2008, unless evidence is provided that the cultivation and harvesting of that raw material does not involve drainage of previously undrained soil.</p>
Promote sustainable forest management	<p><i>Maintaining forest productivity</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The country in which forest biomass was harvested has national or sub-national laws applicable in the area of harvest as well as monitoring and enforcement systems in place ensuring forest regeneration and long-term production capacity of forests. Ensuring that carbon stocks and sinks levels in the forest are maintained, or strengthened, over the long term. A forest management plan exists and is applied

¹ Sustainability Transition Assessment and Research of Biobased Products (STAR-ProBio) available at <http://www.star-probio.eu/>.

² The S2Biom project - Delivery of sustainable supply of non-food biomass to support a "resource-efficient" Bioeconomy in Europe, available at <https://s2biom.wenr.wur.nl/home>.

³ GBEP 2011, The Global Bioenergy Partnership Sustainability Indicators for Bioenergy.

⁴ FAO. 2021. Aspirational principles and criteria for a sustainable bioeconomy. Rome.

Principle	Criteria
Promote the positive and reduce the negative impacts on ecosystems and biodiversity	<p><i>Protection of land with a high biodiversity value</i> Raw material shall not be obtained from land with high biodiversity value, namely land that had one of the following statuses on 1 January 2008 or later</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) primary forest and other wooded land, b) areas designated by law or by the relevant competent authority for nature protection purposes & areas for the protection of rare, threatened or endangered ecosystems or species, c) highly biodiverse grassland, and d) legally recognized conservation value areas (or effectively protected by other means)
	<p><i>Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity</i> The economic operator provides information on how biodiversity values are addressed within the area of operation and the environment directly influenced by the economic operator.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ecosystem functions and services that are directly affected by the operation shall be maintained or enhanced. • Operations shall protect, restore or create buffer zones, including riparian vegetation sections • Ecological corridors shall be protected, restored or created to minimise fragmentation of habitats. • Ensure that it is prevented that the environment is disturbed by invasive species (including genetically modified crops) • Harvesting is carried out considering maintenance of biodiversity with the aim of minimising negative impacts
Conserve and protect water resources	<p><i>Sustainable use of water</i> The economic operator provides information on how quantity of water drawn and released are addressed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application of good agricultural practices to reduce water usage and to maintain and improve water quality • Documentation of water management plans aimed at using water efficiently and the prevention of water pollution • Ensure that surface and groundwater use does not exceed the natural replenishment capacities
	<p><i>Maintaining and enhancing water quality</i> The economic operator provides information on how quality of water drawn and released are addressed</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevention of surface and ground water contamination/pollution as a consequence of the storage and use of chemicals and other biological agents. • Buffer zones shall be set between the operation site and surface or groundwater resources. • Wastewater or runoff that contains potential organic and mineral contaminants shall be treated or recycled
Protect soil quality and productivity	<p><i>Maintaining and enhancing soil quality and productivity</i> Operators shall implement practices to maintain or enhance soil's physical, chemical, and biological conditions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The organization shall take measures that are necessary in order to ensure that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) erosion is prevented and controlled, in which topographic risks are taken into account; b) the nutrient balance is maintained, at least as regards nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) (fertilisers are used according to nutritional requirements); c) the soil organic matter (SOM) is preserved and improved over time; d) the soil structure is maintained and improved over time (include the prevention of compaction); e) soil salination is prevented; f) risks for the soil as a consequence of the storage and the use of chemicals and other business processes are prevented and controlled • Implement measures to improve soil health, (such as following Conservation Agriculture practices) include, inter alia, optimum plant spacing, crop rotation and intercropping, landscaping elements or an appropriate type and use of machinery

Principle	Criteria
	<p><i>Use of residual flows</i> The use of residues does not occur at the expense of the soil nutrient balance, soil organic matter balance or important traditional uses (such as fodder, natural fertiliser, material or local fuel), unless documentation is available to suggest that similar or better alternatives are available and are applied.</p>
Implement best practices for the use of (agro)chemicals	<p><i>Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals</i> None of the chemicals recorded in the WHO's 1a and 1b lists, Annex III of the Rotterdam Convention, Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants or the Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer shall be used.</p>
	<p><i>Use, storage, handling and disposal of (agro)chemicals</i> Good practices shall be implemented for the storage, handling, use, and disposal of (agro)chemicals.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoiding plant protection products by integrated pest management • Use of best practices in plant protection product and fertiliser application, up-to-date records on all applications • Use of best practices storing operating resources • Use of best practices in handling and disposing (agro)chemicals • Only use of (agro)chemicals authorized for the country of production • Restriction on the use of sewage sludge
Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality	<p><i>Air quality</i> The organization shall take any measures that are necessary to ensure that the emission of harmful substances into the air as a result of the production, processing and transport of biomass is limited.</p>
	<p><i>Restriction on open-air burning</i> Operations shall avoid and, where possible, eliminate open-air burning of residues, wastes or by-products, or open air burning to clear the land.</p>
Limit the risk of Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC)	<p><i>ILUC low risk</i> The economic operator provides information on its strategies adopted to reach a "low ILUC risk" level. Strategies to ensure low ILUC-risk include yield increase, use of unused land, and use of waste and residues.</p>

Recently, a study commissioned by CBE JU¹ defined environmental sustainability requirements to ensure the environmental sustainability of bio-based value chains of future EU-funded research & innovation, demonstration and flagship projects. Five overarching environmental principles were defined following a systematic review of literature:

- Mitigate global warming (includes GHG emissions, high carbon stock, fertiliser use, ILUC, forest management)
- Protect and improve biodiversity (includes high biodiversity value, improve biodiversity, integrated pest management)
- Protect and improve water resources (includes sustainable use of water, water quality, hazardous chemicals)
- Protect and improve soil quality and productivity (includes soil quality and productivity)
- Protect and improve air quality (includes open air burning, air quality)

All environmental principles within this CBE JU study are covered in this collation of environmental principles and criteria (presented in Table 2).

¹ nova-Institute, SQ Consult. 2022. Study of the environmental sustainability requirements of biobased value chains and supply chains for bio-based industry in future EU funded R&I demonstration and flagship projects (internal use only)

In the sub-sections below, a description is given on how the definitions of the environmental principles and criteria in Table 2 were made from the review of the legislation, standards, certification schemes and studies described in section 2.1.

Reduce GHG emissions

Criteria on climate change mitigation and GHG emissions were covered in almost all reviewed documents. No requirements are set for the net greenhouse gas emission reduction for biobased products (whereas for biofuels compliance with GHG emissions saving criteria laid down in REDII paragraph 10 of Article 29 is required). The criterion in Table 2 was defined following EN 16751 definition and was complemented with the RSB criteria concerning requirement to meet all applicable regulations and quantify lifecycle GHG emissions.

Conserve land with high carbon stock and peatland

This principle covers the criteria: Protection of land with high carbon stock and Protection of peatland. The criterion in Table 2 were defined following the RED II definition (criteria laid down in paragraphs 4 and 5 of Article 29) and also covered following this definition in sustainability certification schemes RSB, ISCC and Better Biomass that are reviewed.

Promote sustainable forest management

The criteria of Maintaining Forest Productivity are specifically covered in FSC. Also, GBEP specifically considers monitoring the annual harvesting of wood resources relative to the amount which could be removed sustainably. This provides an indication of a forest's ability to provide a continuing supply of forest products and economic and forest management opportunities. The criterion in Table 2 was defined following RED II definition (criteria laid down in paragraphs 6 and 7 of Article 29). These criteria specific for forestry biomass were newly brought into the scope of RED in the recast of 2018 (RED II) and are now included with amendments in the sustainability certification schemes RSB, ISCC and Better Biomass that are reviewed.

Promote the positive and reduce the negative impacts on ecosystems and biodiversity

This principle covers the criteria: Protection of land with a high biodiversity value and Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity.

Criterion on Protection of land with a high biodiversity value was defined following the RED II definition (criteria laid down in paragraph 3 of Article 29) and also covered following this definition in sustainability certification schemes RSB, ISCC and Better Biomass that are reviewed as well as in S2BIOM and GBEP. It is partially covered in the standards ISO 13065 and EN 16751 where only the removal from those areas designated as biodiversity protected areas under applicable national laws and regulations is considered. The definition in Table 2 was extended from the RED II definition by including bullet on legally recognized conservation value areas which refers to the concept of High Conservation Value (HCV) areas also included in FSC.

Criterion on Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity was defined following the definition in ISO 13065 and EN 16751. Additional bullets were included in the definition from the specific additional consideration present in sustainability certification schemes especially following RSB (on ecosystem functions, buffer zones, ecological corridors, invasive species). This criterion is covered in almost all the documents. In REDII only the last bullet in Table 2 is provided which refers to harvesting of forest biomass.

Conserve and protect water resources

This principle covers the criteria: Sustainable use of water and Maintaining and enhancing water quality. They are often covered together and in almost all of the reviewed documents (except REDII). The criteria were defined following the definition in ISO 13065 and EN 16751. Additional bullets were included in the definition from the specific additional considerations present especially in sustainability certification schemes ISCC, RSB and Better Biomass i.e. for Sustainable use of water requirements on water management plan, no depletion beyond replenishment capacities and for Water quality requirements on buffer zones, avoiding runoffs and contamination of surface and ground water resources in particular related to use of chemicals and biological agents.

Protect soil quality and productivity

This principle covers the criteria: Maintaining and enhancing soil quality and productivity and Use of residual flows.

Criterion on Maintaining and enhancing soil quality and productivity was defined largely following RSB definition with first bullet on aspects to address a) to f) following Better Biomass and second bullet on possible measures to improve soil health from ISCC. This criterion is covered in almost all reviewed documents (except REDII).

Criterion on Use of residual flows was defined following the ISCC definition. This criterion was not explicitly covered in ISO 13065 and EN 16751 standards, otherwise covered in almost all reviewed documents including REDII (criteria laid down in paragraph 2 of Article 29). It is important to note that while REDII and ISCC only consider agricultural residues, the effect of harvesting forestry residues is also considered in RSB, Better Biomass and S2BIOM.

Implement best practices for the use of (agro)chemicals

This principle covers the criteria: Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals and Use, storage, handling and disposal of (agro)chemicals

Criterion on Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals was defined following RSB but also covered in other reviewed certification schemes with RSB providing the most detailed references to relevant lists, convention and protocols. STAR-ProBio also considers the use of hazardous chemicals by screening their presence through relevant databases.

Criterion on Use, storage, handling and disposal of (agro)chemicals was defined following RSB and the bullets on requirements following ISCC. This criterion was also covered in other reviewed certification schemes.

Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality

Air quality is explicitly addressed in the reviewed standards, studies and sustainability certification schemes of RSB, ISCC and Better Biomass. The definition of the criterion in Table 2 was done following Better Biomass/NTA 8080-1.

Additionally, a separate criterion is considered for Restriction on open-air burning of residues, wastes or by-products, or open air burning as part of land clearance. This criterion is specifically covered in the voluntary sustainability schemes RSB, ISCC and Better Biomass.

Limit the risk of Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC)

This ILUC criterion is explicitly addressed in few of the reviewed documents: NTA 8080-1/Better Biomass, RSB, STAR-ProBio and S2BIOM. The definition was made following STAR-ProBio and the three strategies provided thereof are from RSB's voluntary Low ILUC risk module. ILUC is also addressed by REDII using a risk-based approach: ILUC risk is defined as either high or low. After

REDII, the Commission published Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/807 which defines high ILUC risk biofuels, as well as criteria for the certification of low ILUC-risk biofuels.¹ The ILUC risk is considered as low if additional biomass is produced through these three strategies: yield increase, use of unused land, and use of waste and residues.

2.3 Circularity Principles and Criteria

This aspect of sustainability is so far not explicitly covered in standards and certification schemes. The principles related to waste management and resource efficiency are usually covered under environmental dimension within these existing documents. In this project it was considered to have circularity as an additional dimension with its own set of principles and criteria. Also extending the scope to include renewable resource use, recyclability and use of recycled materials, which are so far not specifically or explicitly addressed in existing standards and schemes. The collation of the circularity principles and criteria accordingly made is presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Compilation of circularity principles and criteria from review of documents

Principle	Criteria
Promote waste reduction and responsible waste management	<p><i>Waste management</i></p> <p>The organization shall take any measures that are necessary to ensure that the practices applied in its operations are aimed at responsible waste management</p> <p>Attention is paid to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Prevention of waste; Reuse of waste; Official collection and disposal systems are used; Separation of waste for recycling; Recovery of waste other than reuse or recycling; Complying with all local regulations related to waste management
	<p><i>Valorization of residual flows</i></p> <p>The organization shall take measures to ensure that residual flows from the production and processing of biomass are optimally used.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> They shall be reused by the processing/production unit or sold to other sectors whenever their use may improve the overall system's energy balance, greenhouse gas emissions, and/or economic viability. They shall be used for energy generation only if the use for material purposes is not possible (e.g., no market is accessible), and the use is in line with the Air quality principle.
Promote efficient use of energy and material resources	<p><i>Raw material efficiency</i></p> <p>The economic operator provides information on how material efficiency related to their operations are addressed. Biomass should be used as resource efficient as possible over the entire life cycle, and continue to be used.</p>
	<p><i>Efficient use of energy</i></p> <p>The economic operator provides information on how energy use and efficiency are addressed and there is a plan to improve energy efficiency</p>
	<p><i>Use of renewable and non-renewable sources</i></p> <p>The economic operator provides information on how the use of renewable energy sources is promoted and efforts are made to reduce fossil energy consumption.</p>
Promote material circularity	<p><i>Material circularity</i></p> <p>The economic operator provides information on the use of recycled materials and how effective recyclability of the bio-based product is achieved.</p>

¹ European Commission, 2019. Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/807 supplementing Directive (EU) 2018/2001 as regards the determination of high indirect land-use-change-risk feedstock for which a significant expansion of the production area into land with high carbon stock is observed and the certification of low indirect land-use change-risk biofuels, bioliquids, and biomass fuels.

In the sub-sections below, a description is given on how the definitions of the circularity principles and criteria in Table 3 were made through the review of the legislation, standards, certification schemes and studies described in section 2.1.

Promote waste reduction and responsible waste management

The criterion on Waste management is defined following NTA 8080-1/Better Biomass. It is covered in all reviewed standards, schemes as well as in STAR-ProBio study.

Additionally, a separate criterion is considered for Valorization of residual flows which is specifically addressed in the sustainability schemes RSB, ISCC and Better Biomass. The definition in Table 3 is made following NTA 8080-1/Better Biomass combined with bullets of specific consideration provided in RSB related to use or sale for use, and promotion of material use over energy. In STAR-ProBio, the principle for waste management also has a requirement on guidance and clear instructions to the consumer on how the biobased product is to be disposed after use.

Promote efficient use of energy and material resources

This principle includes the criteria on Raw material and Energy efficiency, as well as Use of renewable resources over non-renewable. Raw material efficiency is explicitly covered in EN 16751 and NTA 8080-1/Better Biomass and described following these in Table 3. It is also covered in the studies S2BIOM and FAO. In ISCC Plus and NTA 8080-1/Better Biomass reference to cascading use of biomass is made.

The criterion on Efficient use of energy was described following ISO 13065. It is also specifically addressed in ISCC and studies STAR-ProBio, S2BIOM and GBEP. In EN 16751 it is covered together with material efficiency.

The criterion on Use of renewable and non-renewable sources was explicitly covered in EN 16751 and STAR-ProBio. These two documents promote both the use of renewable raw materials and renewable energy sources. In ISCC and GBEP within energy efficiency criteria also reducing fossil energy consumption and the use of renewable energy are considered.

Promote material circularity

This criterion was described following STAR-ProBio, which is the only document in which this criterion is explicitly addressed. S2Biom has an indicator for secondary resource efficiency. Both ISCC and RSB consider the use of waste / end-of-life products as feedstock for the production of products.

2.4 Social Principles and Criteria

Some of the social principles and criteria were found to be quite standard, addressed by most and in the same manner within the reviewed documents. This is especially due to the linkage to the International Labour Organisation conventions in definition of the social criteria in all the reviewed documents. This is especially seen in the principles Compliance with labour rights and Working conditions as well as Land use rights criteria that are covered by all of the reviewed standards and schemes as well as in STAR-ProBio and S2BIOM studies. Wellbeing of the local population and Food security are the principles that were found to be less covered and addressed explicitly by the reviewed documents. The collation of the social principles and criteria made is presented in Table 4.

Table 4 Compilation of social principles and criteria from review of documents

Social sustainability principle	Sustainability criteria
Compliance with labour rights	<p><i>Child labour</i> Prohibition of child labour. The minimum age must comply with all local and national legislation as well as with ILO Convention 138 and 182.</p>
	<p><i>Forced and compulsory labour</i> Prohibition to impose or permit the imposition of forced or compulsory labour for the benefit of private individuals, companies or associations (ILO 29) as well as to suppress and not to make use of any form of forced or compulsory labour (ILO 105).</p>
	<p><i>Fair salary, Remuneration</i> A living wage is paid which meets at least legal or industry minimum standards</p>
	<p><i>Association and collective bargaining rights</i> Promote the right to freedom of association, as defined in ILO 87 and right to collective bargaining, as defined in ILO 98.</p>
	<p><i>Equal opportunities/discrimination</i> Adherence to non-discrimination in the workplace, as defined in ILO 111 and equal remuneration, as defined in ILO 100. Workers shall be free of discrimination of any kind, whether in employment or opportunity, with respect to wages, working conditions, and social benefits. Policies and/or processes in place that prevent discrimination based on race, colour, gender, sex, religion, political opinion, national extraction or social origin are in place.</p> <p><i>Grievance mechanism</i> The organization shall demonstrate that there is a transparent and easily accessible grievance mechanism, that there are agreements on handling labour conflicts and that employees feel at liberty to make use of them.</p>
Working conditions	<p><i>Contract</i> All own workers and subcontracted workers via outsourced activities are to be provided with fair legal contracts in which all rights and obligations of workers are defined including salary; working hours, overtime and leave details; notice/contract period.</p>
	<p><i>Training</i> The organisation shall provide regular training for workers providing skills and knowledge for personal development and career advancement.</p>
	<p><i>Occupational health and safety</i> Conditions of occupational safety and health for workers shall follow internationally recognised standards (ILO 155 and 184). The organisation shall:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide adequate protective clothing and personal protective equipment, • Provide appropriate training on a regular basis about work-related health and safety risks, handling of hazardous substances and waste, • Implement and maintain procedures and measures addressing emergencies and accidents., including adequate first-aid arrangements. provision of medical care services, • Ensure maintenance of equipment and machinery for their proper and efficient functioning, • Provide measures relating to the safe handling of chemicals at work, • Ensure on-site living quarters are compliant with applicable regulations, equipped with basic services (clean sanitary facilities) and ensure safe and healthy conditions.
	<p><i>Harassment, violence</i> The company shall not engage in or tolerate the use of corporal punishment, mental or physical coercion, verbal or physical abuse or sexual harassment or any kind of intimidation of workers</p>
	<p><i>Hours of work and overtime</i> The organization shall:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrate that the local statutory working hours are not exceeded or, if there are no statutory provisions, that a normal working week, without overtime, is not more than 48 hours;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrate that it has agreements in which it has been laid down that people who work overtime do so on a voluntary basis and that they do not work more than twelve hours in overtime a week; • Monitor and record the working hours of all employees; • Overtime shall be compensated at a premium rate.
Property and usage rights	<p><i>Land use rights (including land tenure)</i> Existing land rights and land-use rights, both formal and informal, shall be assessed, documented, and established. Acquiring the land involves a process for consulting and gaining free, prior and informed consent.</p>
	<p><i>Water use rights</i> The economic operator shall respect existing water rights, both formal and customary.</p>
Wellbeing of the local population	<p><i>Health and safety of local community</i> The organization shall determine and lay down the extent to which the commercial operation of the production location influences the local population such matters as health and safety relating to the infrastructure, hazardous substances and emissions.</p>
	<p><i>Local services (health, education, infrastructure, ..) / Prosperity</i> The organization shall demonstrate that its activities have a positive impact on the access to infrastructure and basic facilities (clean and safe accommodation, access to drinking water, sanitary facilities, education, healthcare, water, energy, etc.) in the region concerned.</p>
	<p><i>Local values</i> The organization shall unambiguously and in consultation with the local population identify locations that represent a special cultural, ecological, economic or religious interest to the local population and have them recognized and protected by the managers responsible.</p>
	<p><i>Community involvement / Stakeholder engagement</i> The organization shall establish consultations and dialogue with local communities and stakeholders (e.g., suggestions, complaints and remarks from local communities)</p>
Food security	<p><i>Food security</i> Operations shall assess risks to food security in the region and locality and shall mitigate any negative impacts that result from their operations. In food insecure regions, operations shall enhance the local food security of the directly affected stakeholders. This involves the simultaneous fulfilment of four dimensions of food security: food availability; food access; food utilization; and the stability of food availability, access and utilization.</p>

In the sub-sections below, a description is given on how the definitions of the social principles and criteria in Table 4 were made through the review of the legislation, standards, certification schemes and studies described in section 2.1.

Compliance with labour rights

This principle covers criteria on Child labour, Forced and compulsory labour, Fair salary and remuneration, Association and collective bargaining and Equal opportunities/discrimination. They are covered in all reviewed documents (except legislation). The certification schemes give reference to the relevant ILO conventions i.e., ILO 138 & 182 for Child labour, ILO 29 & 105 for Forced and compulsory labour, ILO 87 & 98 Association and collective bargaining and ILO 111 & 100 Equal opportunities/discrimination. The criteria in Table 4 were accordingly defined following these ILO conventions. Additionally, a criterion on Grievance mechanism is included which is explicitly covered in the certification schemes. It was described following the NTA 8080-1/Better biomass and RSB.

Working conditions

This principle covers criteria on Contract, Training, Occupational health and safety, Harassment/violence and Work and overtime. Contract and Training are explicitly addressed in ISO 13065 and some schemes and is defined following ISCC and NTA 8080-1/Better biomass. The

criteria on Occupational health and safety for workers are covered in almost all documents and follow the relevant ILO conventions. This criterion was defined collecting the specific considerations present in these documents related to adequate protective equipment and training, procedures for emergencies, functioning of machines and clean sanitary facilities. The criteria on Harassment and violence are defined following ISCC and are also covered in most of the other sustainability schemes. The criterion on Hours of work and overtime is defined following Better Biomass and is complemented with ISCC including the last bullet concerning a premium rate for overtime. This criterion is also covered in most other sustainability schemes.

Property and usage rights

This principle includes both Land use and Water use rights. The criterion on Land use (including land tenure) is covered in all reviewed standards, schemes and studies whereas Water use rights is only explicitly addressed by the standards ISO 13065, EN16751, scheme ISCC and study FAO. The criterion on Land use rights is described following RSB complemented with ISO 13065, whereas the criterion on Water use rights is described following ISCC.

Wellbeing of the local population

This principle covers criteria on Health and safety of local community, Local services (health, education, infrastructure, ..), Local values and Stakeholder engagement. The criterion on Health and safety of local community is defined following NTA 8080-1/Better Biomass and is also specifically addressed in ISCC, FSC and STAR-ProBio. STAR-ProBio also has a separate criterion on health and safety of end users. The criterion on Local services/Prosperity is also described following NTA 8080-1/Better Biomass and is specifically addressed in EN 16751, RSB, ISCC and S2BIOM. Local values refer to especially the cultural or religious values of local population which is separately addressed in the certification schemes. The description of this criteria is made following NTA 8080-1/Better Biomass. The criteria on Community involvement / Stakeholder engagement are covered in almost all of the reviewed documents and were defined generically following the definitions provided in these documents.

Food security

The principle of Food Security is implicitly or explicitly addressed in most of the reviewed documents and was described in Table 4 following the definition provided in RSB with the last sentence on the four dimensions of food security added from FAO study.

2.5 Economic Principles and Criteria

Economic dimension was found to be the one least addressed in the reviewed documents. It is not covered in the legislation, and limitedly addressed in standards and studies mostly related to Economic viability and Integrity principles. Some of the principles that were defined i.e., Use of knowledge and technology and Fair trade and market practices were explicitly covered in only one or two of the reviewed documents. The collation of the economic principles and criteria made is presented in Table 5.

Table 5 Compilation of economic principles and criteria from review of documents

Economic sustainability principle	Sustainability criteria
Financial and economic viability (Economic sustainability, continual improvement)	Produce and trade biobased products in an economically and financially viable way. Organisations shall develop and implement a business plan that reflects a commitment to long-term economic viability.
Fair business practices, Integrity (fraudulent, deceptive, or dishonest)	The organisation provides information on how fraudulent, deceptive or dishonest consumer or commercial business practice is addressed. The organization shall take any measures that are necessary to effectively fight corruption within the organization.
Inclusive economic growth	<i>Local employment and procurement</i> The organisation supports economic development of local communities by providing opportunities for local employment and promoting the purchase of local materials, goods, products and services.
	<i>Community investment</i> The socioeconomic status of local stakeholders impacted by the operations shall be improved e.g., by education and skills development programs
Use of knowledge and technology	<i>Compensate indigenous knowledge</i> The organization shall compensate the local population for the application of their traditional knowledge.
	<i>Use of technology</i> The use of technologies shall seek to maximise production efficiency and social and environmental performance and minimise the risk of damages to the environment and people.
Fair trade and market practices	The economic operator provides information on how fair competition in the market is addressed (regarding anti-competitive behaviour and violations of anti-trust and monopoly legislation).
Risk assessment and management	The organisation shall have procedures to identify potential financial risks and strategies in place to manage and mitigate these.

In the sub-sections below, a description is given on how the definitions of the economic principles and criteria in Table 5 were made through the review of the legislation, standards, certification schemes and studies described in section 2.1.

Financial and economic viability (Economic sustainability, continual improvement)

This principle is covered in most of the reviewed documents either implicitly or explicitly. The definition in Table 5 is made following the standards ISO 13065 and EN 16751 complemented with ISCC regarding development of a business plan and long-term economic viability.

Fair business practices, Integrity (fraudulent, deceptive, or dishonest)

This principle is explicitly covered in the reviewed standards, schemes and in STAR-ProBio study. The definition in Table 5 is made following the standards ISO 13065 and EN 16751 complemented with NTA 8080-1 regarding measure to fight corruption.

Inclusive economic growth

This principle covers the criteria on Local employment and procurement, and Community investment which are complementary to each other. They are covered in EN 16751, NTA 8080-1/Better Biomass, RSB, ISCC, FSC and STAR-ProBio where creating employment and education, skills development to local communities are addressed together. The aspect of public procurement is specifically provided in NTA 8080-1 and STAR-ProBio. The term Inclusive economic growth is provided in the FAO study.

Use of knowledge and technology

This principle includes the criteria on Compensation of indigenous knowledge and Use of technology which are covered in only few of the reviewed documents. Criterion on Compensation of indigenous

knowledge is defined following NTA 8080-1 and is also covered in FSC and FAO study. The criterion on use of technology is explicitly covered in RSB and defined following this scheme.

Fair trade and market practices

This principle is explicitly addressed only in STAR-ProBio concerning anti-competitive behaviour and violations of anti-trust and monopoly legislation.

Risk assessment and management

This principle is described following ISO 13065. It is also explicitly covered in the FAO study. For others, it is implicitly covered within a business plan.

3. Identification and selection of existing sustainability certification schemes and labels for biobased systems

3.1 Sustainability systems, certification schemes and labels

Sustainability systems are market-based initiatives that address sustainability issues by setting a standard or establishing a similar tool that defines performance levels or pathways for improvement.¹ Sustainability certification schemes and labels are voluntary tools used by producers, manufacturers, traders, retailers, and service providers to demonstrate sustainability. Certification scheme is a third party scheme providing assurance of conformance to a normative standard. The organisation determines the objectives and scope of the certification system and applicable standards, as well as the rules for how the system will operate and the standards against which conformance will be assessed. As a result of the certification process, a label on a product shows compliance with the requirements set by the respective certification scheme. Labels are used for the communication of certain product characteristics to consumer and customers.

The definition to certification provided by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) is the provision by an independent body of written assurance (a certificate) that the product, service or system in question meets specific requirements.² An independent third-party (called a certification body) assesses the product in relation to a set of predetermined requirements (the standard). The certification body accordingly gives written assurance that a product conforms to the requirements specified in the standard.

3.2 Development of sustainability certification in the bioeconomy

In the past decade, the role and importance of certification and labelling to ensure a sustainable bioeconomy in Europe has kept growing. The Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) certification scheme came into the market in 1994 for responsible management of forests, and in 1999 The Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC) started. Later many sustainability certification schemes related to food and agricultural products were introduced by international non-profit, multi-stakeholder organizations such as RSPO – Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil, RTRS – Round Table on Responsible Soy Association, and Bonsucro. Although there is no legally binding requirement to use sustainability certifications, they became increasingly demanded in the market. There are also instances where they can be used to show fulfillment of requirements of regulations, for example use of FSC and PEFC to help show that companies have complied with their due diligence obligation under the European Timber Regulation.

From around 2009 (also related to the introduction of the Renewable Energy Directive), voluntary sustainability certification schemes for bioenergy and biofuels were developed (e.g., Roundtable on

¹ ISEAL Credibility Principles v2 2021, www.isealalliance.org/definingcredible-practice/iseal-credibility-principles

² ISO, Certification, <https://www.iso.org/certification.html>

Sustainable Biomaterial (RSB), International Sustainability and Carbon Certification (ISCC), Better Biomass and REDcert). Some of which, originally developed to assure responsible/sustainable cultivation of the feedstock for food purposes, were later adapted to cover these applications (e.g., Bonsucro, RTRS and RSPO). Currently, for bioenergy and biofuels, EC recognizes several voluntary schemes to be used by companies to demonstrate compliance with the sustainability criteria set out in the RED. Recently EC laid down implementing rules¹ to ensure the correct and harmonized functioning of these voluntary schemes. It is clear that over 10 years of sustainability certification for bioenergy products has led to a reasonable level of harmonization. It should be noted that the mandatory sustainability criteria of REDII is limited to certain environmental aspects, and other environmental criteria (such as soil, water, and air quality) as well as social and economic criteria are not included. These additional sustainability principles beyond REDII requirements are already established in most of the voluntary sustainability schemes for biofuels.

Recently, several voluntary schemes for biofuels have already created add-ons or extended their scope to biobased products. These include RSB Advanced Products, ISCC Plus, Better Biomass and REDCert². Moreover, sustainability certification schemes related to forest and agricultural products are also applicable for their application in biobased products.

Furthermore, a key component for the market uptake of biobased products is to communicate the sustainability benefits to the consumer. For this, ecolabels are important tools and can promote responsible production and consumption. Ecolabels are defined as “seals of approval given to products that are deemed to have lower impacts on the environment than functionally or competitively similar products”. The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) distinguished between three types of ecolabels. A 'Type I' label is a third-party assessment of a product based on several criteria/issues involved in the environmental impact of a product or material throughout its life cycle. In Europe the three dominant multi-issue ecolabels of ISO 14024 Type I are: The EU Ecolabel, the Nordic Ecolabel, and the Blue Angel Ecolabel. Specific product categories that include biobased products under these labels are amongst others wooden products, lubricants, paints, textiles and disposables for food. Different labels put emphasis on different environmental impacts of the products. Also, the environmental hotspots are strongly dependent on the product category, which is why each product group has different criteria to fulfil.

Several international and EU sustainability standards have accordingly been developed and are applied currently for biological feedstock and biobased products through voluntary certification schemes and labels. They allow traceability and transparency of sustainability impacts along the value chains and trades within the EU and globally which in turn is vital for responsible production and consumption. They serve as major tools for global production and trade to become more sustainable, and for the private sector to demonstrate corporate social responsibility.

3.3 Creation of a Long list

The initial exercise was to gain a picture of existing sustainability certification schemes and labels that can be applicable to either biobased products and materials, or biological feedstock that can be used for these products.

Accordingly, a list of criteria was defined for initial identification of these schemes and labels.

The main criteria used are the following:

¹ EC (2021) Draft implementing regulation on rules to verify sustainability and greenhouse gas emissions saving criteria and low indirect land-use change-risk criteria (Ares(2021)4234307)

1. Schemes/labels are Applicable to biological resources intended for industrial biobased value chains or Applicable to biobased materials and products
2. Ecolabels – Type 1 Ecolabels as specified in ISO14024 standards
3. Exclude schemes/labels specifically developed for food/feed and biofuel/bioenergy sector
4. Geographical coverage at least EU or global – Exclude the ones that are specific to a single country or only applicable outside EU
5. Full supply chain coverage – Exclude the ones that are focused on one stage of lifecycle (e.g., end of life)
6. Principles and criteria concerning all sustainability dimensions – Exclude schemes that are focused on one sustainability criteria (e.g., climate impact)

Moreover, the below criteria were considered in screening existing schemes/labels:

- a. Focus on most prominent biobased value chains (niche applications could be excluded)
- b. Focus on the schemes most prominent in the market (based on the number of active certificates)
- c. Have a mixture of different categories of biological resources
- d. Have representation of the 6 biobased sectors (chemicals, plastics, textiles, construction, woodworking and pulp & paper)
- e. Exclude schemes labels specific to organic production and labelling of organic products
- f. Exclude business to consumer specific schemes, labels
- g. Exclude company owned private standard (e.g., Cargill, ADM, Bunge)
- h. Exclude ones that are assessment tools/initiatives but not a standard (SAFA, SAI, Bioplastic Feedstock Alliance, Together for Sustainability Initiative)

The main source used for the identification of relevant schemes/labels was the ITC Standards Map¹ which at the time of this review (Dec 2022) included 322 standards. This was complemented by reviewing also the following sources:

- ISEAL members²
- GEN members³
- STAR-ProBio project deliverables⁴
- Online Indexes of Certificates and Labels: www.ecolabelindex.com, www.labelinfo.be/, <https://index.impakter.com/certificates-2>

Sustainability certification schemes identified by application of the criteria are provided in the long list in Table 6.

¹ ITC Standards Map, <https://www.standardmap.org/en/identify>

² ISEAL Community Members, <https://www.isealalliance.org/iseal-community-members>

³ Global Ecolabelling Network members, <https://globalecolabelling.net/organisations/>

⁴ STAR-ProBio (2017), STAR-ProBio Deliverable D1.1, Report on identified environmental, social and economic criteria/ indicators/requirements and related "Gap Analysis". Available from Internet: www.star-probio.eu.

Table 6: Sustainability certification schemes in Long list

Category	Sub-category	Name scheme	Geography	Biological Feedstock	Value chain	
Biological feedstock	Forest	FSC	Global	Wood	Full	
		PEFC	Global	Wood	Full	
	Agriculture – fair trade	-	Bonsucro	Global	Sugarcane	Full
			RSPO	Global	Palm	Full
			RTRS	Global	Soybean	Full
			ProTerra	Global	Crops (e.g., sugarcane, soybean)	Full
			Rainforest Alliance	Global	Crops (e.g., palm, sugarcane, soybean)	Cultivation to distribution
			GlobalG.A.P Crops	Global	Crops	Cultivation to distribution
			Fair Trade International	Global	Multiple (e.g., cotton, sugarcane)	Full
			WFTO Guaranteed System	Global	Multiple	Full
Agriculture cotton	-	Fair for Life	Global	Multiple	Full	
		Better Cotton	Global	Cotton	Cultivation to distribution	
		CmiA	Africa	Cotton	Cultivation to distribution	
		MSC	Global	Fish	Full	
Biobased product	Marine	ASC	Global	Aquaculture	Full	
		GlobalG.A.P. Aquaculture	Global	Aquaculture	Full	
	General		ISCC Plus	Global	Multiple	Full
			RSB Advanced products	Global	Multiple	Full
			Better Biomass	Global	Multiple	Full
			REDCert ²	Europe	Multiple	Full
			Cradle to cradle	Global		Product
			BREEAM	Global		Building
			LEED	Global		Building
			DGNB Certificate	Global		Building
Natureplus	Global		Building products			
Textile		Fair Trade Textile	Global	FT cotton, other responsible fibres	Textile	
		Textile Exchange	Global	Multiple (wool, down, recycled)	Textile	
		bluesign	Global		Textile	
Cleaning products		A.I.S.E. Charter for Sustainable Cleaning standard	Europe		Cleaning products	

Ecolabels that are member of Global Ecolabelling Network, classify as Type 1 ecolabels according to ISO 14024¹, and contain product categories relevant for industrial biobased systems were identified and provided in Table 7.

Table 7: Type-I Ecolabels in Europe

Name	Geography
EU Ecolabel	EU
Nordic Swan Ecolabel	Nordic countries
Blue Angel	Germany
Good Environmental Choice	Sweden
Green Product Mark	Germany
Milieukeur	Netherlands
PlanetProof	Netherlands
Green Crane	Ukraine
Turkish Environmental Label	Turkey

3.4 Further screening to a Short list

It is aimed to produce factsheets on the most relevant and prominent schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems following detailed review of standard documents. Given also the time and resource constraints of this task, it was required to have a condensed list. The long list has been accordingly further screened and shortened considering the following criteria:

- The most relevant schemes for industrial biobased systems (exclude schemes for biological feedstock that are most prominently targeted for food/feed applications)
- Coverage of different type of feedstock (one scheme is selected for one type of feedstock where several prominent schemes exist e.g., FSC and PEFC for wood)
- Coverage of different sustainability dimensions (sustainability certification schemes that focus mostly on one dimension were excluded)
- Focus on the schemes/labels that are prominent in the market (based on the number of active certificates)

This has resulted in the following selection of schemes/labels in the short list:

- Biobased products and materials:
 1. ISCC Plus
 2. RSB Advanced
 3. Better Biomass
 4. Textile Exchange GRS
- Biological feedstock for industrial biobased systems:
 5. FSC (wood)
 6. RSPO (palm)
 7. Bonsucro (sugarcane)
 8. Better Cotton (cotton)
- Ecolabels:
 9. EU Ecolabel
 10. Blue Angel Ecolabel
 11. Nordic Swan Ecolabel

They are highlighted in Table 6 and 7, and their logos are presented in Figure 2.

¹ ISO 14024:2018 Environmental Labels and Declarations—Type 1 Environmental Labelling

Figure 2. Shortlisted sustainability certification schemes and labels

The other schemes and labels included in the long list (Table 6) are all applicable for industrial biobased systems. Factsheets have been produced only for the shortlisted schemes and labels in this deliverable (provided in section 6). The template generated and provided in section 4.2 can be used for generating factsheets for the additional schemes and labels in this long list.

4. Review and analysis of selected schemes and labels

4.1 Approach

Factsheets were prepared on the shortlisted sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems with the goal to provide a quick overview of them. The factsheets are intended to provide besides general information and scope, also information on the governance of the schemes and their sustainability principles. Factsheets were prepared using current version of system documents and information provided on the websites of reviewed sustainability certification schemes and labels.

The description of the sections and different items of the factsheet is provided in section 4.2. The section on 'Governance, Standard Development and Certification Requirements' was developed by using the WWF Certification Assessment Tool [1] as a major reference. The section on 'Sustainability principles and criteria' was defined following the review of selected legislation, standards, schemes and studies as described in chapter 2 and the accordingly collated sustainability principles and criteria. This factsheet template was developed to be applicable for industrial biobased systems considering the full life cycle and all sustainability dimensions. For the sustainability certification schemes developed for biological resource, some of the sustainability criteria were not applicable. In these cases, this was marked as not applicable (n/a). Also, for ecolabels, the focus is on the environmental sustainability criteria, explanation was accordingly provided for the less or no coverage of the criteria in other sustainability dimensions as these being not in main scope of these ecolabels.

The factsheets of the 11 shortlisted sustainability certification schemes and labels are provided in Chapter 6. It is ordered as 4 sustainability certification schemes for biobased products and materials (ISCC Plus, RSB Advanced Products, Better Biomass and Textile Exchange GRS), followed by 4 sustainability certification schemes for biological feedstock (FSC (wood), RSPO (palm), Bonsucro (sugarcane), Better Cotton (cotton)) and then 3 ecolabels (EU Ecolabel, Blue Angel, Nordic Swan).

All these certification schemes do have somewhat different approaches with regard to the scope of sustainability criteria they cover and to the system operating requirements i.e., their rules on the audit system, certification procedures, governance structure, requirements for the auditors, etc. (where an overview is provided in the factsheets provided in chapter 6).

All the factsheets were internally reviewed, and crosschecks were carried out for consistency in the information provided at each factsheet. Additional checks for some schemes were carried out by Control Unions scheme experts. For the external review of the factsheets, we reached out to scheme owners in our network by Control Union providing the linkage with their program managers for the schemes ISCC Plus, Textile Exchange GRS, FSC, RSPO, and Bonsucro. Also, direct contact with scheme owners RSB and NEN was achieved (who are associated partners in sister project STAR4BBS) for the review of RSB Advanced Products and Better Biomass factsheets, respectively. Additionally, Nordic Ecolabelling was contacted (being a member of the Joint Advisory Board) for the review of the Nordic Swan Ecolabel factsheet. The scheme owners were given a copy of the factsheets pertaining to their respective scheme to provide a chance to review and provide their feedback. Comments received were integrated in the finalization of the factsheets.

4.2 Factsheet Sections and Description of Items

The factsheets provide information on the governance, standard development and certification procedures as well as on the content of the standard with regard to sustainability principles and criteria.

Factsheets are divided into the following sections:

- **General:** Provides general information on the scheme's name, owner, website and label as well as number of active certificates and general objective.
- **Scope:** Provides information on the biomass feedstock, product group and supply chain coverage and geographical scope of the scheme.
- **Governance, Standard Development and Certification Requirements:**
- **Sustainability Principles and Criteria:** Provides an overview of the sustainability principles and criteria covered in the scheme divided into the following sub-sections:
 - **Environmental:** criteria concerning greenhouse gas emissions, protection of land with high carbon stock or high biodiversity value, sustainable forest management, soil, water and air quality
 - **Circularity:** criteria concerning waste reduction and management, material and energy efficiency and use of renewable and recycled raw materials
 - **Social:** criteria concerning labour rights, wellbeing of workers and the local population, and food security
 - **Economic:** criteria concerning financial and economic viability, fair business practices, inclusive economic growth and risk management

The following table provides description of each item of the factsheet within each of the section and sub-sections described above.

Table 8: Description of the items of a factsheet

Scheme Feature	Description
General	
Name of scheme	Name of scheme
Scheme owner	Information on the scheme owner
Website	Website
Label provided	Figure of the label provided
Operational since	Year it came into operation
Number of active certificates	Number of active certificates based on available online information
Standard ownership	Private or public ownership
General objective	General objective of the scheme as defined on its website
Scope	
Biomass feedstock coverage	All biomass types or a specific type of feedstock
Sector/Product group coverage	All applications (all industrial biobased or also including food and energy), or for specific category of product/application
Supply chain coverage	Full supply chain coverage or other
Geographic focus of the standard	Global, national or regional
Governance, Standard Development and Certification Requirements	
Scheme governance	General information on the governance structure
Standard documents	In order to guarantee clarity and effectiveness of the certification scheme the standard should consist of the following documents: a. Rules (general regulations, requirements, guidelines for verification); b. Checklists (Principles and criteria, control points and compliance criteria); c. Definitions: clarification of the used definitions; d. In case of international and globally operating standards, national or local interpretation documents

Scheme Feature	Description
	clarifying how standards have to be adapted in a specific context to assure local relevance and appropriateness [1].
Transparency and accessibility of standard documents	The standard should make its documents publicly available in an easily accessible manner: a. Documents are accessible for free and specify requirements. b. Where necessary, documents are available in different languages.
Multi-stakeholder participation in standard development	Creation and revision of the standard should be done by a meaningful stakeholder participation from a balanced, diverse group of stakeholders. This can be demonstrated via: composition of board/ (technical advisory) committees, decision-making processes, or publicly available documentation that show that stakeholder consultations take place. [1]
Compliance with ISEAL's Standards-Setting, Impacts and Assurance Codes of Good Practice	The development of the standard should comply with existing international norms developed by the ISEAL Standard Setting Code of Good Practice (latest version 6, revised in December 2014) [2] or a comparable recognized standard for Setting Social and Environmental Standards. [1]
Compliance with regional, national, international laws	The standard should require compliance with all applicable regional and national laws in the country in which operations occur, as well as conventions and international treaties to which the relevant country has signed. [1]
Reference to standards and policies	References to applicable standards and policies should be cited in system documents.
Obligation for certification	Standards for the primary production as well as the industrial operators and traders along the value chain (chain of custody) should be developed and available.
Certification process	General information on the steps involved in the certification process
Traceability and Chain of custody	The standard should have a robust process for tracing the product along the supply chain to ensure truthful claims [1]. Based on the standard requirements audits may require either physical segregation of products in production processes throughout the supply chain ("physical segregation") or mixed in production but separated in bookkeeping ("mass balance approach").
Verification of compliance	The standard requires independent third-party certification bodies auditing the companies.
Accreditation of Certification Bodies	The standard requires third-party accreditation bodies accrediting the certification bodies (ISO 17065 compliance).
Training of auditors and staff and qualification and evaluation of competencies	a. Auditors and staff are regularly trained concerning the standard's requirements, processes, procedures; b. A document describing the key tasks and responsibilities and qualifications of the system manager, auditors and inspectors is in place.; c. Auditors competences are evaluated by shadow audits
Audit process	General information on the auditing system and process
Frequency of audit	The standard requires independent third-party certification bodies auditing the companies annually.
Internal audit	The standard requires at a minimum annual internal audits to be executed, documented, and followed up by the companies.
Certification claims and labels	The certification scheme provides requirements for the use of certification claims and the use of labels. Procedures for logo use and claims are in place.
Sanctions, non-conformities and suspension	Clear sanctions exist for identified non-compliance at the level of audit and certification. Deadlines to correct the non-conformity depend on the gravity of the non-conformity. Failure to comply with the standard's requirements can potentially lead to the suspension of companies certification.
Complaint and appeal mechanisms	The standard as well as the certified company have a mechanism for hearing complaints and resolving conflicts. a. The standard published the complaints mechanism on the website of the standard. The procedures provide deadlines for handling complaints and include the possibility to forward the complaint to an independent body/person; b. The certified company has a compliant procedure in place and a documented record keeping system shows how complaints are resolved. [1]
Guarantee smallholder inclusiveness of the standard	Standards for individual certification as well as group certification are developed and available.
Promote continuous improvement	To promote continuous improvement: a. A standard review process takes place at least every five years.; b. The standard differentiates between entrance criteria's and more strict development criteria's applicable after a certain amount of time; or c. The standard criteria includes continuous improvement.
Assurance of quality	The standard system requires that the certification body as well as the certified companies implement a quality management system in order to assure quality.
Impact assessment	To minimize or eliminate the most important environmental and social negative impacts of the commodity, product or sector, the standard system should have a written commitment to adhere reducing key economic, environmental and social impacts by e.g., clearly stated mission, vision and/or set of objectives. [1]
Risk management	The standard system requires that the certification body as well as the certified companies implement risk management.
Cost of certification	Information on the cost of certification and where to reach the latest amounts.

Scheme Feature	Description
Sustainability Principles and Criteria	
Reference Document	Information on the document(s) where the sustainability principles are reported.
Major Must and Minor Must	Information whether the standard distinguishes between major must and minor must sustainability criteria.
Environmental	
Reduce GHG emissions	The economic operator provides information on how greenhouse gas emissions and removals related to their operations are managed.
Protection of land with high carbon stock	Raw material shall not be obtained from land with high-carbon stock, namely land that had one of the following statuses in January 2008 and no longer has that status: wetlands, continuously forested areas, and other (sparsely) forested areas.
Protection of peatland	Raw material shall not be obtained from land that was peatland in January 2008, unless evidence is provided that the cultivation and harvesting of that raw material does not involve drainage of previously undrained soil.
Promote sustainable forest management	The country in which forest biomass was harvested has national or sub-national laws applicable in the area of harvest as well as monitoring and enforcement systems in place ensuring forest regeneration and long-term production capacity of forests
Protection of land with a high biodiversity value	Raw material shall not be obtained from land with high biodiversity value, namely land that had one of the following statuses on 1 January 2008 or later a) primary forest and other wooded land, b) areas designated by law or by the relevant competent authority for nature protection purposes & Areas for the protection of rare, threatened or endangered ecosystems or species, c) highly biodiverse grassland, and d) legally recognized conservation value areas (or effectively protected by other means)
Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity	The economic operator provides information on how biodiversity values are addressed within the area of operation and the environment directly influenced by the economic operator (Include considerations for buffer zones, ecological corridors, invasive species).
Sustainable use of water	The economic operator provides information on how quantity of water drawn and released are addressed. Ensure that surface and groundwater use does not exceed the natural replenishment capacities; Application of good agricultural practices to reduce water usage and to maintain and improve water quality; Documentation of water management plans aimed at using water efficiently
Maintaining and enhancing water quality	The economic operator provides information on how quality of water drawn and released are addressed. Prevention of surface and ground water contamination/pollution as a consequence of the storage and use of chemicals and other biological agents; Buffer zones shall be set between the operation site and surface or groundwater resources.; Wastewater or runoff that contains potential organic and mineral contaminants shall be treated or recycled
Maintaining and enhancing soil quality and productivity	Operators shall implement practices to maintain or enhance soil's physical, chemical, and biological conditions (Include consideration of erosion, nutrient balance, soil organic matter, structure, salination).
Soil quality consideration for use of residual flows	The use of residues does not occur at the expense of the soil nutrient balance, soil organic matter balance or important traditional uses (such as fodder, natural fertiliser, material or local fuel), unless documentation is available to suggest that similar or better alternatives are available and are applied.
Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals	None of the chemicals recorded in the WHO's 1a and 1b lists, Annex III of the Rotterdam Convention, Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants or the Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer shall be used.
Implement best practices for the use of (agro)chemicals	Good practices shall be implemented for the storage, handling, use, and disposal of (agro)chemicals (Include consideration of integrated pest management).
Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality	The organization shall take any measures that are necessary to ensure that the emission of harmful substances into the air as a result of the production, processing and transport of biomass is limited.
Limit the risk of Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC)	The economic operator provides information on its strategies adopted to reach a "low ILUC risk" level. Strategies to ensure low ILUC-risk include yield increase, use of unused land, and use of waste and residues.
Circularity	
Promote waste reduction and responsible waste management	The organization shall take any measures that are necessary to ensure that the practices applied in its operations are aimed at responsible waste management (prevention of waste, reuse, recycling, recovery).
Raw material efficiency	The economic operator provides information on how material efficiency related to their operations are addressed. Biomass should be used as resource efficient as possible over the entire life cycle and continued to be used.
Efficient use of energy	The economic operator provides information on how energy use and efficiency are addressed and there is a plan to improve energy efficiency
Promote use of renewable sources	The economic operator provides information on how the use of renewable energy sources is promoted and efforts are made to reduce fossil energy consumption.

Scheme Feature	Description
Promote material circularity	The economic operator provides information on the use of recycled materials and how an effective recyclability of the bio-based product is achieved.
Social	
Compliance with labour rights	Criteria on Child labour, Forced and compulsory labour, Fair salary and remuneration, Association and collective bargaining, Equal opportunities/discrimination and Grievance mechanism
Respect wellbeing of workers	Criteria on Contract, Training, Occupational health and safety, Harassment/violence and Work and overtime
Respect property and usage rights	Land use (including land tenure) and water use rights
Respect wellbeing of the local population	Criteria on Health and safety of local community, Local services (health, education, infrastructure, ..) and Engagement with local community
Food security	Operations shall assess risks to food security in the region and locality and shall mitigate any negative impacts that result from their operations. In food insecure regions, operations shall enhance the local food security of the directly affected stakeholders.
Economic	
Financial and economic viability	Produce and trade biobased products in an economically and financially viable way. Organisations shall develop and implement a business plan that reflects a commitment to long-term economic viability.
Fair business practices, Integrity	The organisation provides information on how fraudulent, deceptive or dishonest consumer or commercial business practice is addressed. The organization shall take any measures that are necessary to effectively fight corruption within the organization.
Promote local development, Inclusive economic growth	The organisation supports economic development of local communities by providing opportunities for local employment and promoting the purchase of local materials, goods, products and services. The socioeconomic status of local stakeholders impacted by the operations shall be improved e.g., by education and skills development programs.
Use of knowledge and technology	The use of technologies shall seek to maximise production efficiency and social and environmental performance and minimise the risk of damages to the environment and people. The organization shall compensate the local population for the application of their traditional knowledge.
Fair trade and market practices	The economic operator provides information on how fair competition in the market is addressed (regarding anti-competitive behaviour and violations of anti-trust and monopoly legislation)
Risk assessment and management	The organisation shall have procedures to identify potential financial risks and strategies in place to manage and mitigate these.

References:

1. WWF, Certification Assessment Tool (version 2.1), 2013
2. ISEAL, Setting Social and Environmental Standards, ISEAL Code of Good Practice, v6.0, 2014

5. Conclusions

In this report, in order to outline sustainability requirements applicable to biological resources and to biobased materials and products, a collation of principles and criteria (P&C) were made considering relevant legislation (RED II, Taxonomy), standards (ISO 13065, EN 16751 and NTA 8080-1), exemplary certification schemes and studies in the field of sustainable bioeconomy (STAR-ProBio, S2BIOM, GBEP, FAO Sustainable Bioeconomy). Besides the documents that are specifically developed for biobased products, also prominent examples of the ones developed for bioenergy/biofuels and food were taken into consideration to incorporate the longer experience in sustainability assessment and certification in these sectors. Principles and criteria were defined under 4 sections: environmental, circularity, social and economic. Attention was paid to ensure the contribution of biobased products to circular economy by including circularity as a fourth dimension.

Next, identification of existing sustainability certification schemes and labels for biobased systems was carried out by developing a list of criteria for screening. The scope is global considering the full life cycle and all value chain actors. Schemes specifically developed for food/feed and biofuel/bioenergy sector were excluded. ITC Standards Map was the main source used for the identification of relevant schemes/labels and preparation of the long list. Following this a further screening was done to identify the most relevant schemes for industrial biobased systems also considering coverage of different type of feedstock and sectors and prominence in the market. This resulted in 11 shortlisted sustainability certification schemes and labels: 4 for biobased products and materials (ISCC Plus, RSB Advanced Products, Better Biomass and Textile Exchange GRS), 4 for biological feedstock (FSC (wood), RSPO (palm), Bonsucro (sugarcane), Better Cotton (cotton)) and 3 ecolabels (EU Ecolabel, Blue Angel, Nordic Swan).

Finally, factsheets were prepared on the shortlisted sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems with the goal to provide a quick overview of them. The factsheets include different sections providing beside general information and scope, also information on the governance of the schemes and their sustainability principles.

The sustainability principles and criteria collated will be useful in designing the content level of the monitoring system as part of WP3 – Task 3.2 *Developing a new monitoring system*. The factsheets prepared for the selected schemes and labels will provide essential information for their testing as part of Task 3.3 *Testing the developed monitoring system and indicators on reviewed schemes and labels*.

6. Factsheets

6.1 Factsheet ISCC PLUS

This factsheet aims to provide accessible and factual information on the ISCC PLUS scheme. This factsheet presents the actual status of the scheme in April 2023. For more detailed information on the system, the reader may visit the website of the certification scheme or contact the scheme owner.

Disclaimer: The information contained in this factsheet is for informational purpose only and cannot be used in replacement of the official ISCC standards and procedures

Table 9 Factsheet ISCC Plus

Scheme Feature	Description
General	
Name of scheme	ISCC Plus
Scheme owner	The ISCC Association (ISCC e.V.) is the legally registered body responsible for governing ISCC – The International Sustainability and Carbon Certification System. ISCC is a standard setting organisation responsible for the development, surveillance, revision and continuous improvement of the ISCC Certification Systems. ISCC operates different certification systems for different markets. These systems are ISCC EU, ISCC PLUS, ISCC CORSIA, ISCC CORSIA PLUS, and ISCC Solid Biomass NL.
Website	https://www.iscc-system.org/
Label provided	
Operational since	2012
Number of active certificates	2768 (Feb 2023)
Standard ownership	Private
General objective	The ISCC objective is 'Contributing to the implementation of environmentally, socially and economically sustainable production and use of all kinds of biomass in global supply chains'.
Scope	
Biomass feedstock coverage	The ISCC certification system covers all sustainable feedstocks, including agricultural and forestry biomass, biogenic wastes, circular materials and renewables.
Sector/Product group coverage	ISCC PLUS certification is applicable for the bioeconomy and circular economy for food, feed, chemicals, industrial applications (e.g., plastics or packaging) and energy from renewable sources used outside of the European Union (i.e. markets that are not regulated by the RED II).
Supply chain coverage	The ISCC Certification Systems are applicable to all elements of the supply chains
Geographic focus of the standard	Global
Governance, Standard Development and Certification Requirements	

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Scheme governance	ISCC is governed by the ISCC Association (ISCC e.V.) with more than 175 members, including international associations, corporations, research institutions and NGOs. The day-to-day operations, management and development of the ISCC system are assigned to the ISCC System GmbH. More details on the governance of ISCC can be found on the ISCC EU System Document 102 "Governance"
Standard documents	ISCC provides System Documents defining the general and technical requirements of each system on its website: https://www.iscc-system.org/process/iscc-documents-at-a-glance/iscc-system-documents/ . ISCC EU System Documents also serve as system documents for the ISCC PLUS scheme. The few differences and requirements that are specific to ISCC PLUS are described in the ISCC PLUS System Document. ISCC also develops Guidance Documents and additional documents to further specify requirements for System Users, Certification Bodies and auditors.
Transparency and accessibility of standard documents	Transparency through freely accessible ISCC Documents and information about certificate holders e.g., through publication of certificates and Summary Audit Reports
Multi-stakeholder participation in standard development	ISCC is an independent multi-stakeholder initiative that has been developed and is being continuously improved with the involvement of its stakeholders
Compliance with ISEAL's Standards-Setting, Impacts and Assurance Codes of Good Practice	During the development of its systems, ISCC takes into account and complements best practice initiatives like the ISEAL Alliance. ISCC is currently not an ISEAL community member.
Compliance with regional, national, international laws	This is covered by the ISCC Principle 5: compliance with, all applicable local, regional and national laws and ratified international treaties
Reference to standards and policies	ISCC EU System Document 201 "System Basics" lists the Reference Documents from the European Commission including binding legislation and communications
Obligation for certification	All relevant elements of the supply chain must obtain a certificate in order to handle sustainable materials. Farms/plantations, forest operations and points of origin for waste and residues, first gathering points or central offices and collecting points, processing units, traders and storage facilities are subject to certification.
Certification process	There are four steps to achieving ISCC certification. Step 1. Company registers with ISCC as System User, Step 2. Company prepares for the audit, Step 3. Certification body conducts the audit, Step 4. Certification body issues the certificate
Traceability and Chain of custody	Biomass shall be traceable throughout the complete supply chain, following the rules laid down in ISCC EU System Document 203 "Requirements for traceability". Under ISCC, there are two chain of custody methods which can be applied to correctly assign all relevant information to the physical amounts of material: physical segregation or mass balance. Book and claim is not allowed. All supply chain operators taking ownership of biomass need to be ISCC certified.
Verification of compliance	The verification of compliance with the ISCC requirements as well as the issuance of ISCC certificates are performed by recognised third-party certification bodies cooperating with ISCC. Self-declarations are forms that have to be completed and signed by farms or plantations and points of origin for waste and residues materials before they can deliver sustainable material into the supply chain. This is a mandatory requirement for farms/plantations and points of origins which are not individually certified.
Accreditation of Certification Bodies	ISCC works with Certification bodies (CBs) that are recognised by a competent national public authority or that are accredited against ISO/IEC 17065 or ISO/IEC 17021. CBs and auditors must comply with the requirements specified in the ISCC EU System Document 103 "Requirements for Certification Bodies and Auditors".
Training of auditors and staff and qualification and evaluation of competencies	ISCC provides an extensive training programme for auditors and other relevant staff at Certification Bodies, as well as for System Users and other interested parties. Further information provided in ISCC EU System Document 103 "Requirements for Certification Bodies and Auditors"
Audit process	ISCC certificates are issued following a successful audit during which the Certification Body verifies the System User's compliance with all applicable ISCC requirements. A risk-based audit approach has to be applied to ISCC audits by the Certification Body.
Frequency of audit	Annual audit
Internal audit	Each System User registered for certification under ISCC must conduct an internal assessment (self-assessment) of their compliance with ISCC requirements at least once a year.
Certification claims and labels	Certified ISCC System Users may use the ISCC logo and claims for relevant communications and documentation following a written request to ISCC. The ISCC seal must not be used for any application other than the ISCC certificate. The requirements for the use of claims and logos

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	(off-product and on-product), a style guide for the use of ISCC logos and examples of ISCC claims are provided in ISCC EU System Document 208 "Logos and Claims".
Sanctions, non-conformities and suspension	Non-conformities with ISCC requirements are classified according to the impact of the non-conformity. Categories of non-conformities are: Minor, Major and Critical. The CB assesses non-conformities of System Users as minor, major or critical and applies the respective sanctions and measures as described in EU System Document 102 Governance
Complaint and appeal mechanisms	ISCC's conflict resolution process consists of the two levels complaints and appeals. A complaint describes an expression of dissatisfaction with decisions or other activities of ISCC or an indication of non-compliance of System Users and CBs or other persons involved in an ISCC certification system with ISCC requirements or of a failure to follow ISCC policies and operating procedures. An appeal is a request for reconsideration of a decision made by ISCC based on a complaint.
Guarantee smallholder inclusiveness of the standard	Within ISCC, group certification can be applied to homogeneous groups of producers of raw material and feedstock, i.e., farms/plantations, points of origin for waste and processing residues, and storage or logistic facilities. This approach is particularly important for the certification of smallholder farmers, producer organisations and cooperatives.
Promote continuous improvement	ISCC is committed to continuously improving its system. The quality and risk management in the ISCC framework contributes to this continuous improvement process. The System Users should adhere to the principle 6: Good management practices and commitment to continuous improvement: The management regularly monitors and reviews all activities and takes actions to continuously improve management with respect to environmental, social and economic sustainable development.
Assurance of quality	The quality management of the ISCC include core features including ISCC Integrity Programme, participation in benchmarking processes, multi-stakeholder dialogue, participation in sustainability conferences and feedback from CBs and system users.
Impact assessment	The goal and mission of ISCC is to induce positive long-term social, environmental and economic impacts. The ISCC Impact Assessment has the goal to monitor the outcomes and impacts of ISCC certification and to evaluate if ISCC's strategies are effective to reach ISCC's mission and goals and lead to the desired outcomes and impacts. The ISCC Impact Assessment covers all of ISCC's Certification Systems and is conducted on a regular basis. The Impact Reports are publicly available on the ISCC website.
Risk management	Risk management is an integral part of the ISCC system. In order to credibly and reliably ensure the fulfilment of the certification system requirements, ISCC defines procedures and specific indicators for risk assessment and management. Further information provided in ISCC EU System Document 204 "Risk Management".
Cost of certification	There are different type of fees for getting certified. *The certification fee is due once per issued certificate. Certification fees are based on the total turnover of the registered operational unit. They cover the costs for the registration process and the certificate. Additionally, a Quantity-dependent fee is to be paid for the amount (metric ton) of outgoing material declared by the System User as sustainable according to ISCC. An up-to-date overview of the fee structure can be obtained from www.iscc-system.org . Additional costs occur for the audit, charged by the CB.

Sustainability Principles and Criteria

Reference Document	The sustainability requirements for all materials that can be certified under ISCC are described in ISCC EU System Document 202 "Sustainability Requirements" and subdocuments where the respective requirements for different kinds of raw materials are described in detail: ISCC EU 202-1 – Agricultural Biomass: ISCC Principle 1, ISCC EU 202-2 – Agricultural Biomass: ISCC Principles 2-6, ISCC EU 202-3 – Forest Biomass: ISCC Principle 1, ISCC EU 202-4 – Forest Biomass: ISCC Principles 2-6 and ISCC EU 202-5 – Waste and Residues.
Major Must and Minor Must	The sustainability criteria fall into two categories: Major Musts and Minor Musts. As stated in the Annex "ISCC Requirements at a Glance", all Major Musts and at least 60% of the Minor Musts must be fulfilled to comply with the ISCC sustainability requirements.
Environmental	
General	Covered under ISCC EU System Document 202 "Sustainability Requirements" and subdocuments - Principle 1: Protection of Land with High Biodiversity Value or High Carbon Stock, Principle 2: Environmentally Responsible Production to Protect Soil, Water and Air.
Reduce GHG emissions	Within ISCC PLUS, the verification of GHG emissions is voluntary and can be added by applying the add-on ISCC EU 205 "Greenhouse Gas Emissions": Application, Calculation and Verification Methodology of Greenhouse Gas Emissions.
Protection of land with high carbon stock	ISCC EU 202-1 Agricultural Biomass, Criteria 1.2 Biomass is not produced on land with high carbon stock. Raw material shall not be obtained from land with high carbon stock, namely land that had one of the following statuses in January 2008 and no longer has this status: (1) Wetlands, (2) Continuously forested areas, and (3) Forested areas with 10-30% canopy cover.

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	ISCC EU 202-4 Forest Biomass, Criteria 2.1.3 Conversion of natural and semi-natural forests to plantation forests. The conversion of natural and semi-natural forests after the cut-off date, January 2008 within the sourcing area of an economic operator to other forms of land use, including plantation forests, is not permitted.
Protection of peatland	ISCC EU 202-1 Agricultural Biomass, Criteria 1.3 Biomass is not produced on peatland. Raw material for biofuels, bioliquids and biomass fuels produced from agricultural biomass shall not be obtained from land that was peatland in January 2008 or thereafter and no longer had this status.
Promote sustainable forest management	ISCC EU 202-3 Forest Biomass, Principle 1 Sustainable harvesting on national and management level, Land-Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) Criteria. The requirements of ISCC Principle 1 for forest biomass ensure the legality of harvesting operations, forest regeneration, the protection of areas designated for nature protection purposes, that harvesting is carried out taking soil quality and biodiversity into account and to ensure the maintenance and improvement of the long-term production capacity of the forest. Additionally, beyond the legal requirements of the RED II, ISCC EU 202-4 Forest Biomass, include Criteria on 2.1.2 Management Plan and 2.2 Maintaining the production capacity and harvesting of wood and non-timber forest products.
Protection of land with a high biodiversity value	ISCC EU 202-1 Agricultural Biomass, Criteria 1.1 Biomass is not produced on land with a high biodiversity value. Raw material shall not be obtained from land with high biodiversity value, namely land that had one of the following statuses in or after January 2008, whether or not the land continues to have that status: (1) Primary forests and other wooded land, (2) Highly biodiverse forest and other wooded land, (3) Areas designated by law or by the relevant competent authority for nature protection purposes, (4) Areas for the protection of rare, threatened or endangered ecosystems or species, and (5) Highly biodiverse grassland spanning more than one hectare. ISCC EU 202-4 Forest Biomass, Criteria 2.1.1 Protection of land with high conservation value forests. The following land categories and their respective protection are of relevance for forest biomass production: Primary forest, Species diversity forests, Indigenous tree species, and Areas designated by law or by the relevant competent authority for nature protection purposes.
Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity	ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass, Criteria 2.1 Conservation of natural resources and biodiversity: 2.1.1 Environmental impact assessment, 2.1.2 Avoidance of damage or deterioration of habitats, 2.1.3 Implementation of ecological focus areas for the protection of pollinators and biodiversity, 2.1.4 A biodiversity action plan is in place, 2.1.5 Natural vegetation areas around springs and natural watercourses are to be maintained or re-established, and 2.1.6 Cultivation of highly invasive species and genetically modified (GM) varieties. ISCC EU 202-4 Forest Biomass, Criteria 2.1.4 Environmental impact assessment, and within 2.3 Protection and promotion of biodiversity in forests: 2.3.1 Natural regeneration and indigenous tree species, 2.3.2 Avoidance of damage or deterioration of habitats, 2.3.3 Highly invasive species, 2.3.4 Cultivation of genetically modified (GM) trees, 2.3.5 Harvesting of non-timber forest products, 2.3.6 Mixed stands, 2.3.7 Rare and endangered species, and 2.3.8 Deadwood.
Sustainable use of water	ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass, Criteria 2.9 Maintaining and improving water quality and quantity. Good agricultural practices should be implemented with respect to reducing unsustainable water use, the abstraction of unsustainable water sources and minimising diffuse and localized pollution from chemical residues, fertilisers, soil erosion or other sources of ground and surface water. ISCC EU 202-4 Forest Biomass, Criteria 2.6 Maintaining and improving water quality and quantity. The water balance and quality of water in the management system at the sourcing area level and downstream outside the unit are at least maintained and where necessary improved.
Maintaining and enhancing water quality	Covered also under ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass, Criteria 2.9 and ISCC EU 202-4 Forest Biomass, Criteria 2.6: Maintaining and improving water quality and quantity.
Maintaining and enhancing soil quality and productivity	Good agricultural/forest management practices concerning soil quality, soil contamination and soil erosion are addressed as part of soil management. This is covered under: ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass, Criteria 2.2 Maintain and improve soil fertility: 2.2.1 Improvement of soil fertility (include erosion, soil nutrient balance, soil organic matter, soil pH, salinization), 2.2.2 Avoidance of soil erosion and compaction, 2.2.3 Annual crops follow crop rotation procedures. ISCC EU 202-4 Forest Biomass, Criteria 2.4 Soil fertility (include maintaining or improving soil structure, and soil biodiversity).
Soil quality consideration for use of residual flows	ISCC EU 202-1 Agricultural Biomass, Criteria 1.4 Monitoring of impacts on soil quality and carbon. In accordance with the RED II regulation Article 29(2) the monitoring of impacts on soil quality and carbon must be implemented. ISCC provides the soil management practices that can be applied e.g., crop rotation, cover/catch crops, no burning of arable stubble.
Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals	The use of chemicals classified as Type 1A and 1B by the World Health Organization (WHO), chlorinated hydrocarbons as well as in Annex III of the Rotterdam Convention (UNEP's Prior Informed Consent (PIC) Program list) are not permitted under ISCC. This is covered under ISCC

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass, Criteria 2.4 Restrictions on plant protection products and seeds: 2.4.1 Prohibition of chemicals, 2.4.3 Local restrictions on the use of plant protection products are followed, and 2.4.4 Seed origin is legitimized; and ISCC EU 202-4 Forest Biomass, Criteria 2.5.1 Restrictions on chemical pesticides.
Implement best practices for the use of (agro)chemicals	ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass, Criteria 2.3 Fertiliser application, 2.5 Avoiding plant protection products with integrated pest management, 2.6 Plant protection product application, 2.7 Handling and disposing of plant protection products, fertilisers and wastes, and 2.8 Storing of operating resources ISCC EU 202-4 Forest Biomass, Criteria 2.5 Pest, disease and weed management: 2.5.2 Usage of chemical pesticides are registered, 2.5.3 Staff handling the chemical pesticides must be skilled and must apply the chemical pesticides appropriately, and 2.5.4 Handling, disposing and storing of chemical pesticides (in line with 2.7 and 2.8 of 202-2 Agricultural biomass).
Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality	ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass, Criteria 2.10.1 Reduction of air pollutants and emissions and 2.1.7 Restriction on burning: The burning of arable stubble or other crop residues is not allowed except where authority (e.g. local, regional or national) has granted an exemption for plant health reasons. Burning as part of land and/or vegetation clearance is prohibited. ISCC EU 202-4 Forest Biomass, Criteria 2.3.9 Burning. The burning of forest residues or parts of the forest is allowed only with the permission of the competent authority and only for the case that biodiversity of nature shall be promoted through the controlled use of fire.
Limit the risk of Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC)	ISCC PLUS voluntary add-on addresses ILUC: "Low ILUC-risk feedstock certification". Measures and verification requirements for low iLUC risk feedstock, additional biomass production through cultivation on unused land and additional yield increase.
Circularity	
General	Covered under ISCC EU System Document 202 "Sustainability Requirements" and subdocuments - Principle 2: Environmentally Responsible Production to Protect Soil, Water and Air. There is also a specific chapter in ISCC PLUS System Document Chapter 7 "The Circular Economy"
Promote waste reduction and responsible waste management	ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass, Criteria 2.7.7 The premises must have adequate provisions for waste disposal. National and regional legislation must be followed when storing and disposing of waste. The risks of different types of waste are identified, and waste is stored according to risk identification; 2.7.8 Waste management includes reduction, reuse and recycling. It reduces waste and avoids the use of landfills or burning. ISCC EU 202-4 Forest Biomass, Criteria 2.3.10 Inorganic litter. The accumulation of inorganic waste, plastic waste and litter is prevented, or such waste and litter is collected, stored in approved areas and disposed responsibly.
Raw material efficiency	Implicitly covered under ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass, Criteria 2.7.8 where waste reduction, reuse and recycling is promoted. Additionally, with Criteria 2.3.5 Use of wastes and agricultural residues: Agricultural waste is reduced, reused and/or recycled. Agricultural waste and co-products can be, for example, composted on-farm and used as soil conditioning, sold to alternative markets or used for alternative purposes.
Efficient use of energy	ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass, Criteria 2.10.2 Efficient energy management. Energy consumption should be as efficient as possible to protect the climate. An energy management plan shall document current and future sustainable practices and identify measures to improve the efficiency.
Promote use of renewable sources	Covered within ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass, Criteria 2.10.1 and 2.10.2: Fossil fuel and energy reduction, the use of renewable energies, e.g., biofuels, biogas, solar or wind energy, are encouraged.
Promote material circularity	Implicitly covered under ISCC PLUS System Document Chapter 7 "The Circular Economy". The ISCC EU System Document 202-05 "Waste and Residues" provides the principles for the certification of raw materials and feedstocks qualifying as "waste" or "residue".
Social	
General	Covered under ISCC EU System Document 202 "Sustainability Requirements" and subdocuments - Principle 3: Safe Working Conditions, Principle 4: Compliance with Human and Labour Rights and Responsible Community Relations
Compliance with labour rights	Covered by Criteria 4.2 Employment conditions of ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass and ISCC EU 202-4 Forest Biomass. Criteria on Child labour (4.2.2 There is no child labour), Forced and compulsory labour (4.2.1 There is no forced labour), Fair salary and remuneration (4.2.10 A living wage is paid which meets at least legal or industry minimum standards), Association and collective bargaining (4.2.12 Labour organisations and collective bargaining are allowed for negotiating working conditions), Equal opportunities/discrimination (4.2.3 There is no discrimination, 4.2.4 Employment conditions comply with equality principles, and 4.2.5 Respect and ensure gender equity), and Grievance mechanism (4.1.6/9 Workers and affected communities must be able to make a complaint).

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Respect wellbeing of workers	Criteria on Contract (4.2.8 All workers are to be provided with fair legal contracts), Training (3.1 Training and competence to ensure health and safety), Occupational health and safety (3.2 Prevention and handling of accidents: Workers are equipped with suitable protective clothing; Potential hazards are clearly identified; Accident procedures and equipment are available), Harassment/violence (4.2.7 Workers are treated with dignity and respect), and Work and overtime (4.2.9 The employment conditions of individual workers comply with legal regulations and/or collective bargaining agreements, 4.2.16 Working times and overtime are documented) of ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass and ISCC EU 202-4 Forest Biomass.
Respect property and usage rights	The Legitimacy of land use is covered in ISCC EU 202-3 "Forest Biomass: Principle 1" and ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass, Criteria 5.1. The producer should be able to prove that the land is being used legitimately and that traditional and customary land rights or tenure have been secured. Additionally, ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass, Criteria 2.9.1 Respect existing water rights concern water use rights.
Respect wellbeing of the local population	Covered by Criteria 4.1 Rural and social development of ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass and ISCC EU 202-4 Forest Biomass. All environmental, social, economic and cultural impacts for surrounding areas, communities, users and landowners are taken into account. Access to basic services and to quality primary school education is provided. Other forms of social benefits are offered by the employer to workers and their families and/or community (e.g., medical care/health provisions). Workers and affected communities must be able to make a complaint.
Food security	Covered under Criteria 4.1 Rural and social development - 4.1.4 Biomass production does not impair food security of ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass. Biomass production shall not replace stable crops or impair local food security. In cases whereby local food prices are expected to rise as a direct effect of biomass production, the farm/plantation shall introduce mitigation measures.
Economic	
General	Covered under ISCC EU System Document 202 "Sustainability Requirements" and subdocuments - Principle 5: Compliance with Land Rights, Laws and International Treaties and Principle 6: Good Management Practices and Continuous Improvement.
Financial and economic viability	Covered by ISCC Principle 6 – Good Management Practices and Continuous Improvement, Criteria 6.1 Economic stability, and 6.2 Management of ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass and ISCC EU 202-4 Forest Biomass. Economic operators shall develop a business plan that reflects a commitment to long-term economic viability.
Fair business practices, Integrity	A written anti-bribery and -corruption statement must be in place provided in Criteria 5.3 of ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass and 5.2 of ISCC EU 202-4 Forest Biomass.
Promote local development, Inclusive economic growth	Covered under ISCC EU 202-2 Agricultural Biomass, 4.1.8 Other forms of social benefits are offered by the employer to workers and their families and/or community: Preferentially offer local businesses the opportunity to supply goods and services and support local community development programs; If appropriate, the employer should make employment opportunities known locally.
Use of knowledge and technology	Implicitly covered under Principle 2 using best available technology to reduce the use of plant protection products, reduce the risk of soil quality degradation, and reduce air pollution. Also, consideration for precision agriculture techniques, and application of technical and local knowledge.
Fair trade and market practices	-
Risk assessment and management	Covered under Principle 6.1.2 Business plan: risk mitigation strategies shall be taken into account.

Date completed: 26 April 2023

Sources:

- ISCC website <https://www.iscc-system.org/> (Last visited: 26 April 2023)
- ISCC System Documents <https://www.iscc-system.org/process/iscc-documents-at-a-glance/iscc-system-documents/> (Last visited: 26 April 2023)

6.2 Factsheet RSB Advanced Products

This factsheet aims to provide accessible and factual information on the RSB Global Advanced Products certification scheme. This factsheet presents the actual status of the scheme in March 2023. For more detailed information on the system, the reader may visit the website of the certification scheme or contact the scheme owner.

Disclaimer: The information contained in this factsheet is for informational purpose only and cannot be used in replacement of the official RSB standards and procedures

Table 10 Factsheet RSB Advanced Products

Scheme Feature	Description
General	
Name of scheme	RSB Global Advanced Products Certification
Scheme owner	The Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials (RSB) is a global, multi-stakeholder independent organisation. Originally established to ensure the sustainability of biofuels, RSB expanded in 2013 to cover biomaterials and now offers the most comprehensive system for certifying bio-based feedstock. The RSB has members from a worldwide movement of businesses, NGOs, academics, government and UN organisations. For fuel producers, RSB offers RSB Global and RSB EU RED. For biomaterials producers, RSB offers the RSB Advanced Product Standard. For groups of smallholders, RSB offers a Smallholder Standard. RSB's low Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC) Standard is a voluntary addition.
Website	https://www.rsb.org/
Label provided	
Operational since	2013
Number of active certificates	21 (https://rsb.org/certification/rsb-certificates/ , 24 March 2023)
Standard ownership	Private
General objective	Driving the development of the bio economy for a better world through certification, sustainability solutions, innovation and partnerships.
Scope	
Biomass feedstock coverage	Any biobased feedstock. Besides biobased feedstock, scheme also includes as feedstock recycled fossil feedstock and end of life products.
Sector/Product group coverage	Any industrial application. RSB Global Advanced Products Certification enables the certification of non-energy products like plastics, textiles, pharmaceuticals, packaging, tableware, cosmetics, nutritional supplements, food, feed, pulp, paper and many others. RSB Certified Advanced Products are split into 3 distinct categories: Category I: Products that are biobased they need to have a share of bio-based content not less than 25% present in the product; Category II: Products produced with recycled content (non-biogenic end-of-life products or production residues) and Category III: Production systems that process bio-based feedstock or non-bio-based end-of-life products or production residues in combination with virgin fossil feedstocks (either biobased or non-biobased).
Supply chain coverage	Applicable to all elements of the supply chains. Biomass production, feedstock processing, intermediary and final product production
Geographic focus of the standard	Global
Governance, Standard Development and Certification Requirements	
Scheme governance	The RSB members are organised into five Chambers that elect the governing body of the organisation – the Assembly of Delegates. Membership Chambers represent different sectors of business, civil society, trade unions, government, academia and multi-lateral organisations. The five chambers are: 1. Growers & producers, 2. End users, blenders & investors, 3. Social, 4. Environmental, 5. UN, Governments & Research. Each

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	chamber elects three delegates forming the Assembly of Delegates. The Assembly appoints a Board of Directors which is responsible for the management of the RSB and provide oversight to the Secretariat. Secretariat is responsible for the day-to-day running of the organisation.
Standard documents	RSB Global Advanced Products Certification is composed of a variety of procedures and methodologies that describe how to produce and trade advanced products. The standards and procedures are provided on its website: https://rsb.org/rsb-certification-for-products/ RSB Principles and Criteria (RSB-STD-01-001), Standard for Advanced products (RSB-STD-02-001), GHG Calculation Methodology (RSB-STD-01-003-01), Procedure for Participating Operators (RSB-PRO-30-001), Procedure for Traceability (Chain of Custody) (RSB-PRO-20-001), Procedure for Communication & Claims (RSB-PRO-50-001), Procedure for Risk Management (RSB-PRO-60-001) and Requirements for woody biomass (RSB-SA-01).
Transparency and accessibility of standard documents	Transparency through freely accessible standards and procedure documents and information about certificate holders e.g., through publication of certificates and Summary Audit Reports
Multi-stakeholder participation in standard development	RSB is an independent multi-stakeholder organisation that has been developed and is being continuously improved with the involvement of its stakeholders
Compliance with ISEAL's Standards-Setting, Impacts and Assurance Codes of Good Practice	RSB is an ISEAL Code Compliant Member implementing ISEAL's Standards-Setting, Impacts and Assurance Codes of Good Practice.
Compliance with regional, national, international laws	This is covered by the RSB Principle 1: Legality. Operations shall comply with all applicable laws and regulations of the country in which the operation occurs and with relevant international laws and agreements.
Reference to standards and policies	RSB Standard for Advanced products (RSB-STD-02-001) provides reference to relevant standards.
Obligation for certification	RSB certification applies to all operators of the product value chain. The RSB standard specifies requirements for different operator types: Primary biomass producers, Points of origin, First collectors, Industrial operators, Mechanical operators and Trader.
Certification process	There are four steps to achieving RSB certification. Step 1. Apply online, Step 2. Arrange an audit with certification body, Step 3. Prepare for audit. Step 4. Audit. After concluding that the operation complies with RSB's requirements the Certification Body issues the certificate.
Traceability and Chain of custody	All RSB certified operators that legally and/or physically control RSB certified material along the supply chain are required to establish effective and transparent chain of custody tracking systems, following the rules laid down in the RSB Procedure for Traceability (Chain of Custody) (RSB-PRO-20-001) RSB provides five different options for the chain of custody system that shall be put in place: Identity Preserved, Product Segregation, Mass Balance, Content Ratio Accounting and Book & Claim.
Verification of compliance	The verification of compliance with the RSB requirements as well as the issuance of RSB certificates are performed by recognised third-party certification bodies cooperating with RSB this is done in compliance with RSB Procedure for Certification Bodies and Auditors (RSB-PRO-70-001). The participating operator shall carry out a self-risk assessment and a self-evaluation of the operations against all applicable requirements of the RSB standards.
Accreditation of Certification Bodies	Accreditation of Certification Bodies in the RSB system is provided by ASI – Assurance Services International in line with ISO 17011. ASI is an international assurance organisation providing oversight of the RSB certification system and independent accreditation. The CB shall comply with all requirements of the international standard ISO 17065.
Training of auditors and staff and qualification and evaluation of competencies	The CB shall make sure that all auditors taking part in evaluation and certification of participating operator (PO) have the required training and qualifications in the scope of certification as provided in the RSB Procedure for Certification Bodies and Auditors (RSB-PRO-70-001). The CB shall ensure that the personnel working for the RSB audit programme receive adequate training to maintain a level of knowledge that ensures the correct implementation of RSB standards. Every auditor will complete the annual RSB Auditor test and attend any events the RSB makes available to the auditors, especially where regulatory updates are concerned.
Audit process	RSB certificates are issued following a successful audit during which the Certification Body verifies the PO's compliance with all applicable RSB requirements. The CB determines the frequency of audits based on a risk-based approach according to the RSB procedure for Risk Management [RSB-PRO-60-001]
Frequency of audit	The CB shall determine the frequency and schedule of audits based on the risk class of the participating operator. Main audit is carried out every 5 years for low-risk class, every 3 years for medium risk class and every 2 years for high risk class. Surveillance audit is carried out annually.

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Internal audit	The PO shall carry out and keep updated a self-evaluation of the operations, to comply with RSB standards and procedures. Additionally, the PO shall carry out a self-risk assessment of the operations which is used as input by CB in determining the audit schedule. In line with RSB Procedure for Participating Operators [RSB-PRO-30-001].
Certification claims and labels	Upon issuance of a valid certificate by the certification body, the PO can use RSB trademarks according to the requirements described in the RSB Procedures on Communications and Claims [RSB-PRO-50-001].
Sanctions, non-conformities and suspension	Areas where the PO does not meet the requirements of the RSB standard shall be defined by the lead auditor as either a minor noncompliance or a major non-compliance. The PO shall define corrective action measures to address the nonconformities and their root causes. The lead auditor shall monitor and evaluate all actions taken by the PO to address non-compliances identified during evaluation. Major non-compliances found during the audit shall be corrected within 90 days of the audit closing meeting. The CB shall ensure that minor non-compliances are addressed according to the corrective action plan within 12 months.
Complaint and appeal mechanisms	The CB shall put in place a grievance mechanism in line with the RSB Grievance Procedure [RSB-PRO-65-001] to address cases of grievance (i.e., complaint, dispute, challenge, conflict) filed by POs or by any third party about any element of RSB evaluations and certifications. Additionally, the PO shall have a system for settling disputes and complaints about the POs performance raised by staff or other people or organisations. The PO shall record how they have managed and settled all disputes and complaints.
Guarantee smallholder inclusiveness of the standard	RSB Certification for Smallholder Groups is designed to support smallholders (areas <75 hectares) to access third-party certification by reducing economic barriers that might prevent small scale farmers from demonstrating compliance with sustainability criteria. The certified smallholder groups can supply RSB biomass to fuels and/or any bio-based product processor. RSB's Certification for Smallholders is composed of a standard for Group Management and an adapted RSB Principles & Criteria for Smallholder Groups.
Promote continuous improvement	The regular monitoring and evaluation of the RSB certification outcomes enables RSB to continuously work to improve the RSB Standard and certification system. The participating operators should adhere to Principle 2 Sustainable operations are planned, implemented, and continuously improved through an open, transparent, and consultative impact assessment and management process and an economic viability analysis.
Assurance of quality	The RSB Monitoring & Evaluation (M&E) System is designed to measure success in achieving the desired long-term goals. RSB monitors its performance by processing data collected among its certified operators through a set of "outcome indicators", which cover all the environmental, social and economic issues and the context in which operators work. Results from the M&E system feed into the continuous improvement of the RSB Standards, Policies, Guidance and Tools of the certification system, as well RSB strategies and activities.
Impact assessment	RSB's 2021 Integrated Impact Report looks not only at certification impacts, but also at how the Standard supports outcomes in project work, how RSB Advisory Services are supporting partners to improve and develop new systems and approaches based on RSB's approach, and how the continuous improvement of the Standard via RSB's multi-stakeholder community is building partnerships, consensus, and understanding to further its impact. The Impact Report is publicly available on the RSB website.
Risk management	The CB shall develop, document and implement a risk management approach to minimise risks which could compromise comprehensive, consistent and transparent implementation of the RSB Standards. The approach includes four (4) main stages: risk identification; risk evaluation; risk management; and risk monitoring. Further information is provided in the RSB procedure for Risk Management [RSB-PRO-60-001].
Cost of certification	There are different type of fees for getting certified. The Certification costs are divided into Application fee (to RSB, one-off fee), Auditor fee (to the certification body), Licence fee (to RSB for being certified and using the label). For all industrial operators a volume-based fee is applicable. For traders a licensing fee is charged for each office and/or site. Volume-based fees are not applied. Retailers pay fees when they repackage or relabel finished RSB-certified products calculated based on the volume and value of the product. An up-to-date overview of the fee structure can be obtained from https://rsb.org/certification/fees/

Sustainability Principles and Criteria

Reference Document	The sustainability requirements for all materials that can be certified under RSB are described in the document RSB Principles & Criteria (RSB-STD-01-001). For Advanced Products additional specific requirements are provided in the RSB Standard for Advanced Products (RSB-STD-02-001). Operators using end-of-life products or production residues shall apply, in addition, the requirements of the RSB Standard for Advanced Fuels (RSB-STD-01-010). Furthermore, RSB Standard Amendment for Woody Biomass clarify the requirements that apply to specific types of woody biomass (RSB-SA-01).
Major Must and Minor Must	The sustainability criteria fall into two categories: Minimum requirements (conditions to be met immediately) and Progress requirements (conditions to be met over time i.e., three years). A non-compliance with a minimum requirement is considered as major noncompliance

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Environmental	
Reduce GHG emissions	Principle 3 in RSB Principles & Criteria provides specific GHG reduction requirements for biofuels. For Advanced Products, GHG emission requirements are provided in the RSB Standard for Advanced Products. Operators producing intermediate products or biomass shall calculate lifecycle cradle-to-gate GHG emissions of certified biomass and/or intermediate products. Whenever certified final products are intended to replace fossil derived products, these certified final products shall achieve at least 10% lower lifecycle GHG emissions calculated on a cradle-to-grave basis relative to the lifecycle GHG emissions of a comparable fossil product. RSB provides RSB GHG Calculation Methodology (RSB-STD-01-003-01) to be followed.
Protection of land with high carbon stock	Criteria 7a. Conservation values of local, regional or global importance within the potential or existing area of operation shall be maintained or enhanced. Minimum requirement: Areas that contain identified conservation values of global, regional or local importance or that serve to maintain or enhance such conservation values shall not be converted after the 1st of January 2008, or earlier as prescribed by other relevant international standards. "No conversion" areas include forests and land with high carbon stock, e.g., wetland and peatland
Protection of peatland	Covered above.
Promote sustainable forest management	No explicit criteria in RSB Principles & Criteria. Yet, the RSB Principles & Criteria ensures, inter alia, the legality of the operation, decent work conditions and well-being of the workers and that there is no negative impact on soil health, water resources, biodiversity, ecosystems and conservation values, including a strict ban on deforestation (including converting forests to plantations) and sourcing biomass from primary forests. RSB Standard Amendment for Woody Biomass state the Forest Management shall comply with the RSB Principles & Criteria, with the FSC Principles & Criteria or equivalent.
Protection of land with a high biodiversity value	Criteria 7a. Conservation values of local, regional or global importance within the potential or existing area of operation shall be maintained or enhanced. Minimum requirement: Areas identified as "no-go areas" shall not be used for operations after the 1st of January 2008, unless feedstock production or processing operations are legally authorised as part of the conservation management for the area concerned. No-go areas including protected areas, primary forest, and highly biodiverse grassland.
Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity	Criteria 7b. Ecosystem functions and services that are directly affected by the operation shall be maintained or enhanced; 7c. Operations shall protect, restore or create buffer zones; 7.d Ecological corridors shall be protected, restored or created to minimise fragmentation of habitats; 7e. Operations shall prevent invasive species from invading areas outside the operation site; 11b. The technologies used in operations including genetically modified plants, micro-organisms, and algae, shall minimise the risk of damages to environment and people, and improve environmental and/or social performance over the long term.
Sustainable use of water	Criteria 9b. Operations shall include a water management plan which aims to use water efficiently and to maintain or enhance the quality of the water resources that are used for the operations; 9c. Operations shall not contribute to the depletion of surface or groundwater resources beyond replenishment capacities.
Maintaining and enhancing water quality	Criteria 9d. Operations shall contribute to the enhancement or maintaining of the quality of the surface and groundwater resources.
Maintaining and enhancing soil quality and productivity	Criteria 8a. Operators shall implement practices to maintain or enhance soil's physical, chemical, and biological conditions. Include consideration for: Soil erosion, soil nutrient balance, soil organic matter, soil structure and implementing measures to improve soil health, such as following Conservation Agriculture practices
Soil quality consideration for use of residual flows	Minimum requirement under criteria 8.a The use of agrarian and forestry residual products for feedstock production, including lignocellulosic material, shall not be at the expense of long-term soil stability and organic matter content.
Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals	Minimum requirement under criteria 11d. None of the chemicals recorded in the WHO's 1a and 1b lists shall be used. None of the chemicals recorded in Annex III of the Rotterdam Convention, in the Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants and the Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer shall be listed (type and annual volume used) and a plan to phase out any such chemical over the three years following certification shall be described in the ESMP.
Implement best practices for the use of (agro)chemicals	Criteria 11d. Good practices shall be implemented for the storage, handling, use, and disposal of biofuels, fertilisers and chemicals. Minimum requirements include Integrated Pest Management and requirements for proper handling of chemicals, fertilizers and pesticides.
Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality	Criteria 10a. Air pollution emission sources from the operations shall be identified; 10b. Operations shall avoid and, where possible, eliminate open-air burning of residues, wastes or by-products, or open air burning to clear the land.
Limit the risk of Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC)	RSB provides additional standards as voluntary add-on to address ILUC: RSB Low iLUC Risk Biomass Criteria and Compliance Indicators [RSB-STD-04-001] and RSB Methodology for Displacement Emissions [RSB-STD-04-002]

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Circularity	
Promote waste reduction and responsible waste management	Criteria 11e. Residues, wastes and byproducts from feedstock processing and biofuel or biomaterial production units shall be managed such that soil, water and air's physical, chemical, and biological conditions are not damaged.
Raw material efficiency	Recommendation under criteria 11d. The operator should use waste and co-products for a material purpose or for energy generation. Operators shall use waste and/or co-products for energy generation only if: the use for material purposes is not possible (e.g., no market is accessible), the use is in line with RSB Principle 10 (Air Quality)
Efficient use of energy	Minimum requirement under criteria 11e. Measures shall be taken to implement clean and efficient processes for conversion of residues, wastes or byproducts into energy appropriate to the scale and intensity of the operation
Promote use of renewable sources	This is implicitly considered in the minimum requirement under criteria 5a. Use of the locally produced bioenergy to provide modern energy services to local poor communities
Promote material circularity	Requirement under criteria 11e. by-products or wastes shall also be reused by the processing/production unit or transferred to other sectors whenever their use may improve the overall system's energy balance, greenhouse gas emissions, and/or economic viability.
Social	
Compliance with labour rights	Covered under Principle 4: Operations do not violate human rights or labour rights and promote decent work and the well-being of workers. Criteria 4a. Workers shall enjoy freedom of association, the right to organise, and the right to bargain collectively; 4b. No slave labour or forced labour shall occur; 4c.No child labour shall occur, except on family farms and then only when work does not interfere with the child's schooling and does not put his or her health at risk; 4d.Workers shall be free of discrimination of any kind, whether in employment or opportunity, with respect to gender, age, wages, working conditions, and social benefits; 4e. Workers' wages and working conditions shall respect all applicable laws and international conventions, as well as all relevant collective agreements. Men and women shall receive equal remuneration for work of equal value; 4h. Operators shall implement and maintain a transparent and easily accessible grievance mechanism, open for all workers and contracted workers
Respect wellbeing of workers	Occupational health and safety covered under Principle 4. Criteria 4f "Conditions of occupational safety and health for workers shall follow internationally recognised standards". Harassment and gender balance covered under criteria 4d. "Work sites shall be safe for women; free from sexual harassment and other discrimination and abuse; and promote access to jobs, skills training, recruitment and career development for women to ensure more gender balance in work and career development". Work and overtime covered under 4e. "The maximum number of regular hours worked per week must not exceed 48. Workers may work overtime which shall be voluntary, but total working hours shall not exceed 80 per week." Training covered under 5b." Training and capacity building shall be required". No explicit criteria found concerning contract, implicitly covered by criteria 1.
Respect property and usage rights	Land rights Criteria 12a. Existing land rights and land-use rights, both formal and informal, shall be assessed, documented, and established. The right to use land for the operations shall be established only when these rights are determined; 12b. Free, Prior, and Informed Consent shall form the basis for all negotiated agreements for any compensation, acquisition, or voluntary relinquishment of rights by land users or owners for operations. Water rights Criteria 9a. Operations shall respect the existing water rights of local and indigenous communities.
Respect wellbeing of the local population	Covered under Criteria 5a. At least one measure to significantly optimise the benefits to local stakeholders shall be implemented within a three-year period of the start of the operations, for instance: Social benefits for the local community such as the building or servicing of clinics, homes, hospitals and schools; 2c. Operators shall implement and maintain a transparent and easily accessible grievance mechanism for directly affected local communities
Food security	Criteria 6a. Operations shall assess risks to food security in the region and locality and shall mitigate any negative impacts that result from their operations; 6b. In food insecure regions, operations shall enhance the local food security of the directly affected stakeholders.
Economic	
Financial and economic viability	Covered by Principle 2: Sustainable operations are planned, implemented, and continuously improved through an open, transparent, and consultative impact assessment and management process and an economic viability analysis.
Fair business practices, Integrity	Minimum requirement under Criteria 1. A system that ensures that all forms of bribery, conflicts of business interest and fraudulent practices are prohibited, including a written policy by the management and appropriate staff training
Promote local development, Inclusive economic growth	Criteria 5a. In regions of poverty, the socio-economic status of local stakeholders impacted by the operations shall be improved. Include requirements for skills training, creation of year-round and/or long-term jobs, supporting empowerment of farmers and rural communities.

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	Additionally, criteria 5b. In regions of poverty, special measures that benefit and encourage the participation of women, youth, indigenous communities and the vulnerable in the operations shall be designed and implemented, including training and capacity building.
Use of knowledge and technology	Principle 11. The use of technologies shall seek to maximise production efficiency and social and environmental performance and minimise the risk of damages to the environment and people.
Fair trade and market practices	-
Risk assessment and management	No explicit criteria under Principles & Criteria standard. Rather given in RSB procedure for Risk Management [RSB-PRO-60-001].

Date completed: 25 March 2023

Sources:

- RSB website <https://rsb.org/> <https://www.iscc-system.org/> (Last visited: 24 March 2023)
- RSB standards and procedures <https://rsb.org/rsb-certification-for-products/> (Last visited: 24 March 2023)

6.3 Factsheet Better Biomass

This factsheet aims to provide accessible and factual information on the Better Biomass certification scheme. This factsheet presents the actual status of the scheme in March 2023. For more detailed information on the system, the reader may visit the website of the certification scheme or contact the scheme owner.

Disclaimer: The information contained in this factsheet is for informational purpose only and cannot be used in replacement of the official Better Biomass standards and procedures

Table 11 Factsheet Better Biomass

Scheme Feature	Description
General	
Name of scheme	Better Biomass
Scheme owner	Better Biomass is managed by NEN, the Netherlands Standardization Institute. As member of CEN and ISO, NEN will ensure that the sustainability criteria and conformity assessment processes are and will remain aligned with the relevant European (EN) and international (ISO) standards. Better Biomass is an international certification system for solid, liquid and gaseous biomass. The Better Biomass certificate is used to demonstrate the sustainability of the biomass used for energy, fuels or bio-based products.
Website	https://www.betterbiomass.com/
Label provided	
Operational since	2011
Number of active certificates	155 (https://betterbiomass.nl/en/certificate-holders/ , March 2023)
Standard ownership	Private
General objective	The mission of NEN is to develop and manage standards and certification schemes with high impact and social and broad stakeholders. The aim of developing and managing schemes by NEN is to ensure the support for the relevant scheme in the market and to increase the uniformity of the conformity assessment.
Scope	
Biomass feedstock coverage	Any type of biomass
Sector/Product group coverage	Energy, fuels or bio-based products. In the 2015 update of the standards the scope was extended to the sustainably produced biomass for biobased products.
Supply chain coverage	Applicable to all elements of the supply chains. Biomass production, feedstock processing, intermediary and final product production
Geographic focus of the standard	Global
Governance, Standard Development and Certification Requirements	
Scheme governance	Better Biomass is managed by NEN (Stichting Koninklijk Nederlands Normalisatie Instituut). The Committee of Experts, composed of range of stakeholders, is responsible for supervising the functioning of the standard and the certification scheme and for adjusting the certification scheme, if necessary. The certification system is supported by the NEN Scheme management manual which is administered by NEN and is

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	provided to all parties concerned, like members of the Committee of Experts and certification bodies that have entered into an agreement with NEN.
Standard documents	NEN Certification Scheme NCS 8080 describes the certification scheme for sustainably produced biomass for bioenergy and bio-based products based on Netherlands Technical Agreements NTA 8080-1:2015 and NTA 8080-2:2015. NTA 8080-1:2015 Sustainably produced biomass for bioenergy and bio-based products – Part 1: Sustainability requirements and NTA 8080-2:2015 Sustainably produced biomass for bioenergy and bio-based products – Part 2: Chain-of-custody requirements. Better Biomass interpretation documents.
Transparency and accessibility of standard documents	The Better Biomass certification scheme (NCS 8080:2018-08) can be downloaded from the Better Biomass website. NTA 8080-1:2015 and NTA 8080-2:2015 standards can be downloaded via the NEN webshop free of charge.
Multi-stakeholder participation in standard development	NEN aspires to offer a broadly supported certificate that has an added value, particularly in relation of the organization with its external stakeholder. NEN strives for a balanced representation of relevant stakeholders in the development and management of schemes. The Committee of Experts is composed of representatives of industry, societal organizations and government.
Compliance with ISEAL's Standards-Setting, Impacts and Assurance Codes of Good Practice	Better Biomass/NEN is currently not an ISEAL community member and do not demonstrate compliance to ISEAL's Standards-Setting, Impacts and Assurance Codes of Good Practice. NEN as scheme owner complies with the requirements set by the Dutch Accreditation Council.
Compliance with regional, national, international laws	NTA 8080-1, section 5.6 "The organization shall, as far as applicable, demonstrably acquainted with laws and regulations that relate to the sustainability aspects in the NTA". It is further written that applicable laws and regulation prevail. Furthermore, criterion 4.1 "No violation of national laws and regulations that are applicable to biomass production and the production area".
Reference to standards and policies	The NCS 8080, NTA 8080-1 and NTA 8080-2 include references to the applicable standards and guidelines. Additionally, on its website links to background documents including Standards and Legislation, regulations and supporting documents are provided: https://betterbiomass.nl/en/certification-documents/background-documents/
Obligation for certification	Better Biomass certification applies to producer (produce biomass or collect residual flows), processor (process biomass), trader and end-user (use processed biomass for application in bioenergy and biobased products). Organizations that only transport producer or processed biomass are not included in the scope of the standards. A biomass flow that is used for bioenergy or bio-based products at the end of the chain is regarded fully sustainable, if all organizations that are classified as 'producer', 'processor', 'trader' or 'end-user' are in the possession of a valid certificate.
Certification process	The process for being granted a Better Biomass certificate includes: Preparation, Initial audit, Granting of certificate and Maintenance of certificate. Preparation concerns performing of a self-assessment and implementing improvements based on that, contacting a certification body and becoming a member. Based on the initial audit the certificate may be granted. The organisation will be published on the register of certificate holders and can use the logo. Maintenance of certificate concern surveillance audits carried out annually and re-certification in order to extend the certificate for another five years.
Traceability and Chain of custody	NTA 8080-2 describes the requirements on the chain of custody from biomass production to final application in order to assure the traceability of the origin of the biomass. For the application in biobased products, the organization may use the chain of custody models of segregation and mass balance approaches. Three different approaches for applying the mass balance are described in the standard. The organisation at the end of the chain of custody for the application of biobased products shall issue a declaration that includes the biogenic content of the product (physical and assigned) and share of sustainably produced biomass in the biogenic share of the product.
Verification of compliance	The verification of compliance with the NTA 8080 requirements as well as the issuance of Better Biomass certificates are performed by recognised third-party certification bodies who have entered into an agreement with NEN.
Accreditation of Certification Bodies	NEN solely enters into agreement with certification bodies having an applicable accreditation declaration from an IAF/MRA partner. In the Netherlands the Dutch Accreditation Council RvA is the accreditation body that is IAF/MRA partner and accredits certification bodies to the application of this certification scheme. Certification body shall be recognised on the basis of the requirements in ISO/IEC 17065 or equivalent to this.
Training of auditors and staff and qualification and evaluation of competencies	The competences of the audit team shall comply with ISO/IEC 17065 and the guidelines given for this in ISO 19011, supplemented with the requirements described in the Better Biomass certification scheme (NCS 8080:2018-08).
Audit process	The initial certification audit and recertification audit consist of two stages: a) Stage 1 concerns the preliminary investigation. The certification body assesses all the necessary documents, at the organization itself if required, carries out a risk analysis and draws up the audit plan on the

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	basis of inter alia these documents. b) Stage 2 concerns the assessment of the organization. The audit team of the certification body assesses the organization on site. Based on the initial audit the certificate may be granted. The surveillance audit only consists of stage 2 and involves the activities to be carried out at the location to assess all applicable requirements.
Frequency of audit	The Better Biomass certificate is issued for a maximum period of five years. During the validity of the certificate, audits shall be carried out at least once a year (surveillance audits).
Internal audit	The organisation investigates whether it meets the certification requirements (self-assessment). A useful tool to coordinate the improvements is a project plan that describes the necessary actions, the persons involved, the resources needed and the time frame.
Certification claims and labels	Organization of which the assessed production processes comply with the applicable requirements of NTA 8080-1 and NTA 8080-2 in accordance with the assessment criteria of the certification scheme will be issued the 'Better Biomass' certificate. This is the new name for the 'NTA 8080 Approved' certificate. Conditions for the use of logo is described in NEN Scheme management manual as well as in NCS 8080 certification scheme.
Sanctions, non-conformities and suspension	In NCS 8080, the verification method of the requirements of NTA 8080-1 and NTA 8080-2, and to which type of scope these requirements apply i.e., 'producer', 'processor', 'trader' or 'end-user', is specified. The category 'producer' is subdivided into the following organizations: biomass producers (e.g., farmers, foresters); smallholders; collectors of primary residual flows (originating from the agriculture, the forestry, and associated sectors including fisheries and aquaculture); collectors of non-primary residual flows (originating from industrial and household waste). Non-compliance with a specific requirement result in a non-conformity. A non-conformity could be classified as a critical, major or minor non-conformity. NCS 8080 Table 5 shows which non-conformities shall be classified as critical or as major. Other non-conformities may be classified as minor. In case of granting the 'Better Biomass' certificate or in case of recertification, the organization may not have any critical or major non-conformities. At a surveillance audit an organization may have minor and major non-conformities, but no critical non-conformities. If the organization has a major non-conformity, the organization shall provide a proposal for improvement within two weeks after receipt of the audit report from the certification body and shall correct the observed non-conformity within three months subsequently and demonstrate this to the certification body.
Complaint and appeal mechanisms	NEN Scheme Management deals with complaints about the functioning of the committees, the implementation of the committees' activities and the incorrect and/or unlawful use of certification marks by third parties. NEN wide complaints procedure is followed. Additionally, the certification body shall have a documented process about the receipt, evaluation and decision-making of objections. The certification body shall have a procedure for complaints and appeals. Further information on the treatment of objections and appeals is provided on the website https://betterbiomass.nl/en/about-us/queries-complaints/ as well as NEN Scheme management manual. For the organisations, NTA 8080-1 section 5.8 requires the organisation to keep registration of the complaints received including how the complaints have been dealt with and the measures that have been taken to prevent repetition of these complaints.
Guarantee smallholder inclusiveness of the standard	The category 'producer' is subdivided into different type of organizations where different requirements are applicable referred to as scope in NCS 8080. Here smallholders are differentiated from biomass producers and less verification requirements apply for this group to ease certification.
Promote continuous improvement	NTAs are reviewed at least once every three years for their being up to date and valid. Internal monitoring is carried out and the scheme owner shall organize at least annually an auditors meeting to support harmonization and unambiguous implementation of the Better Biomass certification scheme. The organizations to be certified should adhere to Monitoring, measurement, analysis, evaluation and continual improvement requirement in NTA 8080-1 section 5.7.
Assurance of quality	The scheme manager and the Committee of Experts guarantee the quality of the published scheme. During the duration of a scheme, this can lead to changes in the scheme. The quality assurance of the scheme requires independent monitoring of the implementation of the scheme. The scheme manager conducts periodic reviews of the licensee to ensure the quality of the application of a scheme and to determine the follow-up to the rules.
Impact assessment	No public document reporting on Impact of the scheme has been found.
Risk management	Risk analysis is part of the assessment process in verification of the requirements by the certification body taking into account the following: a) administrative organization; b) quality of documented information; c) responsibilities and competences of personnel; and d) origin and nature of raw materials; e) annual volumes; f) number of transactions; g) complexity of processes; h) existence of other certifications; i) changes compared with previous year; and j) information from external parties related to scope of certification including possible complaints.

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Cost of certification	The tariffs for certificate holders consist of an annual fee for each certificate and an annual membership fee or annual payment per metric ton. Members are exempt from payment per metric ton and registration costs and receive membership benefits. Membership fee is based on the annual turnover of the organisation. Companies can also choose for a payment of € 0,0312 per metric ton (with a minimum total of € 100). An up-to-date overview of the fee structure can be obtained from https://betterbiomass.nl/en/certification/certification-roadmap/
Sustainability Principles and Criteria	
Reference Document	NTA 8080-1:2015 Sustainably produced biomass for bioenergy and bio-based products – Part 1: Sustainability requirements
Major Must and Minor Must	NCS 8080 Table 5 shows which requirements shall be classified as critical or as major. Others may be classified as minor.
Environmental	
Reduce GHG emissions	6.2.1.2 Greenhouse gas emission savings for biobased products – When using biomass for bio-based products, the organisation shall have access to the data on the own greenhouse gas emissions and the greenhouse gas emissions in the preceding chain. Calculation methodology is provided in Annex C. For biobased products, no requirements are set on the net greenhouse gas emission saving due to lack of (unambiguous) fossil reference.
Protection of land with high carbon stock	6.2.2 High carbon stock, 6.2.2.1 The organization may not produce biomass from land with high carbon stock, namely land that had one of the following statuses on 1 January 2008 or earlier and no longer has this status: a) wetland, b) continuously forested areas, c) land spanning more than one hectare with trees higher than five metres, d) peatland
Protection of peatland	Covered under 6.2.2 High carbon stock
Promote sustainable forest management	6.2.2.4 The organisation shall have written proof for all solid biomass from forests that the production location from which the timber originates, is managed in order to maintain in the long-term or to increase carbon stocks by demonstrating that the carbon cycle remains at least maintained. This proof can be provided in the form of a plan for (sustainable) forest management or similar evidence. Additionally, 6.2.2.5 and 6.2.2.6 are included in the Better Biomass interpretation document N° 8 related to RED II sustainability criteria for forest biomass: one to minimise the risk of using forest biomass derived from unsustainable production; and another to ensure compliance with land use, land-use change and forestry requirements.
Protection of land with a high biodiversity value	6.4.1 Land with high biodiversity value - The organization may not produce biomass from land with high biodiversity value, namely land that had one of the following statuses on 1 January 2008, whether or not the land continues to have that status: a) primary forest and other wooded land, b) areas designated by law or by the relevant competent authority for nature protection purposes & areas for the protection of rare, threatened or endangered ecosystems or species, and c) highly biodiverse grassland
Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity	6.4.2 Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity - Include consideration for buffers for riparian vegetation zones and ecological corridors and for the use of genetically modified crops and invasive species.
Sustainable use of water	6.5.2.2 Renewable sources and the availability of water - The organization must ensure that the use of surface and groundwater does not exceed the natural replenishment of the surface or groundwater system over a five-year average. No water from non-renewable sources shall be used. Link to Water Footprint Network is provided for data on water availability in the region.
Maintaining and enhancing water quality	6.5.2.1 Preservation and improvement of water quality - Include consideration for the measurement of biological oxygen demand and for risks to ground and surface water as a result of the use of chemicals.
Maintaining and enhancing soil quality and productivity	6.5.1.1 Preservation and improving soil quality - Include consideration for: a) erosion, b) nutrient balance, c) soil organic matter, d) soil fertility and soil structure; e) soil salination; and f) use of chemicals. Link is provided to BioESoil to assess the impacts on soil quality.
Soil quality consideration for use of residual flows	6.5.1.2 Use of residual flows - The organization must ensure that the use of residual flows does not conflict with other established, local essential functions for the preservation of the soil and soil quality.
Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals	6.5.1.1 and 6.5.2.1 requires that the use of pesticides that are classified as type 1A or type 1B by the World Health Organization, and the use of chlorified hydrocarbons are excluded
Implement best practices for the use of (agro)chemicals	Consideration of use of chemicals implicitly covered under 6.5.1.1 soil quality and 6.5.2.1 water quality – risks for the soil/water as a consequence of the storage and the use of chemicals and other business processes are prevented and controlled. In the case of forestry, chemicals are used only if the maximum use of ecological processes and sustainable alternatives proves to be insufficient.
Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality	6.5.3.1 Restricting emissions and air pollution – The organisation shall take any measures that are necessary to ensure that the emission of harmful substances into the air as a result of the production, processing and transport of biomass at the production location is limited. 6.5.3.2 No burning as part of the installation or management

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Limit the risk of Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC)	This sustainability aspect is only required for organizations that market their biomass as 'ILUC low risk'. 6.3.3 ILUC low risk - The organization can opt or may be required to market its biomass as ILUC low risk. Then the organisation shall reduce the risk of ILUC in the biomass chain by choosing one or more of the possible solutions: 1) growing biomass on previously unused land; 2) additional productivity increase, on top of the trend line; 3) integrating existing agriculture or forestry with additional biomass production; and 4) use of waste and residual flows that had no other application before. Link is provided to the Low Indirect Impact Biofuel (LIIB) certification module for this purpose.
Circularity	
Promote waste reduction and responsible waste management	6.5.4.1 Waste management - The organization must take measures necessary to ensure that the practices applied in its business operations are aimed at the responsible waste management. This includes prevention of waste, reuse of waste, separation of waste for recycling, recovery of waste other than reuse or recycling, and responsible disposal of waste.
Raw material efficiency	6.3.2 Raw materials - efficient use of biomass - Biomass should be used as resource-efficient as possible over the entire life cycle and continued to be used (Cascading). 6.5.4.2 Use of residual flows - The organization shall take measures to ensure that residual flows from the production and processing process of biomass are put to optimum use.
Efficient use of energy	Implicitly covered under 6.3.2 efficient use of biomass.
Promote use of renewable sources	-
Promote material circularity	Implicitly covered under 6.3.2 which considers continued use of biomass as a raw material, cascading use.
Social	
Compliance with labour rights	Covered by sections 6.7.3.1 Child labour, 6.7.1.1 Fair salary and remuneration, 6.7.3.5 Association and collective bargaining rights, and 6.7.1.4 Grievance mechanism. No explicit section for Forced and compulsory labour, and Discrimination. NTA 8080-2 directly refers to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of the United Nations, with regard to non-discrimination, child labour, forced and compulsory labour, disciplinary practices, safety practices, the freedom of trade union association and the rights of indigenous peoples. Provisions in 6.7.1 and 6.7.3 concretize the practices that should at least be implemented.
Respect wellbeing of workers	Covered by sections 6.7.3.2 Contract, 6.7.3.6 Training, 6.7.1.3 Occupational health and safety, 6.7.3.7 Harassment and violence, and 6.7.1.2 Hours of work and overtime. NTA 8080-2 directly refers to the Tripartite declaration of principles concerning multinational enterprises and social policy of International Labour Organisation concerning employment, labour relations, health and safety, training and education, diversity and equal opportunities, and complaints handling. Provisions in 6.7.1 and 6.7.3 concretize the practices that should at least be implemented.
Respect property and usage rights	Covered by 6.7.4 Property and usage rights
Respect wellbeing of the local population	Health and safety of local community covered by 6.7.5.1 health and safety relating to the infrastructure, hazardous substances and materials, emissions and secretions, health and disease Local services covered by 6.6.1 The organisation shall demonstrate that its activities have a positive impact on the access to infrastructure and basic facilities (a house, sanitary facilities, education, healthcare, water, energy, etc.) in the region concerned. Engagement with local community covered by 6.7.2 Responsible contact with (local) stakeholders, as well as with 5.5 Stakeholder consultation - 5.5.1 The organization shall consult the stakeholders who have some interest in the area where the production location is or will be established
Food security	6.3.1 If the organization makes use of local biomass flows or natural resources (e.g., land, water and raw materials) that are essential to the basic needs of the local population, it shall monitor the local prices thereof. In the event of significant increases in prices, the organization shall demonstrate that such increases are not due to its activities.
Economic	
Financial and economic viability	Implicitly covered under 5.7 Monitoring, measurement, analysis, evaluation and continual improvement
Fair business practices, Integrity	6.7.6 Integrity of the company – 6.7.6.3 The organization shall take any measures that are necessary to effectively fight corruption within the organization.
Promote local development, Inclusive economic growth	6.6.1 The organization shall demonstrate that its activities have a positive impact on the average income in the region concerned 6.6.2 The organization shall demonstrate that it tries to recruit new staff from among the local population; 6.6.4 The organization shall demonstrate that local suppliers, if present, have been contacted when purchasing products and outsourcing services; 6.7.5.2 The organization shall take measures that are necessary in order to positively influence the local population as regards creating employment

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Use of knowledge and technology	6.7.4.4 The organization shall compensate the local population for the application of their traditional knowledge
Fair trade and market practices	-
Risk assessment and management	Risk analysis is mentioned under 6.4.2.2 risk of invasiveness of alien species, 6.5.1.1 erosion risk, 6.5.1.1 and 2.1 risk from chemicals use on soil and water quality, and 6.7.6.1 related to fighting corruption.

Date completed: 30 March 2023

Sources:

- Better Biomass website <https://betterbiomass.nl/> (Last visited: 30 March 2023)
- Better Biomass certification documents <https://betterbiomass.nl/en/certification-documents/current-certification-documents/> (Last visited: 30 March 2023)

6.4 Factsheet Textile Exchange GRS

This factsheet aims to provide accessible and factual information on the Textile Exchange GRS certification scheme. This factsheet presents the actual status of the scheme in March 2023. For more detailed information on the system, the reader may visit the website of the certification scheme or contact the scheme owner.

Disclaimer: The information contained in this factsheet is for informational purpose only and cannot be used in replacement of the official Textile Exchange standards and procedures

Table 12 Factsheet Textile Exchange GRS

Scheme Feature	Description
General	
Name of scheme	Textile Exchange Global Recycled Standard (GRS)
Scheme owner	The Textile Exchange is a global non-profit organization that works to promote sustainability in the textile industry working closely with stakeholders to drive industry transformation in preferred fibers, integrity and standards, and responsible supply networks. It is governed by a Board of Directors and operates with the support of its members and partners. Textile Exchange owns the following standards: Content Claim Standard (CCS), Recycled Claim Standard (RCS), Global Recycled Standard (GRS), Organic Content Standard (OCS), Responsible Down Standard (RDS), Responsible Woold Standard (RWS), Responsible Mohair Standard (RMS) and Responsible Alpaca Standard (RAS).
Website	https://textileexchange.org/recycled-claim-global-recycled-standard/
Label provided	
Operational since	2002
Number of active certificates	Over 10.000 (available from https://textileexchange.org/find-certified-company/)
Standard ownership	The Textile Exchange GRS is a private and voluntary standard.
General objective	The primary goal of the Textile exchange GRS is to increase use of recycled materials in products and reduce the harmful social, environmental, and chemical impacts of production. Textile Exchange's has a goal of helping the fashion, textile, and apparel industry to reduce the greenhouse gas emissions that come from fiber and raw material production by 2030, which they call Climate+.
Scope	
Biomass feedstock coverage	The Textile Exchange GRS certification scheme is focused on the use of range of post- and pre-consumer reclaimed feedstocks of any source including both animal, plant based fibers and synthetic fibers. It does not cover virgin biomass feedstock.
Sector/Product group coverage	Predominantly textile sector, however the Global Recycled Standard is intended for use with any product that contains at least 20% Recycled Material.
Supply chain coverage	The Textile Exchange GRS certification scheme covers the entire supply chain of products made with recycled content, from raw materials to the final product. The supply chain coverage of the GRS includes: collection and sorting, processing, spinning and weaving, manufacturing, distribution and retail. Overall, the supply chain coverage of the GRS is comprehensive, ensuring that products made with recycled content meet certain environmental and social criteria throughout the entire production process.
Geographic focus of the standard	Global

Governance, Standard Development and Certification Requirements

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Scheme governance	The Textile Exchange Governance Board is responsible for approval of substantive changes to Textile Exchange strategy, particularly in reference to any changes to the goals and scope of the standards. The development of Textile Exchange standards shall be led by the International Working Group (IWG), composed of the secretariat and IWG members. IWG members represent brand/retailer, civic society, raw material producers and supply chain services. The secretariat has the administrative role of the IWG, which includes record keeping, stakeholder management, and other functions such as assurance management, and monitoring and evaluation.
Standard documents	The following documents are considered part of the Global Recycled Standard, and are fully binding: Content Claim Standard, Content Claim Standard Implementation Manual, Global Recycled Standard, GRS Logo Use and Claims Guide, Accreditation and Certification Procedures for Textile Exchange, Standards, Policy and Template for Issuing Certificates of Compliance (Scope Certificates, SCs), Scope Certificate Template, Policy and Template for Issuing Transaction Certificates (TCs), Transaction Certificate Template and Textile Exchange Accepted Equivalent Standards. All documents can be found at http://globalRecycled.org .
Transparency and accessibility of standard documents	All Textile Exchange standard documents are publicly available and free of charge on its website.
Multi-stakeholder participation in standard development	Decisions are made by consensus among the members of the International Working Group (IWG), composed of the secretariat and IWG members. Stakeholder engagement is part of the standard development or revision activities with targeted outreach to key stakeholders and an open public invitation to participate and provide feedback.
Compliance with ISEAL's Standards-Setting, Impacts and Assurance Codes of Good Practice	As a full member of the ISEAL Alliance, Textile Exchange follows the ISEAL Codes of Good Practice for standard setting bodies to ensure having a robust and transparent processes for their standards.
Compliance with regional, national, international laws	Textile Exchange expects all organizations certified under Textile Exchange standards to comply with all applicable local, national, and international laws and regulations at all times. In all instances, the international labour standard, national and/or local legislation or GRS requirement that is the most stringent, shall apply to the extent that it does not place them in violation of applicable law.
Reference to standards and policies	Provided in the Global Recycled Standard v 4.0, Section A2.2. Referenced Documents.
Obligation for certification	The GRS certification scheme requires certification of all parties involved in the supply chain of a product that contains recycled content, from the supplier of the recycled material to the brand or product manufacturer who sells the final product. By requiring certification of the entire supply chain, the GRS aims to ensure that the recycled content in the product is accurately traced and verified, and that environmental and social standards are upheld throughout the supply chain.
Certification process	There are 6 steps for achieving the GRS certification standard. Step 1. Select an approved certification body, Step 2. Send application, Step 3. schedule and audit, Step 4. on-site audit (the CB will send an auditor against the requirements of the standard), Step 5 follow up if needed (if a follow-up is needed, a corrective action plan to follow will be given), Step 6. Certification decision (audits results will be reviewed to make a final certification decision).
Traceability and Chain of custody	The Content Claim Standard (CCS) is the Textile Exchange chain of custody standard and is aimed at ensuring the accuracy of content claims, It tracks verified input material through the supply chain and applies to any product, from any industry. The CCS is intended to maintain the integrity of the claimed material's attributes from the original input source to the final product. The CCS is verified by an accredited third-party certification body. The chain of custody model used for the CCS is primarily batch-level segregation with scope certificates and transaction certificates. Scope certificates verify that a company is qualified to produce certified products. Transaction certificates verify that specific products are certified to a given standard. A form of mass balance has been introduced in the Alternative Volume Reconciliation Policy, but with a limited scope of site and process eligibility.
Verification of compliance	An accredited third-party certification body verifies the compliance with applicable Textile Exchange standards.
Accreditation of Certification Bodies	Each certification body is independently accredited by an authorized accreditation body following ASR 101 Accreditation and Certification Procedures and signs a licensing agreement with Textile Exchange. Requirement of certification bodies is covered in section D of the Accreditation and Certification Procedures for Textile Exchange Standards v2.1. Requirements from ISO17065 are referenced in this section.
Training of auditors and staff and qualification and evaluation of competencies	The CB shall make sure that all auditors taking part in evaluation and certification have the required training and qualifications in the scope of certification as provided in the Accreditation and Certification Procedures for Textile Exchange Standards v2.1. Section D.3 Resource requirements. D3.1 Certification Body Personnel (incl. management of competence) and D3.2 Resources for evaluation. The certification body

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	shall have a program for the ongoing training and calibration of auditors and other certification personnel Auditors shall receive ongoing training on updates to the relevant Standard(s) and related requirements.
Audit process	The certification body shall carry out audits in order to verify information and conformity with certification requirements applicable to the organization. Risk assessments shall be conducted by the certification body prior to each audit and at other times as needed. Certified Organizations shall demonstrate that their working conditions are in line with the social principles in Section B2 and environmental requirements in section C of the GRS standard during the annual audit. If they pass this first audit, the company is awarded a “scope certificate” for that standard and from then on are re-assessed annually for compliance. In addition to this, for every sale of certified products, the company must apply for a “transaction certificate” that represents the actual product certification.
Frequency of audit	Annually
Internal audit	Internal audits shall be performed normally once a year. An audit programme shall be established, taking into consideration the importance of the processes and areas to be audited, as well as the results of previous audits. Following ISO 17011 clause 9.7.1-4.
Certification claims and labels	Guidelines for making claims and communicating about the GRS can be found in the Standards Claims Policy document (https://textileexchange.org/app/uploads/2022/09/TE-301-V1.2-Standards-Claims-Policy.pdf) and guidelines for the use of the GRS logo can be found in the Standards Logo Use Specifications document (https://textileexchange.org/app/uploads/2020/10/TE-302-V1.1-Standards-Logo-Use-Specifications.pdf)
Sanctions, non-conformities and suspension	When a non-conformity is identified during an audit, it will be classified as critical, major, or minor in the written audit report that the certification body will provide to the (to be) certified site after the audit. A certification decision can be expected once all non-conformities are resolved. See Appendix B in the ASR-101 Accreditation and Certification Procedures for Textile Exchange Standards for a classification and management of non-conformities (https://textileexchange.org/app/uploads/2021/02/ASR-101-V2.1-Accreditation-Certification-Procedures-for-Textile-Exchange-Standards.pdf)
Complaint and appeal mechanisms	The Textile Exchange Complaints and Feedback Policy explains how Textile Exchange receives, manages, and addresses both complaints and general feedback relating to Textile Exchange standards, standards logos, and scheme participants. A complaint form can be found in: https://textileexchange.org/complaint-form/
Guarantee smallholder inclusiveness of the standard	GRS, A5.2c - Traders with an annual turnover of less than \$10,000 of GRS products, and retailers are exempt from the certification obligation.
Promote continuous improvement	GRS 4.0 was released in 2017; the next scheduled revision was merged with development of a consolidated standard system referred to as the unified standard. TE currently plans to finalize the unified standard system by 2024 by revising their standards framework with the aim of developing a single, more outcome-focused standard that incorporates the Climate+ strategy. The unified standard will let TE track progress more efficiently and effectively while increasing the value of our existing certification system. Organisation should adhere to the GRS criteria for continuous improvement: C1.1e Annual plan to target and reach meaningful environmental improvements across all indicators (Sections C2.1, C2.2, C2.4, and C2.5).
Assurance of quality	Textile Exchange has an Assurance team to implement and maintain the quality assurance and credibility of the Textile Exchange Standards. ASR-202 Assurance System Report describe the measures taken such as both accreditation and certification involve annual assessments and audits.
Impact assessment	Textile Exchange’s mission is to accelerate sustainable practices in the textile industry. The GRS, besides the main goal of increasing the use of recycled materials in products and reduce/eliminate the harm caused by its production, it contains a set of objectives: Alignment of definitions across multiple applications. Track and trace Recycled input materials. Provide customers (both brands and consumers) with a tool to make informed decisions. Reduce harmful impact of production to people and the environment. Provide assurance that materials in the final product are actually recycled and processed more sustainably. Drive innovation in addressing quality issues in the use of recycled materials. TE has a Monitoring and Evaluation system in place to ensure that the individual goals of each standard is being accomplished using guidance from the ISEAL Assessing the Impacts of Social and Environmental Standards Systems. Success indicators are defined for each standard e.g., social and environmental requirements for GRS. The results will be reported out to stakeholders in a publicly available annual report, used to further adjust requirements of the standards, and/or reported back to any individual units if deemed appropriate.
Risk management	In standard development a project plan is prepared that guides the process of standard development or revision as defined in ASR-102 Standard Setting Procedure. This plan includes an assessment of risks in implementing the standard, and how to mitigate these. Additionally, risk

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	management is part of the audit process and is further defined in ASR-101. Appendix C of the document further highlights Risk Assessment process to be carried out by CBs.
Cost of certification	TE licenses certification bodies to perform certifications in accordance with the standards. The certification bodies are charged the following fees: a. A one-time application fee; b. An annual licensing fee per standard scope; c. A fee for each certified site; and d. A fee per day spent auditing group certifications. TE does not charge fees for transaction certificates or for logo use & claims by certified organizations, certification bodies, or accreditation bodies at this time. The certification body sets and charges its own fees, which may or may not include fees charged by Textile Exchange as a separate line item. It is up to the certification body whether they directly pass on any fees to their clients or build it into their fee structure. In addition to many different factors that affect the cost, the amount is ultimately determined by the Certification Body who audits against the standards, so it is recommended to reach out to a few different certification bodies for quotes. For detailing of the different fees, a Textile Exchange Certification Fee structure 2021 is available in: https://textileexchange.org/app/uploads/2021/02/ASR-107-V2021.1-Certification-Fee-Structure.pdf
Sustainability Principles and Criteria	
Reference Document	The Global Recycled Standard (GRS) is the reference document that sets requirements for third-party certification of Recycled Content, chain of custody, social and environmental practices, and chemical restrictions.
Major Must and Minor Must	In the GRS, the following verbal forms are used to indicate requirements, recommendations, permissions, or capabilities: “shall” indicates a requirement, “should” indicates a recommendation, “may” indicates a permission, “can” indicates a possibility or capability. “Desired Outcomes” have been included to detail the intent of requirements, but they are not requirements themselves. They are designated by an icon before each module.
Reduce GHG emissions	
Reduce GHG emissions	Textile Exchange has the Climate+ goal of enabling and guiding the textile industry to reduce GHG emissions (CO ₂ equivalents) to 45% by 2030 in the pre-spinning phase of textile fiber and materials production. The Climate+ Dashboard measures progress toward their Climate+ goals. It looks at fiber and material production data against a 2019 baseline and calculates the associated GHG emissions and water impacts. While the GRS does not have specific requirements for mitigating GHG emissions, it does include a number of criteria related to environmental sustainability that can help to reduce the carbon footprint of products made with recycled materials.
Protection of land with high carbon stock	n/a
Protection of peatland	n/a
Promote sustainable forest management	n/a
Protection of land with a high biodiversity value	n/a
Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity	n/a
Sustainable use of water	Requirements from section C2.2 Water use, more explicitly: C2.2c Measurement and record keeping of water usage shall be undertaken on a monthly basis. C2.2d The Certified Organization shall set and meet targets for meaningful improvements in water use and review progress annually.
Maintaining and enhancing water quality	Requirement from section C2.3 Wastewater/Effluent, more explicitly: C2.3d There shall be identification of the contaminants and wastewater quality parameters and their flow direction, and C2.3e There shall be a system in place to ensure that wastewater receives proper treatment, either on or off-site, to meet minimum requirements before entering the water stream. In Appendix D Wastewater parameter limit values are provided.
Maintaining and enhancing soil quality and productivity	n/a
Soil quality consideration for use of residual flows	n/a
Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals	Requirement D2.1 Inherently problematic substances. Any chemicals used in processing of GRS Products shall not contain Substances of Very High Concern (SVHC) as referred to in Article 57 of European Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation,

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH), and included in Annex XIV of the Regulation. Requirement D2.2 Exclusion of substances and mixtures classified with particular hazard codes or risk phrases. No use is allowed of substances or mixtures that are assigned (or may be assigned by the time of the application) any of the hazard statement codes and/or risk phrases (or a combination of them). A table is included showing the prohibited hazard codes and risk phases of substances.
Implement best practices for the use of (agro)chemicals	The Certified Organization shall have a Chemical Management System (CMS) in place (as specified in Section C1.2), which includes Mechanism to monitor and meet all relevant legal requirements related to chemical management, and accurate lists of all chemical inputs. Additionally, organisation shall maintain a process to assess all chemicals used in GRS products against hazard criteria. Regarding handling of chemicals: B2.5 requires Certified Organizations to undertake sufficient training of workers and management in waste management, handling and disposal of chemicals and other dangerous materials.
Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality	Requirements from section C2.4 Emissions to Air, more explicitly: C2.4e The Certified Organization shall set and meet targets for meaningful improvements in emissions to air and review progress annually.
Limit the risk of Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC)	n/a
Circularity	
Promote waste reduction and responsible waste management	Requirements from section C2.5 Waste management, more explicitly: C2.5e Inventory, management, storage and transportation procedures for all waste streams shall be in place, C2.5f No on-site waste burning or uncontrolled waste landfilling may be undertaken; C2.5i The Certified Organization shall set and meet targets for meaningful reductions in waste production, improvements in waste management, and review progress annually.
Raw material efficiency	Implicitly covered in C2.5g The Certified Organization shall look for and implement ways to minimize waste production and increase re-use or recycling.
Efficient use of energy	Requirement from section C2.1 Energy Use, more explicitly: C2.1d The Certified Organization shall set and meet targets for meaningful improvements in energy use and review progress annually.
Promote use of renewable sources	Not explicitly covered.
Promote material circularity	TE GRS specifically addresses use of recycled input. This is covered in section A4.1 Material Recycling (Entities involved in Material Recycling are subject to GRS certification) and A3 Principles of GRS Certification (The Standard applies to products that contain 20% or more Recycled Content.).
Social	
Compliance with labour rights	Covered in Sections B2 Social Requirements: B2.1 Forced, bonded, indentured and prison labor, B2.2 Child labor, B2.3 Freedom of association and effective recognition of the right to collective bargaining, B2.4 Discrimination, harassment and abuse, and B2.6 Wages, benefits and terms of employment (fair salary and remuneration). Grievance mechanism is not explicitly covered.
Respect wellbeing of workers	Covered in Sections B2.4 Discrimination, harassment and abuse, B2.5 Health and safety (occupational health and safety), B2.6 Wages, benefits and terms of employment (covering contract) and B2.7 Working hours (overtime)
Respect property and usage rights	n/a
Respect wellbeing of the local population	Not explicitly covered
Food security	n/a
Economic	
Financial and economic viability	Economic criteria are outside scope
Fair business practices, Integrity	Economic criteria are outside scope
Promote local development, Inclusive economic growth	Economic criteria are outside scope
Use of knowledge and technology	Not explicitly covered.
Fair trade and market practices	Economic criteria are outside scope
Risk assessment and management	Risk assessment is carried out related to the hazard risks of chemical substances (Section D.2 Restricted chemical substances)

Date completed: 28 March 2023

Sources:

- Textile Exchange website: <https://textileexchange.org/>
- Textile Exchange library of tools and documents <https://textileexchange.org/knowledge-center/documents/> (Last visited: 28 March 2023)

6.5 Factsheet FSC

This factsheet aims to provide accessible and factual information on the FSC certification scheme. This factsheet presents the actual status of the scheme in March 2023. For more detailed information on the system, the reader may visit the website of the certification scheme or contact the scheme owner.

Disclaimer: The information contained in this factsheet is for informational purpose only and cannot be used in replacement of the official FSC standards and procedures

Table 13 Factsheet FSC

Scheme Feature	Description
General	
Name of scheme	Forest Stewardship Council (FSC)
Scheme owner	The Forest Stewardship Council® (FSC) is an independent, not for profit, non-government organization established to support environmentally appropriate, socially beneficial, and economically viable management of the world's forests.
Website	https://fsc.org/en
Label provided	<p>FSC has three labels: 1. FSC 100 %, 2. FSC Recycled, and 3. FSC Mix. All 3 FSC labels support responsible forestry. In FSC 100% all materials used come from responsibly managed, FSC-certified forests. Products with the FSC 100% label contribute most directly to FSC's mission. In FSC Recycled certification scheme the product is made from 100% recycled materials e.g., by using FSC recycled wood or FSC recycled paper. Using recycled material reduces the pressure to harvest more trees. In the FSC Mix certification scheme the product is made with a mixture of materials from FSC-certified forests, recycled materials, and/or FSC-controlled wood. Controlled wood doesn't come from FSC-certified forests.</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> </div>
Operational since	FSC was established in 1993
Number of active certificates	FSC has 55,095 active certificates. Out of those 53,626 certificates are chain of custody certificates and 1,469 Forest Management and Chain of Custody Certificates (on 07.03.2023)
Standard ownership	FSC is a private and voluntary standard
General objective	FSC's mission is the promotion of environmentally appropriate, socially beneficial, and economically viable management of the world forests.
Scope	
Biomass feedstock coverage	FSC 100 % and FSC Mix covers only wood as feedstock, FSC recycled cover reclaimed wood and paper as feedstock.
Sector/Product group coverage	The FSC certification system covers forestry and wood based manufactured products
Supply chain coverage	The FSC certification system covers the whole supply chain from production, to manufacturing, distribution
Geographic focus of the standard	The FSC certification system has a global focus
Governance, Standard Development and Certification Requirements	
Scheme governance	FSC governance structure is built upon the democratic principles of participation and equity. A three-chamber governance structure underpins all decision making, and therefore, FSC's activities. Members represent one of the three chambers – social, environmental and economic – and all have an equal say. Members are represented by a Board of Directors. The FSC General Assembly is FSC's highest decision-making body

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	where key decisions are made. The general assembly which is traditionally held every three years, brings together leaders and decision makers from indigenous peoples, environmentalists, businesses, and many others in FSC's membership to discuss a responsible future for the world's forests and the people and animals who inhabit them.
Standard documents	FSC has elaborated all the requirements very well in several different official documents. Hundreds of standards-related documents are available via the document centre on the FSC website.
Transparency and accessibility of standard documents	Transparency is ensured by freely accessible FSC documents on the website in several languages (mainly English and Spanish). However, due to the high number of documents it may be difficult to find the document that is searched for. Audit reports are not available on the FSC website, but the 'FSC certificates public dashboard' provides an overview of all valid, terminated and suspended FSC certificates.
Multi-stakeholder participation in standard development	FSC standards are continually evaluated and, when appropriate, revised. The process happens through the input and collaboration of a wide variety of stakeholders. Changes to key standards and policies are public and everyone can contribute. On the FSC website the review scheduled is published.
Compliance with ISEAL's Standards-Setting, Impacts and Assurance Codes of Good Practice	FSC complies with ISEAL code of compliance and has successfully undergone independent assessment against the ISEAL Codes of Good Practice in Standards-Setting, Assurance and Impacts (https://www.isealalliance.org/community-members/forest-stewardship-council). The certification system provides internationally recognized standard-setting, trademark assurance and accreditation to companies, organizations, and communities interested in responsible forestry.
Compliance with regional, national, international laws	The first FSC principle requires compliance with all applicable laws. Besides compliance with international standards, it is explicitly mentioned that compliance to national and regional conditions is mandatory.
Reference to standards and policies	FSC makes reference to and requires compliance to all applicable national and local laws and regulations. In addition, throughout the FSC normative framework, and more specifically in Principles 3 and 4, there is a reference to "legal and customary rights".
Obligation for certification	FSC requires that all relevant actors in the value chain obtain a certificate in order to handle FSC products from production to the manufacturing and the distribution. Certification is therefore required for all organizations in the supply chain of forest-based products that have legal ownership of certified products.
Certification process	The process is as following: FSC sets the standards; The accredited certification bodies verify FSC standard compliance of organizations, take the certification decision, and register the certification status in the FSC certification database.
Traceability and Chain of custody	Chain of custody certification is how the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) verifies that forest-based materials produced according to our rigorous standards are credibly used along the product's path from the forest to becoming finished goods. The requirements are described in FSC-STD-40-004 Chain of Custody Certification. The FSC chain of custody control system is used for controlling the quantities of products in a product group that can be sold with the FSC claims. The transfer system is an FSC control system which provides the simplest approach for the determination of output claims by transferring the FSC claims of inputs materials directly to the output products. Through segregation from ineligible materials, the link between input and output material is assured through all stages of an organization's processes. The transfer system can be applied to all types of product groups, FSC claims, and activities. The percentage system is an FSC control system which allows all outputs to be sold with a percentage claim that corresponds to the proportion of claim-contributing inputs over a specified claim period. The percentage system can be applied to FSC Mix and FSC Recycled product groups (not to FSC 100%).
Verification of compliance	The verification of compliance with the FSC requirements as well as the issuance of certificates are performed by recognized third-party certification bodies that hold valid agreements with FSC. Independent certification bodies carry out the forest management and chain of custody assessments that lead to FSC certification.
Accreditation of Certification Bodies	Certification bodies are accredited by an independent accreditation body. Assurance Services International (ASI) is FSC's accreditation body.
Training of auditors and staff and qualification and evaluation of competencies	FSC operates confirm ISEAL standards and accreditation of CB's is required. Next to this FSC developed detailed certification standards and certification process requirements. Accredited CBs shall be responsible for attending training and remaining up to date with FSC requirements as described in General requirements for FSC accredited certification bodies FSC-STD-20-001.
Audit process	Audits are carried out by third-party certification bodies. FSC certificates are issued following a successful audit during which the Certification Body verifies the compliance with all applicable FSC requirements.
Frequency of audit	The FSC audit cycle is 5 years. However, it is a requirement that third party audits by independent accredited certification bodies are conducted at a minimum within a 12-month period following the initial audit.
Internal audit	FSC requires internal audits and those are at least performed annually (FSC-STD-20-001 General requirements for FSC accredited certification bodies, 2.5.4)

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Certification claims and labels	The FSC Promotional License allows companies to use the FSC logo and other trademarks in their marketing and advertising efforts. There are 3 types of FSC labels: FSC 100%, FSC Mix, FSC Recycled. Only FSC certified companies are authorized to place FSC labels onto products. The FSC label applied to a product depends on the FSC claim an FSC-certified company makes and the control system they employ when producing the product.
Sanctions, non-conformities and suspension	FSC developed a specific document for certifiers. Sanctions, suspensions, non-conformities, corrective actions, are specified in the document 'FSC-STD-20-001 General requirements for FSC accredited certification bodies'. Major non-conformities shall be fully corrected within three months and may be extended once for a maximum period of another three months if full implementation of corrective action was not possible due to circumstances beyond the control of the organization. Minor non-conformities shall be fully corrected within one year.
Complaint and appeal mechanisms	FSC developed a s specific process for complaints as described in FSC-PRO-01-008 'Processing Complaints in the FSC Certification Scheme Procedure' and FSC-PRO-01-009 'FSC Template for Submitting Policy For Association Complaints'. Procedure FSC-PRO-01-005 'Processing Appeals' describes procedure for receiving, evaluating and deciding on appeals against decisions taken by FSC. Additionally, Certification Bodies should have their own Complaint and Appeal procedure. Complaints against the performance of FSC accredited Certification Bodies are dealt with by Accreditation Services International and processed according to the procedure ASI-PRO-20-104.
Guarantee smallholder inclusiveness of the standard	FSC launched the New Approaches for Smallholders and Communities Certification project in 2016 to help small or low-intensity managed forest, or SLIMF, withstand forest management challenges and overcome barriers to certification such as the number and complexity of the requirements, cost of certification and lack of access to sustainability markets. The project was later consolidated into a full-fledged program known as the Community and Family Forests (CFF) program which includes Asia Pacific Regional Forest Stewardship Standard for Smallholders for smallholders in India, Indonesia, Thailand and Vietnam. To reduce certification costs, FSC certificate holders can also form a group. Group certification makes it easier, particularly for smallholders, to become FSC-certified.
Promote continuous improvement	The next review of the FSC Principles and Criteria shall occur within three years of the approval of the International Generic Indicators, with a view to completion of any necessary revisions within two years of the review. Subsequent review and revision of the FSC Principles and Criteria shall occur within a five-yearly cycle according to FSC-PRO-01-001. The FSC standard refers to continuous improvement as 'adaptive management'. Adaptive management is part of principle 7 ("the management plan shall be implemented and kept up to date based on monitoring information in order to promote adaptive management") and Principle 8 ("the Organization shall demonstrate that, progress towards achieving the management objectives, the impacts of management activities and the condition of the Management Unit, are monitored and evaluated proportionate to the scale, intensity and risk of management activities, in order to implement adaptive management"). Additionally, the concept of continuous improvement is used for smallholder certification whereby smallholders are able to take a stepwise approach to conformance, focusing on the most important criteria first and offers flexible steps towards conformity with the remaining requirements within a defined timeframe.
Assurance of quality	The implementation of a quality management system is part of the FSC standard requirements covered under General requirements for FSC accredited certification bodies FSC-STD-20-001.
Impact assessment	FSC is compiling evidence to demonstrate outcomes and impacts of FSC certification. Currently, the two main sources of evidence are internally generated data and independent scientific studies. FSC makes reports on corrective action requests (CARs) available in the FSC certificate holder database to allow anybody to access information from certification assessments. Additionally, the FSC Impact Dashboard is an interactive and user-friendly tool that allows the user to navigate through a compilation of isolated results from scientific studies about the outcomes of FSC-certification across the world's forests available at https://connect.fsc.org/impact/demonstrating-impacts
Risk management	FSC certification requires several risk assessments. Standard FSC-STD-20-007 'Forest Management Evaluations' v4 introduces requirements for risk-based evaluations and how to audit against risk according to FSC-PRO-60-010 Development of a National Forest Stewardship Standard Risk Assessment, enabling the risk-based approach concept to be implemented across the FSC system. To support companies with their risk assessments, a FSC risk assessment platform has been set up. This platform offers in a simple and user-friendly way, an overview of the content of all 60 FSC risk assessments. In addition, free downloads are available for a quick guide, user manual, view tutorial, and legal & privacy statement available at https://connect.fsc.org/fsc-risk-assessment-platform
Cost of certification	FSC charges to the accredited certification bodies an annual administration fee (AAF) per FSC certificate holder. The CBs shall specify the scope, duration and costs related to the assessment services.

Sustainability Principles and Criteria

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Reference Document	Standard FSC-STD-01-001 'FSC Principles and Criteria for Forest Stewardship' describe the ten FSC Principles and their associated Criteria. The FSC requirements are described in various documents which can be found on the FSC website in the Document Centre. The standards and along going documents are divided in four categories: Forest Management, Controlled Wood for Forest Management, Chain of Custody, and Project Certification. An overview of all FSC Certification Requirements per type of FSC certification is available.
Major Must and Minor Must	FSC distinguishes between major nonconformities and minor non conformities.
Environmental	
Reduce GHG emissions	Not explicitly covered.
Protection of land with high carbon stock	The protection of land with high carbon stock is captured in general terms in Principle 6 Environmental Values and Impacts. Specifically with Criterion 6.9 The Organization shall not convert natural forest to plantations, nor natural forests or plantations on sites directly converted from natural forest to non-forest land use; and Criterion 6.10 Management Units containing plantations that were established on areas converted from natural forest after November 1994 shall not qualify for certification.
Protection of peatland	n/a
Promote sustainable forest management	The promotion of sustainable forest management is fully covered. FSC was established with the mission to promote environmentally appropriate, socially beneficial, and economically viable management of the world's forests. Especially Principle 10 Implementation of Management Activities Criterion 10.1 After harvest or in accordance with the management plan, The Organization shall, by natural or artificial regeneration methods, regenerate vegetation cover in a timely fashion to pre-harvesting or more natural conditions and Criterion 5.2 The Organization shall normally harvest products and services from the Management Unit at or below a level which can be permanently sustained.
Protection of land with a high biodiversity value	Covered under Principle 9 High Conservation Values: The Organization shall maintain and/or enhance the High Conservation Values in the Management Unit through applying the precautionary approach. Specifically, HCV 1 - Species diversity, HCV 2 - Landscape-level ecosystems and mosaics, HCV 3 - Ecosystems and habitats, and HCV 4 - Critical ecosystem services.
Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity	The restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity is captured in general terms in Principle 6. The Organization shall maintain, conserve and/or restore ecosystem services and environmental values of the Management Unit, and shall avoid, repair or mitigate negative environmental impacts. Specifically Criterion 6.4 The Organization shall protect rare species and threatened species and their habitats in the Management Unit through conservation zones, protection areas, connectivity and/or (where necessary) other direct measures for their survival and viability, and Criterion 6.8 The Organization shall manage the landscape in the Management Unit to maintain and/or restore a varying mosaic of species, sizes, ages, spatial scales and regeneration cycles appropriate for the landscape values in that region, and for enhancing environmental and economic resilience.
Sustainable use of water	Covered in Criteria 6.7. Natural water courses, water bodies, riparian zones and their connectivity shall be protected or restored. The Organization shall avoid negative impacts on water quality and quantity and mitigate and remedy those that occur. Additionally, Water resources is part of the environmental values, and its protection is covered under Principle 6 Environmental Values and Impacts.
Maintaining and enhancing water quality	Covered in Criteria 6.7. Natural water courses, water bodies, riparian zones and their connectivity shall be protected or restored. The Organization shall avoid negative impacts on water quality and quantity and mitigate and remedy those that occur. Additionally, Water resources is part of the environmental values, and its protection is covered under Principle 6 Environmental Values and Impacts.
Maintaining and enhancing soil quality and productivity	Soil is part of the environmental values, and its protection is covered under Principle 6 Environmental Values and Impacts. Additionally, under Criteria 10.6 and 10.7 where organization shall prevent, mitigate and/or repair damage to environmental values, including soils, from the application of chemical pesticides and fertilizers. Also, under Principle 9 High Conservation Values where HCV 4 cover control of erosion of vulnerable soils
Soil quality consideration for use of residual flows	Not explicitly covered.
Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals	The prohibition of hazardous/toxic chemicals is covered under Criterion 10.7 the Organization shall not use any chemical pesticides prohibited by FSC policy. In addition, FSC established a Pesticides Policy for managing the use of chemical pesticides in FSC-certified management units which includes good practices as well as list of hazardous pesticides.
Implement best practices for the use of (agro)chemicals	Covered in Criterion 10.6 The Organization shall minimize or avoid the use of fertilizers. When fertilizers are used, The Organization shall demonstrate that the use is equally or more ecologically and economically beneficial than the use of silvicultural systems that do not require fertilizers, Criterion 10.7 The Organization shall use integrated pest management and silviculture systems which avoid, or aim at eliminating, the use of chemical pesticides.

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality	Atmosphere is part of the environmental values, and its protection is covered under Principle 6 Environmental Values and Impacts: The Organization shall maintain, conserve and/or restore ecosystem services and environmental values of the Management Unit, and shall avoid, repair or mitigate negative environmental impacts.
Limit the risk of Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC)	Not explicitly covered.
Circularity	
Promote waste reduction and responsible waste management	The promotion of waste reduction is captured in Criteria 10.11 & 10.12, reduction of waste and disposal of waste in an appropriate manner.
Raw material efficiency	Implicitly covered under Principle 5 Benefits from the Forest - Criterion 5.1 The Organization shall identify, produce, or enable the production of, diversified benefits and/or products, based on the range of resources and ecosystem services existing in the Management Unit
Efficient use of energy	Not explicitly covered.
Promote use of renewable sources	Not explicitly covered.
Promote material circularity	The promotion of recycled material takes place due the establishment of a special standards and logos for FSC recycled and FSC mixed products.
Social	
Compliance with labour rights	The compliance with labour rights is covered in Criteria 2.1 compliance with the principles and rights at work as defined in the ILO Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work (1998) based on the eight ILO Core Labour Conventions is required. Additionally, Criteria 2.4 cover fair salary which is referred to as living wages and Criteria 2.6 cover mechanisms for resolving grievances and for providing fair compensation to workers for loss or damage to property
Respect wellbeing of workers	Respecting well-being of workers is captured in Criteria 2.1 - 2.6. Specifically, Criteria 2.2 promote gender equality in employment practices, training opportunities, awarding of contracts, processes of engagement and management activities; Criteria 2.3 implement health and safety practices to protect workers from occupational safety and health hazards; and Criteria 2.5 demonstrate that workers have job-specific training and supervision to safely and effectively implement the management plan.
Respect property and usage rights	Criteria 1.2 The Organization shall demonstrate that the legal status of the Management Unit, including tenure and use rights, and its boundaries, are clearly defined. Additionally Criteria 3.2 for indigenous people and 4.2 for local communities require the Organization to recognize and uphold the legal and customary rights of Indigenous Peoples/Local communities to maintain control over management activities within or related to the Management Unit to the extent necessary to protect their rights, resources and lands and territories. In the event of delegation of control over management activities, Free, Prior and Informed Consent is required.
Respect wellbeing of the local population	Respecting the wellbeing of the local population is captured in the Criteria 4.1-4.8. Specifically Criterion 4.5 The Organization, through engagement with local communities, shall take action to identify, avoid and mitigate significant negative social, environmental and economic impacts of its management activities on affected communities, and Criterion 4.6 4.6 The Organization, through engagement with local communities, shall have mechanisms for resolving grievances and providing fair compensation to local communities and individuals with regard to the impacts of management activities of The Organization.
Food security	n/a
Economic	
Financial and economic viability	The financial and economic viability is part of the mission of FSC as well as the FSC Principles and Criteria. It is specifically captured in the Criteria 5.5, and in general in the Principle 5 requiring maintaining or enhancing long term economic viability, Principle 7 requiring a management plan and Principle 8 monitoring and assessment.
Fair business practices, Integrity	Fair business practices and integrity are covered in Criteria 1.7 The Organization shall publicize a commitment not to offer or receive bribes in money or any other form of corruption and shall comply with anti-corruption legislation where this exists. In the absence of anti-corruption legislation, The Organization shall implement other anti-corruption measures proportionate to the scale and intensity of management activities and the risk of corruption.
Promote local development, Inclusive economic growth	The promotion of local development is covered by Criterion 4.3 The Organization shall provide reasonable opportunities for employment, training and other services to local communities, contractors and suppliers proportionate to scale and intensity of its management activities; and Criterion 4.4 The Organization shall implement additional activities, through engagement with local communities, that contribute to their social and economic development, proportionate to the scale, intensity and socio-economic impact of its management activities. Additionally, Criterion 5.4

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	concerns the use of local processing, local services, and local value adding. The organization shall make reasonable attempts to help establish these services.
Use of knowledge and technology	Covered by Criterion 3.6 and 4.8 The Organization shall uphold the right of Indigenous Peoples/Local communities to protect and utilize their traditional knowledge and shall compensate for the utilization of such knowledge and their intellectual property
Fair trade and market practices	Not explicitly covered
Risk assessment and management	Risk assessment and management is partly captured in the Criteria 5.5, and in general in the Principle 5 requiring maintaining or enhance long term economic viability, and criteria 7.5 requiring a management plan.

Date completed: 12 April 2023

Sources:

- FSC website [Home | Forest Stewardship Council \(fsc.org\)](https://www.fsc.org/) (Last visited: 30 March 2023)
- FSC library of tools and documents <https://connect.fsc.org/document-centre> (Last visited: 30 March 2023)
- Chain of Custody Certification FSC-STD-40-004 V3-1 EN
- <https://www.isealalliance.org/community-members/forest-stewardship-council> (Last visited: 30 March 2023)
- General requirements for FSC accredited certification bodies (page 20-24)
- FSC-STD-20-001 V4-0 EN
- FSC documents with reference code: FSC-PRO-01-008 and FSC-PRO-01-009
- FSC Principles and Criteria for FSC

6.6 Factsheet RSPO

This factsheet aims to provide accessible and factual information on the RSPO scheme. This factsheet presents the actual status of the scheme in March 2023. For more detailed information on the system, the reader may visit the website of the certification scheme or contact the scheme owner.

Disclaimer: The information contained in this factsheet is for informational purpose only and cannot be used in replacement of the official RSPO standards and procedures

Table 14 Factsheet RSPO

Scheme Feature	Description
General	
Name of scheme	Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO)
Scheme owner	RSPO is a global, not-for-profit organization with voluntary members. It is managed by a Board of Governors, designated by the General Assembly. In response to the pressing global call for sustainably produced palm oil, the RSPO was formed in 2004 by founding members the World Wildlife Fund, the Malaysian Palm Oil Association (MPOA), Unilever, AAK, and Migros. Since then, they have developed a set of environmental and social criteria that companies must comply with to produce RSPO Certified Sustainable Palm Oil (CSPO). These measures help minimise the negative impact of palm oil production on the local environment, wildlife and communities.
Website	https://rspo.org/
Label provided	<p>There are different sets of RSPO Label packages specifically designed for certified members in accordance with the supply chain models, and one package for the Book and Claim supply chain. 1. Identity Preserved (IP) and Segregated (SG) – “CERTIFIED” RSPO Label package (from a single or different identifiable certified source(s) that is kept separately from ordinary palm oil throughout the supply chain); 2. Mass Balance (MB) – “MIXED” RSPO Label package (from certified sources that is mixed with ordinary palm oil throughout the supply chain); 3.. Book and claim - “CREDITS” RSPO Label package. It is for Manufacturers and retailers that can buy RSPO Credits and RSPO Independent Smallholder Credits from RSPO Certified growers, crushers and independent smallholders</p> <p>The image shows three RSPO label packages. Each package consists of a square logo with a palm tree and the text 'CERTIFIED SUSTAINABLE PALM OIL' and 'RSPO'. Below the logo is a green bar with the label name: 'CERTIFIED', 'MIXED', or 'CREDITS'. Below the green bar is a small icon and a line of text: 'Contains certified sustainable palm oil. www.rspo.org' for CERTIFIED, 'Contributes to the production of certified sustainable palm oil. www.rspo.org' for MIXED, and 'Supports the production of sustainable palm oil. www.rspo.org' for CREDITS.</p>
Operational since	RSPO was formally established in 2004, in 2005 P&C pilot was launched
Number of active certificates	RSPO has 3748 certified companies (13.03.2023). Approximately 14% of global palm oil production is certified to the RSPO standard (February 2023)
Standard ownership	RSPO is a private standard
General objective	The objective of RSPO is to promote the growth and use of sustainable palm oil and palm oil products. The vision is to transform markets to make sustainable palm oil the norm, by convening stakeholders from across its different sectors to set and implement the most ambitious standard for sustainability in the industry.
Scope	

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Biomass feedstock coverage	RSPO focuses on oil palm, thus on specific type of feedstock
Sector/Product group coverage	RSPO certified oil palm products can be used in food, feed and fuel or oleochemical products
Supply chain coverage	Coverage of supply chain operators: oil palm growers, palm oil processors, consumer goods manufacturers and repacking and labelling, it does not cover distribution.
Geographic focus of the standard	The RSPO standard has a global focus
Governance, Standard Development and Certification Requirements	
Scheme governance	The RSPO is managed by a Board of Governors (BoG) comprised of 16 members, designated by the General Assembly for 2 years. BoG provides strategic direction to Secretariat and oversees delivery. Secretariat is in charge of the day-to-day running. BoG delegates specific functions to Standing Committees and receives reports. Standing Committees establish and oversee Working Groups and Task Forces where members feed into the decision-making process.
Standard documents	Via RSPO's website a set of standard documents is available e.g., RSPO Certification systems, RSPO Principles and Criteria, RSPO Supply Chain Certification Standard, RSPO Independent Smallholder Standard, RSPO communication and claims
Transparency and accessibility of standard documents	Transparency and accessibility is covered through freely accessible RSPO documents and information about certificate holders, all documents are available in different languages
Multi-stakeholder participation in standard development	RSPO is an independent multi-stakeholder initiative that has been developed and is being continuously improved with the involvement of its stakeholders. It has over 5200 members spread across all regions of the world
Compliance with ISEAL's Standards-Setting, Impacts and Assurance Codes of Good Practice	RSPO is ISEAL Code compliant, ISEAL Code Compliant designates members who have successfully undergone independent evaluations against the ISEAL Codes of Good Practice in Standards-Setting, Assurance and Impacts
Compliance with regional, national, international laws	RSPO requires compliance with local and international laws and regulations. Principle 2. Criterion 2.1 There is compliance with all applicable local, national, and ratified international laws and regulations
Reference to standards and policies	The Principles and Criteria for the production of sustainable Palm oil Annex 3 give an overview of the key international laws and conventions applicable to the production of palm oil, next to this RSPO supports global efforts to tackle deforestation and forest degradation, including those by the EU to ensure that products entering the EU market are not linked to these practices. On 6 December 2022, the European Parliament and the Council of the EU reached a provisional agreement on the proposed Regulation on Deforestation-free products, which will now include a.o. palm oil. New requirements were included in RSPO to ensure the effective contribution of RSPO to halting deforestation
Obligation for certification	Oil palm growers, palm oil processors, consumer goods manufacturers require certification. Traders and distributors themselves do not require certification.
Certification process	The certification process knows 5 Steps: STEP 1: Choose your role in the supply chain: oil palm growers, palm oil processors or traders or consumer goods manufacturers. STEP 2: Become an RSPO Member. STEP 3: Choose your supply chain models. STEP 4: Get certified under the relevant RSPO Standard: RSPO Principles and Criteria (P&C), RSPO Supply Chain Certification (SCC) Standard, RSPO Independent Smallholder (ISH) Standard. STEP 5: Ensure having a valid RSPO PalmTrace license to start trading!
Traceability and Chain of custody	RSPO allows mills, crushers, traders, refiners, manufacturers, and retailers to sell and buy RSPO under one of the four supply chain models: Identity Preserved, Segregated, Mass Balance, Book and Claim. For the purpose of certification, the first three (anyone or a combination) of the models shall be used. RSPO installed a supply chain traceability working group. The objective of this working group is to provide guidance to the Secretariat on optimising the supply chain for uptake of RSPO and traceability requirements.
Verification of compliance	Accredited third party Certification Bodies (CBs) conduct audits to evaluate members' compliance against the RSPO Standards. To ensure that members are competent to undertake credible, consistent audits, the RSPO Certification System requires that only accredited CBs are allowed to provide the RSPO certification services.
Accreditation of Certification Bodies	CBs that offer RSPO certification services are accredited by Assurance Services International (ASI). This is an established accreditation body that has demonstrable expertise in monitoring the performance of CBs globally, through a well-developed accreditation process. The CBs' performance is evaluated and closely monitored by the accreditation body. View the full list of RSPO accredited CBs. Accreditors ensure that CBs are operating in a manner consistent with the intent and requirements of the ISO/IEC 17021-1 with the specific RSPO requirements detailed in the certification standards.

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Training of auditors and staff and qualification and evaluation of competencies	The CB shall identify annual training needs and shall provide access to specific training to ensure its auditors (including freelance) and other personnel involved in certification activities are competent for the functions they perform (from RSPO certification systems document)
Audit process	RSPO certificates are issued following a successful audit during which the Certification Body verifies the System User's compliance with all applicable RSPO requirements.
Frequency of audit	RSPO recertification audit shall be undertaken once in every five years. The CB shall undertake annual surveillance audits during the certificate's validity, and a full recertification audit of compliance shall take place before the end of the five-year period.
Internal audit	RSPO standard requires to perform of each participating site and outsourced companies an internal audit at least annually to determine whether the organisation conforms to the requirements in RSPO standards and effectively implements and maintains the standard requirements within its organisation. The results of the internal audit and all actions taken to correct non-conformities shall be subject to management review at least annually.
Certification claims and labels	Certified RSPO members may use the RSPO logo and claims for relevant communications and documentation following a written application to RSPO for an RSPO Trademark licensee on MyRSPO. The requirements for all RSPO members when making any communication about RSPO certified products is provided in the RSPO Rules on Market Communications and Claims document
Sanctions, non-conformities and suspension	In the RSPO standard sanctions and deadlines for non-conformities exist: All major non-compliances shall be addressed to the satisfaction of the CB before certification is granted. Major non-compliances raised during surveillance and recertification audits shall be closed successfully within 90 days after the Main Assessment and 30 days after the annual surveillance audits, or the certificate shall be suspended, and subsequently withdrawn if the major non-compliances are not addressed within an agreed timeframe as set between CB and RSPO member, not longer than six (6) months from the last day of audit
Complaint and appeal mechanisms	The RSPO standard has a complaint and appeal procedure in place to handle and address complaints against RSPO Members in a fair, transparent and impartial process. The complaint and appeal procedure is not intended as a replacement for legal requirements and mechanisms in force. Additionally, CBs shall make available procedures for handling of complaints and grievances on its website. This shall include complaints against the certified organisation, the certification decision or the CB itself.
Guarantee smallholder inclusiveness of the standard	Under RSPO Certification, smallholders can grow oil palm independently, as part of an Independent Smallholder Group or as part of a Smallholder Scheme. To include more smallholders and to reflect their unique circumstances and needs, RSPO Independent Smallholder (ISH) Standard was developed exclusively for independent smallholders, this standard strikes a balance between promoting greater smallholder inclusion and protecting the core sustainability requirements. Additionally, Principle 5 concerns smallholder inclusion.
Promote continuous improvement	The RSPO standards has a: a. five year review process b. differentiates between major and minor criteria and immediate compliance and compliance within one year c. continuous improvement is part of impact area prosperity and included as a major point in Criteria 3.2
Assurance of quality	RSPO makes reference to ISO 9001 QMS (Management documents are documented information and evidence to interact with the RSPO P&C. It shall be in the form of manual, working procedures, report and records that subject to be audited and reviewed periodically), There is also a strong focus on record keeping
Impact assessment	RSPO has a mission to monitor and evaluate the economic, environmental and social impacts of the uptake of certified sustainable palm oil in the market. RSPO continuously monitors the impact of their work and reports in impact reports. RSPO's impact report 2022 is published and publicly available. It includes impact on human rights, smallholders, protection and restoring nature, preventing fire, limiting climate change, advancing certification, transforming markets
Risk management	In the RSPO certification system risk assessments are part of the standards, especially in relation to health and safety. The RSPO Risk Unit is responsible for managing, monitoring and assessing risks identified by the RSPO Secretariat in relation to RSPO Members.
Cost of certification	An up-to-date overview of the fee structure can be obtained from https://rspo.org/as-an-organisation/marketplace/fees/ . Additional costs occur for the audit, charged by the CB.
Sustainability Principles and Criteria	
Reference Document	The central sustainability requirements for RSPO are described in the document "RSPO Principle and Criteria" and "RSPO supply chain certification standards". Next to these standards there are various specific standards and interpretations available including an extensive standard for smallholder certification.

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Major Must and Minor Must	The RSPO standard differentiates between critical (C) indicators and other indicators. Indicators marked with (C) indicate Critical and any non-compliance against this indicator (i.e. indicator marked as (C)) shall be graded as Major non-compliance. Non-compliance against indicators without marking with (C) shall be graded as Minor non-compliance.
Environmental	
Reduce GHG emissions	Minimising GHG emissions is covered by critical indicators: 1. GHG emissions are identified and assessed for the unit of certification. Plans to reduce or minimize them are implemented, monitored through the Palm GHG calculator and publicly reported. 2. the carbon stock of the proposed development area and major potential sources of emissions that may result directly from the development are estimated and a plan to minimize them prepared and implemented (following the RSPO GHG Assessment Procedure for New Development). Principle 7, Indicator 7.10.1 and 7.10.2
Protection of land with high carbon stock	Preservation of high carbon stock is covered by critical indicators: Land clearing does not cause deforestation or damage any area required to protect or enhance High Conservation Values (HCVs) or High Carbon Stock (HCS) forest. HCVs and HCS forests in the managed area are identified and protected or enhanced Principle 7, Criteria 7.12, Indicators 7.12.1, 7.12.2 and 7.12.4
Protection of peatland	Preservation of peatland is covered by critical indicators: No new planting on peat, regardless of depth after 15 November 2018 and all peatlands are managed responsibly. Principle 7, Criteria 7.7
Promote sustainable forest management	n/a
Protection of land with a high biodiversity value	Preservation of high biodiversity values is covered by critical indicators: Land clearing does not cause deforestation or damage any area required to protect or enhance High Conservation Values (HCVs) or High Carbon Stock (HCS) forest. HCVs and HCS forests in the managed area are identified and protected or enhanced Principle 7, Criteria 7.12, Indicators 7.12.1, 7.12.2 and 7.12.4
Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity	Measures to enhance biodiversity covered within the critical criteria: An integrated management plan to protect and/or enhance HCVs, HCS forests, peatland and other conservation areas is developed, implemented and adapted where necessary, and contains monitoring requirements. Principle 7, Criteria 7.12.4
Sustainable use of water	Requirement of a water management plan. Water criteria covered with principle: Practices maintain the quality and availability of surface and groundwater. Criteria 7.8. The criteria contained are mostly non-critical
Maintaining and enhancing water quality	Requirement of a water management plan. Water criteria covered with principle: Practices maintain the quality and availability of surface and groundwater. Criteria 7.8. The criteria contained are mostly non-critical
Maintaining and enhancing soil quality and productivity	Soil quality related criteria: 7.4 soil fertility, 7.5 soil erosion, 7.6 soil surveys. The criteria contained are mostly non-critical. Soil suitability maps or soil surveys should be done by independent experts.
Soil quality consideration for use of residual flows	n/a
Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals	Covered by Criteria 7.2, Indicator 7.2.5 Pesticides that are categorised as World Health Organisation Class 1A or 1B, or that are listed by the Stockholm or Rotterdam Conventions, and paraquat, are not used, unless in exceptional circumstances, as validated by a due diligence process, or when authorised by government authorities for pest outbreaks.
Implement best practices for the use of (agro)chemicals	Covered by Criteria 7.1 Pests, diseases, weeds and invasive introduced species are effectively managed using appropriate Integrated Pest Management (IPM) techniques 7.2 Pesticides are used in ways that do not endanger health of workers, families, communities or the environment
Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality	Various requirements included: Criteria 3.4 Part of SEIA assessment of activities with impact on air quality; Indicator 7.10.3 Other (non-GHG) significant pollutants are identified and plans to reduce or minimise them implemented and monitored; Indicator 7.11.1 Land for new plantings or replanting is not prepared by burning
Limit the risk of Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC)	In SEIA definition indirect effects are mentioned, no explicit criteria exist on this. "This process incorporates relevant environmental and social data, as well as stakeholder consultations, in order to identify potential impacts (both direct and indirect) and to determine whether these impacts can be satisfactorily addressed, in which case the proponent also defines specific actions to minimise and mitigate potential negative impacts"
Circularity	
Promote waste reduction and responsible waste management	These aspects are included in the standard via the request for: a waste management plan, proper disposal of waste material, the prohibition of open fire for waste disposal. Criteria 7.3
Raw material efficiency	Part of the waste management plan is improving the efficiency of resource utilisation and recycling potential wastes as nutrients or converting them into value-added products. Criteria 7.3

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Efficient use of energy	This aspect is covered in the RSPO standard. A plan for improving efficiency of the use of fossil fuels and to optimise renewable energy has to be in place, monitored and reported. Criteria 7.9
Promote use of renewable sources	This aspect is covered in the RSPO standard. A plan for improving efficiency of the use of fossil fuels and to optimise renewable energy has to be in place, monitored and reported. Criteria 7.9
Promote material circularity	n/a
Social	
Compliance with labour rights	RSPO requires compliance to all labour rights aspects as covered by Principle 6 Protect workers' rights and ensure safe and decent working conditions. a) no forced labour Criteria 2.2, 6.6. b) no child labor Criteria 6.4 c) freedom for association and collective bargaining Criteria 6.3, d) fair salary Criteria 6.2, e) equal opportunities, no form of discrimination Criteria 6.1, and f) grievance mechanism in place Criteria 6.5
Respect wellbeing of workers	RSPO Principle 6 specifically covers wellbeing of the workers. a) occupational health and safety Criteria 3.6 and 6.7, b) no harassment Criteria 6.5, c) training Criteria 3.7, d) employment contracts Criteria 2.2, 6.2 e) working times Criteria 6.2
Respect property and usage rights	Respect of land use rights is covered fully in RSPO Criteria 4.4, 4.5, 4.6, 4.7 and 4.8
Respect wellbeing of the local population	Promotion of the wellbeing of the local community is guaranteed through Criteria 4.3 local sustainable development which covers access to health, quality education, clean water and sanitation; Criteria 4.2 system for complaints and grievances; Criteria 7.2 consideration of health of communities; Criteria 7.12 development should be proportional to the needs of the local community
Food security	RSPO includes this requirement by a) An assessment that should be made including the impact on all dimensions of food and water security including the right to adequate food, and monitoring food and water security for affected communities Criteria 3.4; b) The unit of certification should support the implementation of existing national strategies with regard to food and water security, and not contradict them by any of its business activities. Criteria 4.5; c) Support/enhance/secure food and water security as part of Criteria 4.3.
Economic	
Financial and economic viability	RSPO covers this by the request that top management should be able to demonstrate attention to economic and financial viability through long-term management planning Criteria 3.1 and reviews of the economic performance Criteria 3.2.
Fair business practices, Integrity	RSPO covers this by the requirement for fair conduct of business and a prohibition of all forms of corruption, bribery and fraudulent use of funds and resources Criteria 1.2
Promote local development, Inclusive economic growth	RSPO covers this through Criteria 4.3 as the certification should contribute to local sustainable development which covers: Reduction of poverty and Where candidates for employment are of equal merit, giving preference to members of local communities.
Use of knowledge and technology	This aspect is not explicitly covered in the RSPO documents. However, can be implicitly covered in the requirement of a plan (monitored and reported) for improving efficiency of the use of fossil fuels and to optimise renewable energy is in place. Criteria 7.9
Fair trade and market practices	Covered by RSPO by the requirement that the unit of certification commits to ethical conduct in all business operations and transactions Principle 1.2 and with requirement for collaboration with smallholders in fair pricing and transparent contracts Criteria 5.1.
Risk assessment and management	RSPO requires an implemented management plan for the unit of certification that aims to achieve long-term economic and financial viability. Criteria 3.2. Risk assessment is not explicitly written.

Date completed: 22 March 2023

Sources:

- RSPO website <https://rspo.org> (last visited: 22 March 2023)
- RSPO P&C Metrics Template https://view.officeapps.live.com/op/view.aspx?src=https%3A%2F%2Frspo.org%2Fwp-content%2Fuploads%2FRSPO_PC_Metrics_Template_version_2.1_.xlsx&wdOrigin=BROWSELINK
- <https://rspo.org/resources/?category=2019-rspo-independent-smallholder-ish-standard>
- [RSPO Certification Systems Document - November 2020-ENG-1.pdf](#)

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

- <https://rspo.org/wp-content/uploads/rspo-principles-criteria-for-production-of-sustainable-palm-oil-2018revised-01-february-2020-with-updated-supply-chain-requirements-for-mills.pdf>
- <https://rspo.org/wp-content/uploads/RSPO-Impact-Report-2022.pdf>

6.7 Factsheet Bonsucro

This factsheet aims to provide accessible and factual information on the Bonsucro certification scheme. This factsheet presents the actual status of the scheme in March 2023. For more detailed information on the system, the reader may visit the website of the certification scheme or contact the scheme owner.

Disclaimer: The information contained in this factsheet is for informational purpose only and cannot be used in replacement of the official Bonsucro standards and procedures

Table 15 Factsheet Bonsucro

Scheme Feature	Description
General	
Name of scheme	Bonsucro (formerly called Better Sugarcane Initiative (BSI))
Scheme owner	Bonsucro is the leading global sustainability platform and standard for sugarcane, one of the world's most important crops. Its purpose is to collectively accelerate the sustainable production and use of sugarcane. Bonsucro convenes over 300 members from more than 50 countries to address critical challenges in the sugarcane sector and drive both performance and impact through its system of sustainability standards. The organisation works across all sugarcane products and derivatives – sugar, ethanol, molasses, and bagasse in traditional and newer market sectors, from sugar and alcohol to biofuels and bioplastics.
Website	https://bonsucro.com/
Label provided	
Operational since	2009
Number of active certificates	235 certified entities Can be consulted at https://bonsucro.com/certified-members-3/
Standard ownership	Private
General objective	The purpose of Bonsucro is "to collectively accelerate the sustainable production and uses of sugarcane".
Scope	
Biomass feedstock coverage	Specific type of feedstock - Sugarcane
Sector/Product group coverage	Bonsucro standard covers all sugarcane products and derivatives – sugar, ethanol, molasses, and bagasse in traditional and newer market sectors, from sugar and alcohol to biofuels and bioplastics.
Supply chain coverage	Bonsucro standard covers production, processing and trade around the world.
Geographic focus of the standard	Global
Governance, Standard Development and Certification Requirements	
Scheme governance	Bonsucro is governed by a Board of Directors, who are the Legal Members of Bonsucro. The Board exercises ultimate responsibility for Bonsucro, while delegating the day-to-day responsibility for managing the organisation to the CEO and Secretariat team. The Board of Directors delegates responsibility to specific Committees (e.g., Finance & Risk Committee; Governance and Nominations Committee; Human Resources and remuneration Committee), Technical Advisory Board and ad hoc task groups to support in its work. The Members' Council (MC) has been

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	created as the representative body for Bonsucro members. The Chair and Vice Chair of the MC both also sit on the Board of Directors and so can ensure a cross flow of information and views between the bodies
Standard documents	Bonsucro Certification system consists of standards, Guidance for implementation and the Bonsucro Certification Protocol. There are three standards for Bonsucro certification– two on the production side of the supply chain, the Production standard and Production Standard for smallholders, and one on the trading side of the supply chain, the Chain of Custody standard. Also, there is the EU RED standard. Bonsucro has a library of tools and documents on its website: https://bonsucro.com/certification-tools/ and https://bonsucro.com/tools-and-resources/
Transparency and accessibility of standard documents	Transparency through freely accessible Bonsucro standard documents and information is available in different languages as English, Portuguese and Spanish predominantly (https://bonsucro.com/public-qms-library/).
Multi-stakeholder participation in standard development	Bonsucro is a multi-stakeholder non-profit organization and supports over 300 members in over 50 countries, from all elements of the sugarcane supply chain, including farmers, millers, traders, buyers and support organizations.
Compliance with ISEAL's Standards-Setting, Impacts and Assurance Codes of Good Practice	Bonsucro is ISEAL Code Compliant member of ISEAL alliance. The system has been independently evaluated against ISEAL's Codes of Good Practice.
Compliance with regional, national, international laws	Ensured by Principle 1. Indicator 1.3.1 The operator has a system in place to promote compliance with all applicable local, national, and ratified international laws and regulations.
Reference to standards and policies	General requirements for Bonsucro certification system are in line with ISO 17065:2012 and Certification bodies audit personnel shall follow guidelines included in ISO19011:2011. The scope of the Bonsucro Certification System can be with or without compliance with the EU Renewable Energy Directive (RED), its similar provisions in the EU Fuel Quality Directive (FQD) and their amendments as per Directive 2015/1513. As such, the Bonsucro Certification System makes a distinction between: 1. Compliance with Bonsucro requirements 2. Compliance with Bonsucro EU requirements: Bonsucro requirements plus additional requirements that are needed for EU RED compliance.
Obligation for certification	The Bonsucro Certification System is applicable to sugarcane farms, sugarcane mills, sugarcane Smallholders farmers and operators in the supply chain. The standard applies to any economic operator wishing to sell or buy sugarcane and sugarcane derived products as Bonsucro certified and make related claims. Retailers and distributors of finished products do not need certification.
Certification process	There are 7 steps to achieve a Bonsucro certification: Step 1. Initial contact, Step 2. Download documents & tools, Step 3. Establish certification team and define scope of certification, Step 4. Increase capacity and attend training, Step 5. Perform gap analysis, Step 6. Establish roadmap to certification, Step 6. Schedule a pre-audit or full audit: Contract a Bonsucro Licensed Certification Body to carry out an audit of the mill and farms), Step 7. Schedule a pre-audit or full audit: Achieve Bonsucro certification and start selling Bonsucro certified products and communicating to your stakeholders your achievement on product claims and credit trading.
Traceability and Chain of custody	Bonsucro follows a mass balance approach for tracing Bonsucro certified claims in the supply chain. Further information is provided in Bonsucro Mass Balance Chain of Custody Standard Version 5.1
Verification of compliance	The verification of compliance with the Bonsucro requirements as well as the issuance of certificates are performed by recognised third-party certification bodies that hold valid License Agreements with Bonsucro.
Accreditation of Certification Bodies	The CB shall be accredited or comply with ISO 17065. Part A of the Bonsucro Certification Protocol v5.1 sets out the process and procedures that a certification body (CB) shall follow to obtain accreditation from Bonsucro to carry out audits against the Bonsucro Production and Mass Balance Chain of Custody Standards and there is the Bonsucro Accreditation and Oversight Procedure that sets the CB monitoring process.
Training of auditors and staff and qualification and evaluation of competencies	Accredited CBs shall be responsible for attending CB training when necessary, and as requested by Bonsucro, and remaining up to date with Bonsucro requirements. Technical managers and Lead Auditors are required to pass a Bonsucro exam in order to receive a certificate to be able to qualify.
Audit process	Audits are carried out by licenced third-party certification bodies. Bonsucro certificates are issued following a successful audit during which the certification body verifies the compliance with all applicable Bonsucro requirements.
Frequency of audit	After the initial audit, the CB shall carry out audits following a three (3) year certification cycle. Two (2) surveillance audits, in a 12-month period, shall be carried out during the certification cycle before the next re-certification audit.
Internal audit	The operator ensures that internal monitoring processes are conducted, corrective actions implemented & management review conducted
Certification claims and labels	For public communication the operator shall comply with the logo use requirements as set out in Bonsucro Claim and Labelling Rules and License Agreement (https://bonsucro.com/claims/).

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Sanctions, non-conformities and suspension	After each audit (i.e., initial, surveillance and re-certification), the economic operator receives a compliance audit report from the Certification Body identifying the nonconformities any agreed corrective actions and deadline for implementation/verification. NCs are graded according to indicator 18. Conformity Level Grading of the Certification Protocol v6, and the deadlines and issuance of certificate are set according to Table 9: Corrective action plans management from the Certification Protocol v6. The economic operator must correct all NCs on Core indicator before certification decision either for Systemic or Incidental NC. For non-core indicator, must correct at least a required number of NCs to meet the pass rate to receive a certificate. Suspensions and withdraw follows the indicators 23. Suspension and Withdrawal from the Certification Protocol v6.
Complaint and appeal mechanisms	Bonsucro has a publicly available Grievance Mechanism, specifying the procedure to follow to submit a complaint. Additionally, Bonsucro offers the possibility for stakeholders to report on the actions of a Bonsucro certificate holder or of a Bonsucro licensed certification body. https://bonsucro.com/complaints-and-grievances/
Guarantee smallholder inclusiveness of the standard	To widen access to certification, Bonsucro launched the Production Standard for Smallholder Farmers in 2018. It is based on the rigorous Production Standard but has been adapted to facilitate collecting data on a much smaller scale to ensure the cost for implementation is lower and inclusive.
Promote continuous improvement	A standard review process takes place at least every five years. The standard distinguished between core and non-core indicators. For certified companies the standard requires conformity with Principle 3 Criterion 3.1 To monitor production and process efficiency; to measure the impacts of production and processing so that improvements are made over time.
Assurance of quality	The CB is responsible for developing and implementing a documented quality management system reflecting all Bonsucro requirements, supporting the audit team with requirements interpretation. Additionally, Bonsucro requires certified companies to operate a quality management system to ensure and demonstrate the correct implementation and maintenance of Bonsucro Standard(s).
Impact assessment	In 2021, Bonsucro launched its new five-year strategic plan, Changing for Good. It presents how Bonsucro will grow and provide a stronger and more specific focus on climate action and human rights. It also sets out plans to develop an impact fund, support more smallholder farmers, and improve use of data and digitisation. Bonsucro Outcome Reports are publicly available on the website and published every year.
Risk management	For companies wishing to get certified certification body carries out a risk to be included in the audit report. For certified companies the standard requires conformity with Principle 1 Criterion 1.1. Leadership demonstrated through enactment of commitment, context analysis, stakeholder mapping & risk assessments
Cost of certification	No explicit and general information is available for the costs of the whole certification process. To achieve certification with the Bonsucro Standards, companies must be members of Bonsucro. Fees for Bonsucro membership are payable annually and differ depending on the nature of the business. Membership fees can be found at: https://bonsucro.com/join-the-network-2/
Sustainability Principles and Criteria Reference Document	
Major Must and Minor Must	The “Bonsucro Production Standard” defines principles and criteria for certification for achieving sustainable production of sugarcane and all sugarcane derived products in respect of economic, social and environmental dimensions. The Standard is used by Bonsucro members who wish to achieve certification. It is also used by Licensed Certification Bodies and auditors when carrying out certification audits. The current Production Standard is the version 5.1 that is under an interim revision for version 5.2; and the previous version 4.2 that is also in force until December 2023.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Core indicators: which must be complied with. These are identified with the term 'Core' in the column “scope” throughout the Standard. • Non-core indicators: which must be complied with in line with the certification decision section of the Bonsucro Certification Protocol V6
Environmental	
Reduce GHG emissions	Principle 3.2 to monitor global warming emissions with a view to minimising climate change impacts. Available the Bonsucro Calculator providing certified operations with an effective tool to assess and take action on their GHG emissions.
Protection of land with high carbon stock	Principle 4 indicator 4.1.3 The operator ensures that no areas of natural ecosystems defined internationally or nationally as legally protected has been converted to agriculture on or after 1st of January 2008
Protection of peatland	Principle 4 indicator 4.1.3 The operator ensures that no areas of natural ecosystems defined internationally or nationally as legally protected has been converted to agriculture on or after 1st of January 2008
Promote sustainable forest management	n/a

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Protection of land with a high biodiversity value	Principle 4 criterion 4.1 To protect and rehabilitate biodiversity and ecosystem services, as well as maintaining and enhancing high conservation values (HCVs), indicator 4.1.5 – The operator ensures that cane expansion is from non-HCV areas following certification.
Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity	Implicitly covered in Principle 4 indicator 4.1.2 The operator develops and implements a Biodiversity Management Plan (BMP)
Sustainable use of water	Principle 4 criterion 4.3 Water Stewardship Plan in place.
Maintaining and enhancing water quality	Principle 4 criterion 4.3 Water Stewardship Plan in place, indicator 4.3.6 The operator minimises detrimental effects of waste discharge
Maintaining and enhancing soil quality and productivity	Principle 4 criterion 4.2 Soil Management Plan in place to avoid erosion and maintain and improve soil health
Soil quality consideration for use of residual flows	n/a
Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals	Principle 4 indicator 4.4.4 The operator only applies legal & safe agrochemicals
Implement best practices for the use of (agro)chemicals	Principle 4 criterion 4.4 Pest, Disease and Weed Management Plans in place and criterion 4.5 To ensure hazardous chemicals and materials do not negatively impact biodiversity and ecosystem services
Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality	Principle 5 criterion 5.2 To reduce emissions and effluents. Indicator 5.2.1 The operator comply with point source air emissions legislation.
Limit the risk of Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC)	No specific criterion. It is indicated in the standard that ILUC is difficult to estimate.
Circularity	
Promote waste reduction and responsible waste management	Principle 5 Criterion 5.2 To reduce emissions and effluents. To promote recycling of waste streams where practical
Raw material efficiency	Principle 3 Criterion 3.1 To monitor production and process efficiency; to measure the impacts of production and processing so that improvements are made over time
Efficient use of energy	Principle 3 indicator 3.2.5 3.2.5 The Operator maximises the energy return on energy invested
Promote use of renewable sources	Not explicitly covered
Promote material circularity	n/a
Social	
Compliance with labour rights	Principle 2. Criterion 2.3 To respect workers right to favourable working conditions, and 2.4 To safeguard respect for labour rights through functioning social dialogue mechanisms
Respect wellbeing of workers	Principle 2. Criterion 2.1 To provide a safe and healthy working environment in workplace operations, Criterion 2.2 To provide all workers (including migrant, seasonal and other contract labour) with benefits and salary sufficient to achieve an adequate standard of living, Criterion 5.3 To train workers and other workers in all areas of their work and develop their general skills, and Criterion 5.4 Continuous improvement of worker welfare
Respect property and usage rights	Principle 2. Criterion 2.5 Use of land and water resources does not diminish the legal, customary or user rights of indigenous peoples and local communities.
Respect wellbeing of the local population	Implicitly covered by Indicator 1.2.3 The operator conducts and documents an improvement opportunity assessment outside the unit of certification (that identifies opportunities to address adverse social and environmental conditions)
Food security	Not explicitly covered
Economic	
Financial and economic viability	Principle 5. Criterion 5.1 To promote economic and social sustainability.
Fair business practices, Integrity	Criterion 1.1.1 The operator develops and implements sustainability policies, which covers anti-corruption, anti-bribery
Promote local development, Inclusive economic growth	Implicitly covered by Criterion 1.2.4 The operator develops and implements a continuous improvement plan to address the salient opportunities identified outside the unit of certification (defines and prioritises actions the operator shall take to narrow environmental and social gaps between certification area and supplier area)

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Use of knowledge and technology	Implicitly covered by Criterion 3.1 To monitor production and process efficiency; to measure the impacts of production and processing so that improvements are made over time
Fair trade and market practices	No specific criterion.
Risk assessment and management	Principle 1. Criterion 1.2.2 The operator conducts a risk analysis on compliance against the Bonsucro Production Standard

Date completed: 20 March 2023

Sources:

- Bonsucro website <https://bonsucro.com/> (Last visited: 19 March 2023)
- Bonsucro library of tools and documents <https://bonsucro.com/certification-tools/> (Last visited: 19 March 2023)

6.8 Factsheet Better Cotton

This factsheet aims to provide accessible and factual information on the Better Cotton certification scheme. This factsheet presents the actual status of the scheme in April 2023. For more detailed information on the system, the reader may visit the website of the certification scheme or contact the scheme owner.

Disclaimer: The information contained in this factsheet is for informational purpose only and cannot be used in replacement of the official Better Cotton standards and procedures

Table 16 Factsheet Better Cotton

Scheme Feature	Description
General	
Name of scheme	Better Cotton
Scheme owner	The Better Cotton Initiative is a non-profit, multistakeholder governance group that promotes better standards in cotton farming and practices across 21 countries.
Website	https://bettercotton.org/
Label provided	
Operational since	2010 (founded in 2005)
Number of active certificates	2.2 million Licensed Better Cotton Farmers (according to Better Cotton 2021 Annual report)
Standard ownership	Private
General objective	The purpose of the BCI is to make global cotton production better for the people who produce it, better for the environment it grows in and better for the sector's future. BCI connects people and organisations from across the cotton sector, from field to store, to promote measurable and continuing improvements for the environment, farming communities and the economies of cotton producing areas.
Scope	
Biomass feedstock coverage	Specific type of feedstock – Cotton.
Sector/Product group coverage	The BCI covers the cotton sector and products made from cotton. The BCI scheme covers cotton fiber, cottonseed, and cotton products such as yarn, fabric, and apparel. However, it's important to note that the BCI does not certify finished products, but rather the cotton used to produce those products.
Supply chain coverage	The BCI works with a wide range of stakeholders in the cotton industry, including farmers, ginners, traders, spinners, weavers, knitters, and retailers. The BCI certification scheme covers the entire cotton production process, from farming to manufacturing, and focuses on promoting sustainable farming practices, improving the livelihoods of cotton farmers and workers, and reducing the environmental impact of cotton production.
Geographic focus of the standard	Global
Governance, Standard Development and Certification Requirements	
Scheme governance	Better Cotton is governed by a Council, an elected multi-stakeholder board. The Council sits at the centre of the organisation and is responsible for the strategic direction. Council Members come from the organisations and companies that represent four different Better Cotton membership categories: Civil society, Producer Organisations, Retailers & Brands, and Suppliers & Manufacturers. Each category has up to three seats. Each category has up to three seats, two elected by the General Assembly, made up of 2,100+ Better Cotton Members, and one nominated by

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	the existing Council. A global group of secretariat staff, led by the Better Cotton Executive Group and Leadership Team, manage day-to-day operations and act as the conduit between Council decision-making and ground-level action.
Standard documents	Better Cotton certification system (among others) includes the following main documents: BCI Principles and Criteria, the Better Cotton Assurance Model, Chain of Custody Guidelines, and Better Cotton Claims Framework.
Transparency and accessibility of standard documents	Transparency through freely accessible Better Cotton standard documents and information is available in different languages upon request and on the BCI website.
Multi-stakeholder participation in standard development	The Better Cotton Initiative is a non-profit, multistakeholder group that promotes better standards in cotton farming and practices across 21 countries. Council members are drawn from the organisations and companies that represent the four major Better Cotton membership categories: retailers and brands, suppliers and manufacturers, producer organisations and civil society. The General Assembly, made up of 2,100+ Better Cotton Members from across the cotton supply chain and beyond elects the Council.
Compliance with ISEAL's Standards-Setting, Impacts and Assurance Codes of Good Practice	The Better Cotton Initiative is ISEAL Code Compliant and therefore has successfully undergone independent evaluations against the ISEAL Codes of Good Practice in Standards-Setting, Assurance and Impacts.
Compliance with regional, national, international laws	Section 1.4 Scope of Better Cotton Principles & Criteria (P&C) states that underpinning the P&C is the fundamental premise that producing Better Cotton respects national and other applicable law. Cotton producers should always abide by national legislation, unless that legislation sets standards that are below the referenced internationally recognised standards and conventions, in which case, the international standards prevail. However, where national legislation sets higher requirements on a specific issue than these standards, national legislation applies.
Reference to standards and policies	References are provided for the Better Cotton Principles and Criteria development: The ISEAL Code of Good Practice for Setting Social and Environmental Standards (v. 6.0); The Better Cotton Assurance Programme; The Better Cotton Standard Setting and Revision Procedure; The Procedure for Developing Local Interpretation of BCI Global Standards.
Obligation for certification	Under the Better Cotton assurance model, all Producers require a Licensing Assessment before they can receive a licence to sell Better Cotton. Licensing Assessments are field-based visits that assess compliance against Core Indicators in the Better Cotton Principles & Criteria and monitor progress against continuous improvement priorities. Under the Better Cotton Standard System, farms are differentiated into three categories: Smallholders, medium farms and large farms. Smallholders and Medium Farms are grouped into Producer Units (PUs) and are licensed to sell Better Cotton at the PU level. Large Farms are licensed to sell Better Cotton on an individual farm basis.
Certification process	Certification process includes registering participation, completing a self-assessment survey, commissioning a Licencing agreement with an approved third-party verifier, review of conformance by the Better Cotton Assurance Managers and receiving licencing based on the evaluation. Further information is provided in The Better Cotton Assurance Manual v4.3.
Traceability and Chain of custody	The Better Cotton Chain of Custody Guidelines set out requirements for organisations in the supply chain that are buying or selling Better Cotton or cotton-containing products as BCI Orders. The Better Cotton Chain of Custody Guidelines incorporate two different chain of custody models: product segregation between the farm and gin and mass balance beyond the gin. Between the farm and gin level, this includes cotton produced by licensed BCI Farmers in accordance with the Better Cotton P&C which must be kept segregated from conventional cotton. This ensures that all Better Cotton bales produced by registered BCI gins are 100% Better Cotton and can be traced back to licensed BCI Farmers. After the gin level, BCI Orders are bought or sold together with 'Better Cotton' claims using mass balance model. Refer to the Better Cotton Claims Framework for more detail on the claims that can be made when sourcing or selling products associated with Better Cotton claims.
Verification of compliance	The verification of compliance with the BCI requirements combines assessments by approved third-party verifiers along with assessments by trained Better Cotton staff members, support visits by Programme Partners (for Producer Units only), and regular self-assessments by producers themselves. Programme Partners are organisations with local expertise who oversee the setup and management of Producer Units under the Better Cotton assurance model.
Accreditation of Certification Bodies	Approval Procedures for Verifiers document presents the different procedures developed by the BCI for approving third-party verifiers: what are the core competencies required, the application/approval procedures in place. Reference to third-party accreditation bodies accrediting the certification bodies (ISO 17065 compliance) was not found in this document. The application procedure for prospective third-party verifiers seeking BCI approval is made of 4 different steps: Send in the completed verifier application form; Participate in an interview with BCI; If recommended after the interview, participate in BCI training for verifiers as required and address any conditions required by BCI prior to approval; Successfully pass the verifier assessment at the end of the training program Verification organisations who have successfully completed the

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	application process, addressed any additional conditions stipulated by BCI, had their Lead Verifiers attend the training workshop and passed the online training assessment, will be eligible to conduct third-party verification visits on the Better Cotton Principles and Criteria.
Training of auditors and staff and qualification and evaluation of competencies	The Better Cotton third party verifiers (3PV) Qualifications and Competency Requirements lists the qualifications and competencies that a lead verifier must have, are desirable as well as a verification mechanism to evaluate them. Verification organisations will need to implement an on-going training programme to ensure that all verifiers meet the Qualifications and Competencies requirements.
Audit process	The audit process consists of first-party audits in the form of producer self-assessment, and Licensing Assessments comprising either 2 nd party audits (conducted by BCI) or 3 rd party audits (conducted by an approved third-party verifier) conducted prior to a license being granted. A license is valid for 3 years and the producer must undergo a new Licensing Assessment at the end of the active license period to demonstrate continued compliance. In addition to Licensing Assessments, Surveillance Assessments are carried out on a sample of licensed PUs in the second or third year of an active licence.
Frequency of audit	At minimum, producers will undergo an external audit (either 2 nd party conducted by BCI or 3 rd party) every three years. Licensed Producer Units are also subject to Surveillance Assessments at BCI's discretion during their active 3-year license period; these Surveillance Assessments would be conducted in the second or third year of an active license.
Internal audit	To be licensed to sell Better Cotton, producers must submit an annual self-assessment survey on producer practices. The results of the self-assessment are not directly linked to licensing; they are used instead to help the PU or Large Farm Manager identify improvement areas. Self-assessment results may also be used by third-party verifiers (3PVs), Programme Partners (PPs), or Better Cotton teams to help prepare for an assessment or monitoring visit.
Certification claims and labels	The Better Cotton Claims Framework enables Members to make credible and positive claims about Better Cotton. The Claims Framework equips members to make credible and positive claims about Better Cotton while allowing flexibility in how to communicate about their commitment. The BCI Logo Guidelines set guidelines for the correct use of the logo.
Sanctions, non-conformities and suspension	Non-conformities (NCs) identified during Licensing Assessments and Surveillance Assessments are graded as either incidental or systemic. For incidental non-conformities: Corrective action plan to be completed within ten working days of being notified of assessment findings. The Producer has six months to implement corrective actions to prevent the identified non-conformity from re-occurring in future. BCI staff verify the implementation of corrective actions, either through a remote evidence review and/or through a site visit. For Systemic non-conformities: The Producer is denied a licence (for a Surveillance Assessment, the PU's active licence is cancelled). Corrective action plan to be completed within ten working days of being notified of assessment findings and implementation of corrective actions is checked during the subsequent Licensing Assessment. Additionally, Criterion 7.4 of the Better Cotton Principles and Criteria: The Producer must monitor and review risks of noncompliance and implementation of corrective actions.
Complaint and appeal mechanisms	In the case of complaints against the conduct and/or performance of the third-party verifiers, producers have the option of initiating the Appeals Process if they feel a licence has been incorrectly refused. Appeals process is explained in section 21 of the Better Cotton Assurance Manual. There is also the BCI Grievance Management Process which can be activated by other BCI members and stakeholders formally involved in BCI to address concerns about verifiers. Better Cotton recognises that anyone that engages with Better Cotton activities, people or programmes has the right to raise a complaint. There are two ways in which to report a complaint. By filling the Better Cotton complaints form or send a report directly to complaints@bettercotton.org . The Better Cotton Complaints Policy and Procedures has been developed that provides clear guidance on how to raise a complaint, how complaints are handled and what to do if a complaint is not satisfactorily resolved.
Guarantee smallholder inclusiveness of the standard	Under the Better Cotton Standard System, farms are differentiated into three categories: Smallholders, medium farms and large farms. Smallholders and Medium Farms are grouped into Producer Units (PUs) and are licensed to sell Better Cotton at the PU level. Farmers in a Smallholder Producer Unit are further divided into Learning Groups (LGs) of approximately 35 farmers (with a Lead Farmer in each one) managed by a Field Facilitator (FF) to help facilitate learning. Typically, each FF in a Smallholder PU will work with about 10 Learning Groups, or 350 farmers at a maximum. This helps to ensure the FF can have regular contact and visits with each farmer.
Promote continuous improvement	The Better Cotton P&C undergoes a periodic revision (at least once every five years) to ensure the requirements remain locally relevant, effective and up to date with innovative agricultural and social practices. The revision consists of an iterative process of drafting and various stakeholder consultations. It follows the ISEAL's Standard-Setting Code of Good Practice v.6.0, which sets out best practice guidelines to develop or revise sustainability standards. The Better Cotton Standard System approaches more sustainable cotton production as a journey of

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	continuous improvement. Producers are required under Core Indicator 7.1.1 to demonstrate ongoing sustainability improvements through the development and implementation of a Continuous Improvement Plan.
Assurance of quality	The Better Cotton Assurance Manual v4.3 document sets out the main requirements of the Better Cotton assurance model for key stakeholders. It is intended to be a reference manual for Programme partners, Producers, Better Cotton staff, and third-party verifiers, to ensure consistent implementation of assurance requirements across all Better Cotton projects. The assurance model supports this process through providing Producers with regular assessment and feedback. Quality assurance is part of the licensing process where quality of the data provided, and the reporting done by the producers are checked. Incomplete or insufficient quality can lead to license cancellations. Criterion 7.3 The Producer must operate a data management system. When operating the data management system, it is important for the Producer to continuously assess their adherence to data quality principles.
Impact assessment	Results Indicator reporting is the annual collection of environmental, economic, and social data from a representative sample of smallholder farmers, and from all Medium and Large Farms. Results Indicators quantitatively measure differences between licenced Better Cotton Farmers and other farmers in the same geographic area who are not participating in the Better Cotton Programme. Via the Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning Programme, BCI analyses data from across the breadth of the cotton community and examines the results in detail to gauge improvements in social, environmental and economic performance. This ensures that sustainability improvements are measured everywhere Better Cotton projects are implemented.
Risk management	CB carries out Surveillance Assessment based on risk factors (i.e., known sustainability issues or labour violations in a specific region). The total sample of surveillance assessments varies depending on the risk factors. For Assessment Sampling farms with any compliance risks are prioritised for assessment.
Cost of certification	No complete overview was found on the overall certification costs, only for membership. Information on the Membership fees can be found in the document Better Cotton Membership Fees. Fees are different for different membership categories (Civil Society, Producer Organization, Retailers and Brands, Suppliers and Manufacturers, and Associate Members).
Sustainability Principles and Criteria	
Reference Document	The Better Cotton Principles and Criteria (P&C) document aims to assist BCI Implementing Partners in interpreting the P&C and explaining to cotton farmers both the importance of addressing the issues covered by the P&C, and the practical implications of producing Better Cotton. It also seeks to help other audiences interested in Better Cotton, such as retailers, ginners, spinners, traders, NGOs, trade unions, producer organisations and large independent cotton farmers, in better understanding the P&C.
Major Must and Minor Must	The BCI standard has two type of indicators that are color-coded in the farmer category boxes: core indicators (highlighted in red with ticks) and improvement indicators (using blue ticks). The compulsory nature of each requirement is expressed according to a simplified form of the ISO 'verbal forms for the expression of provisions': 'must', 'should', 'may' and 'can'.
Environmental	
Reduce GHG emissions	Section 2.2. of Annex 5 Climate change mitigation within the BCI Principles and Criteria. In the context of cotton production, the use of good management practices can substantially reduce GHG emissions. Reference to criterion 3.1. concerning fertilizer management to ensure optimal nitrogen oxide use and ultimately mitigate the resulting emissions and managing soil carbon to increase carbon stocks through appropriate practices.
Protection of land with high carbon stock	Principle 4 criterion 4.2 For the conversion of land used to grow cotton, the Producer must adopt the High Conservation Value approach and respect the right of local communities and indigenous people. Reversing land degradation through the adoption of a sustainable land use change approach, so that high carbon density areas are protected from significant loss. HCV2: Intact Forest Landscapes and large landscape-level ecosystems and ecosystem mosaics that are significant at global, regional or national levels, and that contain viable populations of the great majority of naturally occurring species in natural patterns of distribution and abundance. E.g., a large tract of forest, grasslands or wetlands.
Protection of peatland	Covered by Principle 4 criterion 4.2. Additionally, Principle 2 Water Stewardship. Criterion 2.1 The Producer must adopt a Water Stewardship Plan to help protect and conserve local water resources and identify opportunities for climate change adaptation. i. Mapping and understanding water resources includes mapping wetlands; iv. Managing water quality includes protecting wetlands areas
Promote sustainable forest management	n/a
Protection of land with a high biodiversity value	Principle 4 criterion 4.2 For the conversion of land used to grow cotton, the Producer must adopt the High Conservation Value approach and respect the right of local communities and indigenous people.

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity	Principle 4 criterion 4.1 The Producer must adopt a Biodiversity Management Plan that conserves and enhances biodiversity on and surrounding the farm and includes all of the following components: i. Identifying and mapping biodiversity resources; ii. Identifying and restoring degraded areas; iii. Enhancing populations of beneficial insects as per the Integrated Pest Management plan (Principle 1); iv. Ensuring crop rotation; v. Protecting riparian areas.
Sustainable use of water	Principle 2 Water Stewardship. Criterion 2.1 The Producer must adopt a Water Stewardship Plan to help protect and conserve local water resources and identify opportunities for climate change adaptation. Especially iii. Applying efficient irrigation practices to optimise water productivity, and v. Engaging in collaboration and collective action to promote sustainable water use.
Maintaining and enhancing water quality	Principle 2 Water Stewardship. Criterion 2.1 The Producer must adopt a Water Stewardship Plan to help protect and conserve local water resources and identify opportunities for climate change adaptation. Core Indicator 2.1.1: A time-bound Water Stewardship Plan is defined that addresses each of the following component iv. Managing water quality. Indicator 2.1.8 Risk to water quality is considered when managing and applying nutrients and pesticides, as per the Water Stewardship Plan.
Maintaining and enhancing soil quality and productivity	Principle 3 Soil Health. Criterion 3.1 The Producer must adopt a soil management plan to maintain and enhance soil health that includes all of the following components: i. Identifying and analysing soil type; ii. Maintaining and enhancing soil structure; iii. Maintaining and enhancing soil fertility; iv. Continuously improving nutrient cycling.
Soil quality consideration for use of residual flows	n/a
Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals	Principle 1 Criterion 1.3 Pesticides listed in: i. Annex A and B of the Stockholm Convention; or ii. Annexes of the Montreal Protocol; or iii. Annex III of the Rotterdam Convention; are not used. Criterion 1.4 The Producer must phase out the use of any pesticide active ingredients and formulations that are known or presumed to be extremely or highly hazardous (acute toxicity). Criterion 1.5 The Producer must phase out the use of any pesticide active ingredients and formulations that are known or presumed to be carcinogenic, mutagenic or reprotoxic (CMR) substances.
Implement best practices for the use of (agro)chemicals	Principle 1 Crop protection: Criterion 1.1 The Producer must adopt an Integrated Pest Management Programme. Criterion 1.2 All pesticides used are registered nationally and correctly labelled. Criterion 1.8 Producers must store, handle and clean pesticide application equipment and containers, in order to avoid environmental harm and human exposure. Criterion 1.9 Producers must apply pesticides in appropriate weather conditions, according to the directions on the label, and/or manufacturers' directions, with appropriate and well-maintained equipment. Principle 3. Soil Health: Indicator 3.1.15 Fertilisers are applied using precision agriculture technologies.
Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality	Partially covered under Principle 3 Soil Health where burning of plant residue and other organic matter should be avoided.
Limit the risk of Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC)	Not explicitly covered
Circularity	
Promote waste reduction and responsible waste management	Principle 1 Crop protection: 1.10 Producers should dispose of used pesticide containers safely, or through a collection and recycling programme. 1.8.1 The areas must fully comply with relevant legislation for the storage, handling and disposal of pesticides. Within these areas, all rinsate and runoff must be completely captured so that it poses no contamination risk.
Raw material efficiency	Principle 5 Fibre Quality: Criterion 5.1 The Producer must harvest, manage and store seed cotton to minimise trash, contamination and damage. Criterion 5.2 The Producer should adopt management practices that maximise fibre quality.
Efficient use of energy	Not explicitly covered
Promote use of renewable sources	Not explicitly covered
Promote material circularity	n/a
Social	
Compliance with labour rights	Covered under Principle 6 Decent Work: Child labour - Criterion 6.1 The Producer must ensure there is no child labour, in accordance with ILO Convention 138. In the case of family smallholdings, children may help on their family's farm provided that the work is not liable to damage their health, safety, well-being, education or development, and that they are supervised by adults and given appropriate training. Forced and compulsory labour - Criterion 6.3 The Producer must ensure there is no forced or compulsory labour, including bonded or trafficked labour.

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	<p>Equal opportunities/discrimination - Criterion 6.4 The Producer must not practise discrimination (distinction, exclusion or preference) that denies or impairs equality of opportunity, conditions or treatment based on individual characteristics, group membership or association; Criterion 6.5 The Producer must observe the principle of equal pay for equal work; Criterion 6.16 The Producer should ensure that temporary, seasonal, and (sub-) contracted workers receive equivalent benefits and employment conditions to permanent workers in relation to their period of employment. Grievance mechanism – Covered under Criterion 6.4 and 6.5.</p> <p>Association and collective bargaining - Criterion 6.11 The Producer must guarantee all workers the right to establish and join organisations of their own choosing, and to draw up their own constitutions and rules, elect representatives, formulate programmes, and bargain collectively; Criterion 6.12 The Producer should provide representatives from trade unions or other workers' organisations with access to reasonable facilities.</p> <p>Fair salary and remuneration - Criterion 6.13 The Producer must ensure that all workers – waged and piece rate – are paid wages at least equivalent to the applicable legal national minimum wage or regional norm, whichever is higher; and that workers are paid regularly, on time, and through an appropriate method of payment.</p>
Respect wellbeing of workers	<p>Covered under Principle 6 Decent Work:</p> <p>Occupational health and safety: Criterion 1.7 Producers must ensure that any person who prepares and applies pesticides always uses appropriate protective and safety equipment in a correct manner; Criterion 6.2 The Producer must ensure that for hazardous work, the minimum age is 18 years; Criterion 6.6 The Producer must provide access to safe and hygienic sanitation facilities and to potable and washing water; Criterion 6.7 The Producer must provide all workers with a clean place to eat and access to adequate medical care; Criterion 6.8 The Producer should provide workers with regular health and safety training appropriate to the work they perform; Criterion 6.9 The Producer should identify work hazards, inform workers of safe work practices, and adopt preventive measures to minimise hazards in the workplace. The Producer must maintain records of any accidents and occupational illnesses; Criterion 6.10 The Producer should ensure that measures are in place to deal with accidents and emergencies, including first aid, trained first aiders and access to appropriate transportation to medical facilities.</p> <p>Contract - Criterion 6.14 The Producer must obtain the worker's consent in advance regarding all working conditions; Criterion 6.15 The Producer should keep adequate records on employment obligations, in accordance with national law and sufficient to enable monitoring.</p> <p>Work and overtime - Criterion 6.17 The Producer should ensure that working hours comply with national laws or relevant collective agreements, whichever is more favourable to the worker; Criterion 6.18 The Producer should ensure that overtime work is voluntary and remunerated in accordance with the law or applicable collective agreements.</p> <p>Harassment/violence - Criterion 6.19 The Producer must not engage in or tolerate the use of corporal punishment, mental or physical coercion, sexual harassment, physical or verbal abuse or harassment of any kind; Criterion 6.20 The Producer must have a transparent policy and system for disciplinary measures, and must communicate this to workers.</p>
Respect property and usage rights	<p>Covered under Criterion 4.2 For the conversion of land used to grow cotton, the Producer must adopt the High Conservation Value approach and respect the right of local communities and indigenous people. Negotiating land and resource use rights through Free, Prior and Informed Consent (FPIC).</p>
Respect wellbeing of the local population	<p>Covered under Criterion 6.21 The Producer should develop partnership and collaboration on decent work at local, regional or national level. Producers should recognise their role in contributing and supporting local communities: In times of need (e.g. natural disasters) by taking advantage of equipment or facilities; In improving living standards with expertise (e.g. domestic agricultural practices); By taking advantage of equipment or facilities (e.g. providing space for community leaders to meet); Through education on caring for the environment and basic health and safety practices.</p>
Food security	n/a
Economic	
Financial and economic viability	<p>Principle 7 Management, Criterion 7.1 The Producer must develop and implement a Continuous Improvement Plan. Criterion 7.2 The Producer must ensure that BCI Farmers and workers receive regular training on best practices to achieve the Better Cotton Initiative Principles and Criteria Core Indicators and relevant Continuous Improvement Plan goals.</p>
Fair business practices, Integrity	Not explicitly covered
Promote local development, Inclusive economic growth	<p>Covered under Criterion 6.21 The Producer should develop partnership and collaboration on decent work at local, regional or national level. Producers should also engage with local communities with the aim of supporting community development and wellbeing of community members, extending decent working conditions to other employers in the community, and securing a solid base of capable workers. Community</p>

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	engagement activities can include: Establishing and managing local decent work committees with involvement from other employers in the community; Establishing or supporting child labour monitoring committees; Contributing training and development of skills, safety and development of the potential workforce or community members; Putting forward individuals for Lead Farmer roles.
Use of knowledge and technology	Covered under Principle 2 Water Stewardship. 2.1.5 Irrigation methods and technologies are implemented to improve irrigation efficiency, as per the Water Stewardship Plan (applicable to irrigated farms only), under Principle 5 Fibre Quality in managing contamination risks, as well as under Principle 1 Crop protection: enabling farmers to make informed choices about the availability of technologies, and how to use them appropriately.
Fair trade and market practices	Implicitly covered under Criterion 6.22 Producer Organisations should also collectively market members cotton production and find/negotiate outlets. While collective action in itself cannot solve all the competitive and structural challenges faced by Producers, Producer Organisation can create: An intermediary and larger business that enables them and notably smallholders to compete more effectively in the market and increase their bargaining power; A platform for producers to promote and defend their interests; A channel through which support and investment can be provided to ensure implementation of the Better Cotton Standard System.
Risk assessment and management	Principle 7 Management, Criterion 7.2 also considered an analysis of the risks perceived by farmers in adopting the improved practices, for example, in terms of an adverse impact on cotton production and/or an increase in financial inputs that may be needed to introduce the improved practices. Criterion 7.4 The Producer must monitor and review risks of noncompliance and implementation of corrective actions.

Date completed: 4 April 2023

Sources:

- Better Cotton website: <https://bettercotton.org/> (Last visited: 4 April 2023)
- Better Cotton resource library: <https://bettercotton.org/document-library/> (Last visited: 4 April 2023)

6.9 Factsheet EU Ecolabel

This factsheet aims to provide accessible and factual information on the EU Ecolabel. This factsheet presents the actual status of the ecolabel in April 2023. For more detailed information on the system, the reader may visit the website of the certification scheme or contact ecolabel owner.

Disclaimer: The information contained in this factsheet is for informational purpose only and cannot be used in replacement of the official EU Ecolabel standards and procedures

Table 17 Factsheet EU Ecolabel

Scheme Feature	Description
General	
Name of scheme	EU Ecolabel
Scheme owner	The functioning of the EU Ecolabel is set out in the official Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council (No 66/2010). The EU Ecolabel is managed by the European Commission and the Member States. The European Commission manages the EU Ecolabel at the EU level to ensure that the EU Ecolabel Regulation is implemented correctly and agrees on a Strategic Working Plan for the EU Ecolabel. Different groups involved in the management, implementation and growth of the EU Ecolabel include the European Commission, EU Ecolabelling Board, Competent Bodies, Stakeholders, and EU Ecolabel Helpdesk.
Website	https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy/eu-ecolabel-home_en
Label provided	
Operational since	1992
Number of active certificates	As of March 2023, 2367 licences have been awarded for 88045 products (goods and services) in the EU market.
Standard ownership	The EU Ecolabel is a voluntary ecolabelling scheme primarily for the EU market. The EU Ecolabel is the official European Union label for environmental excellence.
General objective	The EU Ecolabel aims to promote products and services with a reduced environmental impact during their entire life cycle and to provide consumers with accurate, non-deceptive, science-based information on the environmental impact of products. It is awarded to sustainably designed products that contribute to the EU goal of climate neutrality by 2050 and to the circular economy.
Scope	
Biomass feedstock coverage	The EU Ecolabel covers a wide range of biomass: from forestry, agricultural, as well as residual products from production and manufacturing processes such as straw from cereal production or bagasse from sugar cane production or recycled material like fibres. The label is provided on the products and not on raw materials.
Sector/Product group coverage	The EU Ecolabel covers a wide range of products that we use in our day-to-day home and work life. The products groups currently covered by the EU Ecolabel are: Cleaning, Clothing and textiles, Coverings, Do it yourself (paints and varnishes), Electronic equipment, Furniture and mattresses, Gardening, Holiday accommodation, Lubricants, Paper, and Personal and animal care products. Additionally, the EU Ecolabel is developing the following new product group criteria: Financial products, Food and feed products, and Office buildings. For this project, the 6 sectors are: plastics, construction, woodworking, textiles, pulp and paper, and chemicals. Therefore, the product groups of cleaning, clothing and textiles, coverings, paint and varnishes, furniture, lubricants, paper and personal and animal care products are most relevant.

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Supply chain coverage	EU Ecolabel encompasses the entire product life cycle and therefore considers the full supply chain.
Geographic focus of the standard	The EU Ecolabel is applied in all EU member states, and also in Norway, Liechtenstein and Iceland. EU Ecolabel is recognised worldwide.
Governance, Standard Development and Certification Requirements	
Scheme governance	<p>The EU Ecolabel has a multi-layered governance structure composed by:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. European Parliament and Council of the European Union: adopt/revise Regulation on Community Eco-label Award Scheme. 2. European Commission: manages the EU Ecolabel at the EU level to ensure correct implementation of the ecolabel. EC is responsible for preparing the final draft of the criteria documents, taking into account comments from the EU Ecolabelling Board (EUEB) 3. European Ecolabelling Board (EUEB): composed of representatives of the Competent Bodies of the European Union, Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway, and the representatives of 13 stakeholder organisations and 3 EU/UN bodies. EUEB contributes to the development and revision of Ecolabel criteria and the implementation of the EU Ecolabel scheme, gives advice and assistance to the commission in the recommendations on minimum environmental performance requirements. 4. National competent bodies: responsible for implementing the EU Ecolabel scheme at the national level, receive and assess applications and award the EU Ecolabel to products that meet the criteria set for them, work for EUEB and commenting on draft criteria (partly with financial contributions from the national authorities), manage the licensing process, seek opinions at national level of interested parties, and promote the use of the EU Ecolabel. 5. Stakeholders: take part in the development of the criteria with a balanced participation of all relevant stakeholders concerned with a particular product group, such as industry and service providers, including SMEs, and their business organisations, trade unions, traders, retailers, importers, environmental protection groups and consumer organisations must be guaranteed. 6. EU Ecolabel helpdesk: assists the European Commission with various tasks such as writing news publications, generating stakeholder support and soliciting aid for certain marketing activities. It also provides help to the public by email and phone regarding general questions about the EU Ecolabel.
Standard documents	<p>The EU Ecolabel Regulation (No 66/2010) lays down rules for the establishment and application of the voluntary European Union Ecolabel scheme, which applies to any goods or services which are supplied for distribution, consumption or use on the European Community market. These provisions regulate the award of the EU Ecolabel and terms and conditions of its use. The EU Ecolabel provides for each product group documents with information on the current criteria, the validity and application pack/user manual. The criteria and application documents can be downloaded from its website: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy/eu-ecolabel-home/product-groups-and-criteria_en. The EU Ecolabel has additional guidelines regarding use of the EU Ecolabel Catalogue (ECAT) for applicants and License holders and use of logo. The documents can be found at: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy/eu-ecolabel-home/how-apply_en</p>
Transparency and accessibility of standard documents	The EU ecolabel is transparent regarding the criteria that products must meet. Documents explaining the criteria, guidelines, application forms are publicly and freely available online. User Manuals are available to support applicants and users of EU Ecolabel.
Multi-stakeholder participation in standard development	EU Ecolabel criteria development and revision is a multi-step and multi-stakeholder process carried out according to the Annex I of the EU Ecolabel Regulation (No 66/2010). They are developed with the input of relevant stakeholders such as industry, business organisations, SMEs, environmental and consumer organisations and trade unions. The EU Ecolabel criteria development is managed by the Joint Research Centre. Every set of criteria undergoes several rounds of discussion. Criteria are finally adopted through a Decision of the European Commission.
Compliance with ISEAL's Standards-Setting, Impacts and Assurance Codes of Good Practice	The EU Ecolabel is an ISO 14024 (2018) Type 1 Ecolabel and conforms to the requirements of this international standard along with the more general ISO 14020 (2022). The EU Ecolabel does not refer to ISEAL codes. However, certification schemes that the EU Ecolabel accepts as documentation for responsibly sourced raw materials, must comply with ISEAL codes.
Compliance with regional, national, international laws	The EU Ecolabel follows international, European, or national standards. They verification of compliance shall take into consideration the net environmental balance between the environmental benefits and burdens, including health and safety aspects; where appropriate, social and ethical aspects shall be considered, e.g., by making reference to related international conventions and agreements such as relevant International Labor Organization (ILO) standards and codes of conduct.
Reference to standards and policies	The EU Ecolabel is an ISO 14024 Type 1 ecolabel and a member of the Global Ecolabelling Network. In the product criteria other standards (ISO and European standards) may apply and references are provided. This information can be found in the product criteria documents.
Obligation for certification	Producers, manufacturers, importers, service providers and wholesalers placing their products and/or services on the EEA (the European Union, Liechtenstein, Norway and Iceland) market can apply for the EU Ecolabel. Retailers can also apply for products placed on the market under their own brand name. Any product or service that is supplied for distribution, consumption or use in the EEA market can be awarded the EU Ecolabel,

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	regardless of the origin of the product. The EU Ecolabel Regulation allows manufacturers, producers and retailers based in non-European countries to apply for the EU Ecolabel on the condition that they meet the criteria for their respective product group and that the product is sold in the EEA market. The application can be made to the competent body of the country where the products are produced (if inside the EEA) or will be marketed (if outside the EEA).
Certification process	The EU Ecolabel application process consist of the following steps: 1.Contact the Competent Body (in the European Union and Iceland, Lichtenstein, and Norway), 2. Register your goods or service in the online EU Ecolabel catalogue (ECAT) or the EU Ecolabel tourist accommodation catalogue, 3. Build your application dossier with your goods and service description and testing, 4. Submit your application and pay the fees, 5. Assessment, 6. Application approval and licence award, 7. Communicate about your EU Ecolabel goods and services.
Traceability and Chain of custody	The EU Ecolabel requires a chain of custody certification system to meet the following requirements: It must be issued by an accredited, competent third party and it must assure traceability, documentation and controls throughout the production chain. The manufacturer of the EU Ecolabelled product must show that raw material suppliers are certified and provide information about traceability system. The applicable chain of custody system is provided per product group. The supplier of wood raw materials must have a valid Chain of Custody (CoC) certification under the FSC / PEFC schemes. In the case of Lubricants, the following supply chain models for the uptake of the certified palm oil and palm kernel oil products: Identify Preserved, Segregated System and Mass Balance system.
Verification of compliance	The EU Ecolabel is a Type 1 Ecolabel and requires independent third-party certification. The user of the EU Ecolabel shall allow the competent body (including its authorised agents) which has awarded the EU Ecolabel to the product to undertake all necessary investigations to monitor its on-going compliance with the product group criteria. The EU Ecolabel licence holder is the responsible to ensure criteria compliance throughout the entire validity of its licence.
Accreditation of Certification Bodies	The Competent bodies are independent and neutral organisations responsible for implementing the Community Eco-label award Scheme at national level. Competent bodies shall ensure that the verification process is carried out in a consistent, neutral and reliable manner by a party independent from the operator being verified, based on international, European or national standards and procedures concerning bodies operating product-certification schemes. The EU Ecolabel works and create synergies with European Union Eco-Management and Audit Scheme (EMAS).
Training of auditors and staff and qualification and evaluation of competencies	Competent bodies and their personnel shall carry out the conformity assessment activities with the highest degree of professional integrity and have the requisite technical knowledge and sufficient and appropriate experience to perform the conformity assessment tasks. Competent bodies shall participate in, or ensure that their assessment personnel are informed of, the relevant standardisation activities and the activities of the working group of competent bodies.
Audit process	After receiving the application, the Competent Body will examine all submitted documentation (including any material that might have been sent directly by suppliers) and gives initial feedback within two months. After all documentation has been assessed, the Competent Body may carry out an on-site visit of the operator or suppliers' sites. The Competent Body judges the necessity for this on-site visit on a case-by-case basis unless otherwise stated within the EU Ecolabel criteria and may charge a fee for it. After approval, the Competent Body communicates how often test samples of the product should be conducted to proactively verify criteria compliance. Depending on the Competent Body, factory inspections and product tests or visits may be carried out. These inspections are intended to ensure that environmental excellence is maintained for consumers.
Frequency of audit	Once the contract is in place, the competent body may at any time request the necessary documentation from the licence holder to monitor compliance of the product with the criteria and the conditions of use laid down in the contract. The competent body may also visit the premises of the license holder to ensure that the requirements are met. The use of EU Ecolabel is limited to the period of validity of the product group criteria which is usually valid for a period of three to five years, depending on the product group. Licence holders may use the EU Ecolabel starting from the date it is awarded until the end of the period of the validity of the criteria. If criteria are revised, license holders need to renew their contract. If criteria validity is prolonged, the contract is automatically renewed as long as the criteria remain valid for a product or service.
Internal audit	As a licence holder, it is the operator's responsibility to ensure criteria compliance throughout the entire validity of the licence(s). The Competent Body will explain how often test samples of the product should be conducted to proactively verify criteria compliance. The manufacturer or the supplier will need to keep a journal of all tests conducted on the goods or services along with their results. This documentation should be always available and may be requested by the Competent Body.
Certification claims and labels	The EU Ecolabel Logo Guidelines provides detailed information on the use of the EU Ecolabel logo. More information can be found at:

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy/eu-ecolabel-home/eu-ecolabel-branding_en#logo-guidelines
Sanctions, non-conformities and suspension	EU Ecolabel relays on the Competent Body to evaluate non-conformities and suspension. If the Competent body receives evidence that the goods or service no longer complies with the criteria during the validity period, the Competent Body will request an immediate Corrective Action Plan or may even prohibit the use of the EU Ecolabel on that good or service.
Complaint and appeal mechanisms	The competent body which has awarded the EU Ecolabel to the product shall inform the user of the EU Ecolabel of any complaints made concerning the product bearing the EU Ecolabel and may request the user to reply to those complaints. The competent body may withhold the identity of the complainant from the user. EU Ecolabel help desk has a “Non-compliance with EU Ecolabel criteria complaint form” online at: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy/eu-ecolabel-home/community-and-helpdesk_en
Guarantee smallholder inclusiveness of the standard	The EU ecolabel supports small, medium enterprises, micro-enterprises and operators in developing countries with specific measures to encourage small and medium sized enterprises to take part in the scheme, e.g., reduced fees, consultation procedures open to SMEs, testing and verification requirements adapted to SMEs' capabilities. The EU Ecolabel gives 25% discount for SMEs and applicants from developing countries.
Promote continuous improvement	The EU Ecolabel is a Type 1 Ecolabel according to the standard ISO 14024 which requires a development through continuous improvements and regular evaluation. The different product group criteria is revised on a regular basis to reflect on technical innovation, such as evolution of materials or production processes, emission reductions and changes in the market. This revision process reinforces the trust that consumers and professionals place in the EU Ecolabel to only include high quality goods and services that respect the latest environmental standards.
Assurance of quality	The EU Ecolabel is awarded by independent third-party organisations only to the best 10- 20% products on the market, in terms of environmental performance. The EU ecolabel also fulfils high standards with respect to the protection of human health while also having the same fitness for use and quality. The label also encourages companies to develop innovative products that are durable, easy to repair and recyclable.
Impact assessment	The Commission initiated its Regulatory Fitness and Performance Programme (REFIT) in 2012, where one of the resultant actions of the program is the Fitness Check which has the purpose to analyse the effectiveness, efficiency and the added value of European regulations, as well as, to evaluate and assess the contribution to competitiveness, sustainable consumption, and production. The Fitness Check mandate applies to the EU ecolabel voluntary scheme. With the fitness check, the Commission, together with the EU Ecolabelling Board, assesses whether the objectives of these regulations have been met and whether implementation has been done in a cost-effective way.
Risk management	Aspects of risk management are considered in the EU Ecolabel, and this should be implemented in compliance with precautionary principle Article 191 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union. The precautionary principle may be invoked when a phenomenon, product or process may have a dangerous effect, identified by a scientific and objective evaluation. The principle belongs in the general framework of risk analysis (which, besides risk evaluation, includes risk management and risk communication), and more particularly in the context of risk management which corresponds to the decision-making phase.
Cost of certification	The certification cost includes: 1) Application fee: no lower than EUR 200 and no higher than EUR 2000. Reductions may apply for some applications, 2) Annual fee: This can be a flat fee, or a fee based on the annual value of sales within the Union of the product awarded the EU Ecolabel, 3) Inspection fee: annual fee does not cover the cost of testing, verification and any on-site inspections that may be required. Applicants will cover the cost of such testing, verification and inspections themselves., 4) Extension and modification fee: fee for modification or extension of a licence and shall not be higher than the application fee. Updated information about the fees can be found at: https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy/eu-ecolabel-home/how-apply_en
Sustainability Principles and Criteria	
Reference Document	The EU Ecolabel is a component of the European Commission’s action plan on Sustainable Consumption and Production and Sustainable Industrial Policy. There is not a single document summarizing and describing the sustainability principles and criteria requirements for all product categories. The background information, environmental, quality criteria, chain of custody and reference for each product groups can be found in individual documents.
Major Must and Minor Must	n/a
Environmental	
General information	EU Ecolabel sets environmental requirements for each set product group related to: the impact on climate change, the impact on nature and biodiversity, energy and resource consumption, generation of waste, emissions to all environmental media, pollution through physical effects and use and the substitution of hazardous substances by safer substances, as such or via the use of alternative materials or designs, wherever

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	it is technically feasible. There is special focus on use of sustainable and renewable raw materials. To ensure that biological resources are sustainably sourced, EU Ecolabel accepts credible third-party standards and certification schemes e.g., FSC and PEFC for sustainable forestry in products which include fibre raw materials and some agricultural products e.g., palm (RSPO).
Reduce GHG emissions	The Ecolabel sets thresholds limiting the amount of GHG emissions during the production. This is especially linked to the criteria on energy consumed during the production processes (combustion emissions).
Protection of land with high carbon stock	The EU Ecolabel criteria aim to protect forests from deforestation by requiring that at least 70 % of fibre material allocated to the product is recycled or originates from forests managed according to sustainable forestry principles set out by an independent third-party certification scheme such as the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC). For agricultural products the sustainable production is checked through compliance with certification schemes such as a RSPO for palm oil.
Protection of peatland	EU Ecolabel criterion excludes the use in the product of intentionally added peat (for growing media and soil improvers). This restriction was set because peat extraction affects valuable habitats for wildlife and contributes to the emission of sequestered carbon into the atmosphere, accelerating climate change.
Promote sustainable forest management	EU Ecolabel requires that wood raw materials used in products must come from sustainably managed forests. For wooden products placed on the market bearing the Ecolabel, at least 70% of any solid wood and 40% wood-based materials must originate either from sustainably managed forests which have been certified by independent third-party schemes fulfilling the criteria listed in paragraph 15 of the Council Resolution of 15 December 1998 on a Forestry Strategy for the EU and further development thereof, or from recycled materials. Following certification system are acceptable. FSC Forest Stewardship Council, PEFC Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification schemes, SFI Sustainable Forestry Initiative, CSA Canada's National Standard for Sustainable Forest Management.
Protection of land with a high biodiversity value	The position of the European Commission regarding the protection of biodiversity has been focus on raw material extraction which should be covered by appropriate mitigation measures that aim at minimising biodiversity losses and guarantee appropriate recovery of the areas where extraction activities take place. Key changes are proposed after revising the EU Ecolabel criteria in 2022 and new principles set by the latest EU strategies were included, with reference to the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and Soil Strategy for 2030.
Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity	The EU Ecolabel is taken measures to protect and strength biodiversity according to the European Green Deal aims to preserve and restore ecosystems and biodiversity, the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 aims to protect and restore carbon-rich ecosystems and peatlands which are in agreement with the EU Soil Strategy for 2030 to promote the restoration of drained organic soils and EU Ecolabel criteria for growing media and soil improvers. For wood products it is required that measures must be in place to minimise potential impacts on the surrounding habitat and birds, and to limit the presence of invasive species.
Sustainable use of water	The EU Ecolabel sets requirements for sustainable water consumption. Manufacturing plants shall have systems for water-saving.
Maintaining and enhancing water quality	The EU Ecolabel demands that measures be taken to reduce the amount of unwanted chemicals end in water e.g., dishwasher detergents awarded with the EU Ecolabel should not contain substances adversely affecting marine life when discharged into a waterway and for textiles minimising effluent chemical oxygen demand (COD). Manufacturer applicants are also required to measure the emissions to water at the wastewater treatment plant.
Maintaining and enhancing soil quality and productivity	The European Commission has implemented policy tools such as the EU Soil Strategy for 2030 which promotes the restoration of drained organic soil and the future implementation of carbon farming in the EU, aimed at helping private actors and public authorities start up carbon farming initiatives. In the EU ecolabel the soil quality is addressed through voluntary sustainability certification schemes.
Soil quality consideration for use of residual flows	Within Fertilizer Product Regulation (FPR) the use of compost and digestate, as components of EU fertilising products, is promoted to recirculate organic matter and nutrients. This inclusion accommodates the principles of the Waste Framework Directive, stating that a waste ceases to be a waste if it undergoes recovery operations (including recycling) and meets specific criteria. From 16 July 2022, there will be a new consolidated version of the FPR, due to ongoing amendments, which were considered during the development of the revised EU Ecolabel criteria.
Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals	In May 2021, the European Commission has adopted the Zero Pollution Action Plan, as part of the European Green Deal, envisaging a toxic-free environment by 2050. The initiative aims to reduce air, water and soil pollution to levels no longer considered harmful to health and natural ecosystems, and that respect the boundaries our planet can cope with, thus creating a toxic-free environment. The EU Ecolabel is key to contributing to the Zero Pollution Action Plan's toxic-free environment objective. It is a transparent and reliable environmental label with a strong focus on toxic-free products, safe and sustainable by design. The EU Ecolabel may not be awarded if the product meet the criteria for classification with the hazard statements or risk phrases specified in table 4, in accordance with Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 or Council

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	Directive 67/548/EEC, nor they contain substances or mixtures referred to in Article 57 of Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH).
Implement best practices for the use of (agro)chemicals	The European Commission has adopted a proposal for a new Regulation on the Sustainable Use of Plant Protection Products, including EU wide targets to reduce by 50% the use and risk of chemical pesticides by 2030, in line with the EU's Biodiversity strategies. The proposal, adopted on June 2022, the main measures include: 1) Legally binding targets at EU level to reduce by 50% the use and the risk of chemical pesticides as well as the use of the more hazardous pesticides by 2030. 2) Environmentally friendly pest control: new measures will ensure that all farmers and other professional pesticide users practice Integrated Pest Management (IPM). EU Ecolabel have strict requirements for the use of pesticides in cultivation of e.g., cotton and promotes use of IPM.
Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality	The EU Ecolabel is a strong instrument to reduce contamination of air. The EU Ecolabel guarantees that certified paints and varnished contain reduced amounts of hazardous substances and volatile organic compounds (VOCs). Also, for paper mills limit on the sulphur, phosphorous and NOx emissions. Manufacturer applicants are required to measure the emissions to air.
Limit the risk of Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC)	-
Circularity	
General information	The EU Ecolabel promotes Europe's transition to a circular economy, supporting both sustainable production and consumption. The new Circular Economy Action Plan recognizes the valuable role of EU Ecolabel criteria to inspire mandatory legislation and prescribes the systematic inclusion of circular economy aspects in the EU Ecolabel criteria. The EU Ecolabel encourage producers, depending on the product group, to efficiently use raw materials, generate less waste and emission during the manufacturing process, use less hazardous chemicals and develop products that are durable, easy to repair and recyclable.
Promote waste reduction and responsible waste management	The EU Ecolabel strives to reduce waste. For some products there is criterion setting limits on the quantity of waste generated during the manufacture and packaging of the products. There is a requirement to have a waste management system in place for waste reduction, separation, reuse and recycling during the production.
Raw material efficiency	The implementation of material efficiency aspects has been progressively gaining importance in product policies, especially after the recast of the Ecodesign directive and EU Ecolabel regulation. For the EU Ecolabel, material efficiency criteria considered relate to reuse/recycling of process residues and waste.
Efficient use of energy	EU Ecolabel is a tool for reduced total energy consumption and less use of fossil fuels and promotes locally produced energy in products and services. In production systems the EU Ecolabel has limits to ensure energy efficiency (e.g., paper products and floor coverings).
Promote use of renewable sources	The EU Ecolabel promotes and stimulates the use of more sustainable and renewable resources and ingredients in different product criteria. Such as the requirement for lubricants that are manufactured from at least 50% renewable raw materials. Thereby EU Ecolabel promotes integration of bio-based products in the European economy. There is also restriction on the use of non-renewable energy sources and promotion of use of renewables.
Promote material circularity	The EU Ecolabel is referred to in the new Circular Economy Action Plan. The Action Plan foresees that the review of the Ecodesign Directive as well as further work on specific product groups, will build, among others and where appropriate, on criteria and rules established under the EU Ecolabel Regulation. The EU Ecolabel has in fact acted as a pioneer in promoting the circular economy, as the criteria are based on the main principles of the circular economy concept; for example, by promoting reuse of materials, setting strict chemical requirements that allow the materials to be recycled, and requirements on durability of products. The EU Ecolabel requires information to be provided for users about maintenance and disposal.
Social	
General information	The EU Ecolabel puts most emphasis on environmental aspects, but also include some social requirements.
Compliance with labour rights	The EU ecolabel promotes full and productive employment and decent work for all and guarantees social and ethical aspects. Applicants shall ensure that the fundamental principles and rights at work shall be observed by production sites by referring to related international conventions and agreements, such as relevant International Labour Organization (ILO) standards and codes of conduct. Companies that make products with the EU Ecolabel must always adhere to the relevant legislation. For industries that typically carry out production outside the EU, this also means that no child labour or forced labour, along with other social requirements.
Respect wellbeing of workers	EU Ecolabel favour substitution of hazardous substances with safer ones. This helps to prevent both users and factory workers from being exposed to harmful chemicals.

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Respect property and usage rights	This aspect is indirectly covered through recognition of voluntary sustainability certification schemes where this requirement is covered.
Respect wellbeing of the local population	This aspect is indirectly covered through recognition of voluntary sustainability certification schemes. Additionally, EU Ecolabel helps reducing the amount of hazardous substances and promoting healthy lives for all. This applies to substances that come into direct contact with humans as well as substances that pollute air, soil and water. For example, the EU Ecolabel sets requirements for personal care products, prohibiting among other things, substances classified as carcinogenic, mutagenic or allergenic as well as reproductive toxicants and substances listed by the EU as possible endocrine disruptors.
Food security	This aspect is indirectly covered through recognition of voluntary sustainability certification schemes.
Economic	
General information	The EU Ecolabel criteria focus mainly on environmental aspects, health aspects and some social aspect of concern in a few product groups. Economic aspects are outside scope. Relevant information found related to economic aspects are provided below.
Financial and economic viability	The EU Ecolabel is a tool for enhancing business competitiveness, promoting resource efficiency and helping to create new business models and innovative solutions. The EU Ecolabel enhances company's sustainable image, and can also lead to financial savings (e.g., reduced resource use and electricity consumption, improved waste management). Having products or services awarded with the EU Ecolabel ensures easier access to Green Public Procurement.
Fair business practices, Integrity	-
Promote local development, Inclusive economic growth	-
Use of knowledge and technology	-
Fair trade and market practices	-
Risk assessment and management	-

Date completed: 13 April 2023

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D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

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D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

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6.10 Factsheet Blue Angel

This factsheet aims to provide accessible and factual information on the Blue Angel. This factsheet presents the actual status of the ecolabel in April 2023. For more detailed information on the system, the reader may visit the website of the certification scheme or contact ecolabel owner.

Disclaimer: The information contained in this factsheet is for informational purpose only and cannot be used in replacement of the official Blue Angel standards and procedures

Table 18 Factsheet Blue Angel

Scheme Feature	Description
General	
Name of scheme	Blue Angel
Scheme owner	The German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection (BMUV) is the owner of the Blue Angel, and it carries a high level of responsibility when it comes to using the label for providing reliable product information. It promotes the Blue Angel to the public, companies and associations, as well as within the political arena. The Blue Angel has been the ecolabel of the German federal government for more than 40 years. It is awarded to environmentally friendly products and services.
Website	https://www.blauer-engel.de/en/
Label provided	
Operational since	1978
Number of active certificates	The Blue Angel has currently 95 product groups and has awarded more than 20,000 products and services from more than 1,600 companies.
Standard ownership	The Blue Angel is a private, independent and voluntary ecolabel.
General objective	The Blue Angel aims to provide private customers, large institutional consumers and public institutions with reliable guidance for environmentally conscious purchasing. The ecolabel aims to promote eco-friendly innovations by creating a specific demand for environmentally friendly products, and in turn help to minimise environmental pollution.
Scope	
Biomass feedstock coverage	A wide range of biomass is covered by the Blue Angel. The Blue Angel uses certification system for verification of feedstock sustainability such as certified recycled or forestry biomass (FSC, PEFC or equivalent rules sustainable management according to FAO), as well as for agricultural biomass and biological wastes. The label is provided and not on the raw materials.
Sector/Product group coverage	The ecolabel covers a wide spectrum of products and services. The Blue Angel certification is applicable to different products and services. There are 8 product categories: household/drugstore, living/textile, green IT/household appliance, construction products, heating/energy, paper/stationary, vehicles/ mobility and services/municipality. No fuels and energy generation is covered, only products related to these (e.g., energy meters, stoves for wood, car sharing services, catalytic converters for motor vehicles). For this project the 6 sectors are: plastics, construction, woodworking, textiles, paper and chemicals. Therefore, these categories of Blue Angel are most relevant: household/drugstore, living/textile, construction products, paper/stationery and services/municipality.
Supply chain coverage	The Blue Angel covers the whole supply chain. The environmental label takes a holistic view of the life cycle of the product – from its production and use through to its disposal and recycling.

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Geographic focus of the standard	The Blue Angel focuses on German government's environmental policy; however the ecolabel is used globally in international markets. The Blue Angel has now concluded "mutual recognition agreements". These agreements usually include close collaboration in the development of award criteria and mutual testing and certification of applications for the use of the labels. This helps companies to also use the ecolabel of the other country. Blue Angel has agreements with Austria, China, Japan and South Korea.
Governance, Standard Development and Certification Requirements	
Scheme governance	The German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection (BMUV) is the owner of the label. It defines the fundamental guidelines for the award of the Blue Angel and appoints the members of the Environmental Label Jury. The German Environment Agency (UBA) develops the Basic Award Criteria on a scientific basis that a product or service must comply with in order to be certified with the Blue Angel. UBA also regularly checks the criteria to ensure they conform to the latest technological standards. The Environmental Label Jury is an independent, impartial, and voluntary body that ensures the reliability of the Blue Angel and decides which new product groups are added and discusses and approves the Basic Award Criteria proposed by the UBA. An independent organisation, RAL gGmbH (a non-profit private limited company) checks compliance with the requirements after the submission of the product-specific application by a company and concludes contracts on the use of the Blue Angel with the companies.
Standard documents	Blue Angel provides for each product group the Basic Award Criteria and application documents to help through the application process. They can be downloaded from the website: https://www.blauer-engel.de/en/products , where the list of labelled products is also available. The Blue Angel provides additional guidelines e.g., regarding use of logo are also available at: https://www.blauer-engel.de/sites/default/files/2021-11/Logo-Guidelines-Blue-Angel-Edition-November-2021.pdf .
Transparency and accessibility of standard documents	The Blue Angel sets the requirements that all certified products must comply with. The Blue Angel is transparent and publishes all of the Basic Award Criteria (in German and English), as well as information on the background to the different labels, companies, certified products and updates to each product group.
Multi-stakeholder participation in standard development	The Blue Angel has a multistakeholder participation. The German Environment Agency (UBA) develops requirements (so-called Basic Award Criteria) for each specific product group based on scientific publications. The experts at the UBA are responsible for any updates that are required due to changes in technological standards and for periodic reviews of the criteria, sometimes in cooperation with other independent scientific institutions and experts. Interested stakeholders, such as companies, scientists and NGOs from the relevant product sector, are also involved in the development of the Basic Award Criteria and dialogue is maintained with them. The Environmental Label Jury is the decision-making body and is comprised by a multistakeholder with 15 representatives from environmental and consumer associations, trade unions, industry, the trade, crafts, local authorities, academia, the media, churches, young people and the German federal states.
Compliance with ISEAL's Standards-Setting, Impacts and Assurance Codes of Good Practice	The Blue Angel is an ISO 14024 (2018) Type 1 Ecolabel and conforms to the requirements of this international standard along with the more general ISO 14020 (2022). The Blue Angel does not refer to ISEAL codes. However, certification schemes that the Blue Angel accepts as documentation for responsibly sourced raw materials, must comply with ISEAL codes.
Compliance with regional, national, international laws	Compliance with the relevant German and European legislation and international laws is written in the Basic Award Criteria.
Reference to standards and policies	The Blue Angel is an ISO 14024 Type 1 ecolabel and a member of the Global Ecolabelling Network. In the Basic Award Criteria per product category reference to the relevant standards and legislation are provided. Standards at national, European and International level (DIN, EN, ISO standard) are referenced.
Obligation for certification	The Blue Angel is awarded to a company that offers or produces its products or services in a particularly environmentally friendly way and fulfils the established product criteria. The Blue Angel may only be used for the end product that has been awarded the label.
Certification process	The Blue Angel application process is as follows: 1. Find Basic Award Criteria for your product or service. 2. Download the documentation for application. 3. Submit the documentation to the online application portal exclusively. Following application RAL checks the application for the use of the environmental label for compliance with the stipulated requirements and concludes contract on the use of the environmental label with the supplier/manufacturer.
Traceability and Chain of custody	The manufacturer of the Blue Angel ecolabelled product must show that raw material suppliers are certified and provide information about traceability system. The applicable chain of custody system is provided per product group, e.g., mass Balance, is accepted as traceability systems for palm oil palm kernel oil and their derivatives, but other product groups also use identity preserved and segregation models. The supplier of wood raw materials must have a valid Chain of Custody (CoC) certification under the FSC / PEFC schemes.

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Verification of compliance	The Blue Angel is a Type 1 Ecolabel and requires independent third-party certification which is carried out by RAL gGmbH as an independent certification body.
Accreditation of Certification Bodies	The RAL gGmbH as an independent certification body, checks compliance with the requirements after the submission of the product-specific application by a company and concludes contracts on the use of the Blue Angel with the companies. The Blue Angel is a TYPE I environmental label, based on ISO 17065 and the DIN ISO 14024 international standard, a its independent product testing and transparent processes for the development and award of the label. The general list of accredited testing institutions in Germany can be found at e.g. www.dakks.de/content/datenbank-akkreditierter-stellen and the overview of the European accreditation members at: www.european-accreditation.org/ea-members .
Training of auditors and staff and qualification and evaluation of competencies	Not explicitly provided in public documents.
Audit process	RAL gGmbH inspects the completeness and accuracy of the documents provided as evidence of compliance with the relevant criteria and requirement. If the product satisfies the relevant requirements, the parties enter into an agreement on the use of the Blue Angel.
Frequency of audit	Use of the Blue Angel ecolabel is limited to the period of validity of the Basic Award Criteria which are reviewed and prolonged with or without revision every 2 to 4 years. In case of revision re-certification and a new auditing is required. The company needs to submit a new application based on the amended criteria. Specific information is provided on license validity in each product group criteria document. The company receives notification about the termination of the existing contract and information on the new criteria.
Internal audit	No requirement on self-assessment or internal audit provided in public documents.
Certification claims and labels	The Blue Angel Guidelines are designed to be used by all label holders and label users whose products comply with the requirements of the Basic Award Criteria. Label holders and label users of the Blue Angel certification are permitted to use the logo on the relevant product for their advertising and communication measures after concluding a contract on the use of the environmental label with RAL gGmbH.
Sanctions, non-conformities and suspension	The RAL gGmbH does not conclude the contract on the Use of the Environmental label before consulting the respective State Ministry for the Environment and before reviewing the submitted documents for correctness and completeness and the results of the testing laboratories. In the event of misuse of the Blue Angel a warning letter will be sent to the label user and in the event of breach of the Basic Award Criteria the eco-label can be withdrawn.
Complaint and appeal mechanisms	The complaint and appeal mechanism of the Blue Angel is not explicitly described in public documents. However, there is feedback channel online to reach the Blue Angel. https://www.blauer-engel.de/en/blue-angel/feedback
Guarantee smallholder inclusiveness of the standard	Not explicitly provided in public documents.
Promote continuous improvement	The Blue Angel is a Type 1 Ecolabel according to the standard ISO 14024 which requires a development through continuous improvements and regular evaluation, review of the requirements and tightens the requirements based on the latest environmental knowledge and market developments. As a member of GEN, the scheme is evaluated against ISO 14024 regularly within every five-six years in the GENICES process by colleagues under the auspices of the GEN board.
Assurance of quality	Aspect of quality management is considered in the requirements for product properties that ensure quality The Blue Angel guarantees that a product places less burden on the environment and fulfils high standards with respect to the protection of human health while also having the same fitness for use and quality as other products. Longevity, ability to repair and recyclability are also considered for the product quality.
Impact assessment	The Blue Angel guarantees that a product does less damage to the environment based on scientific investigations, its own studies, and market research, the German Environment Agency (UBA) creates requirements specific to product groups ("award criteria") as a prerequisite for being certified with the ecolabel. The aim is to identify the key environmentally relevant areas for each group of products in which considerable impacts on the environment can be reduced or even avoided.
Risk management	Aspect of risk management is considered indirectly in the Blue Angel by using the international agreements as a reference for internal purposes and also in the sense of precautionary risk management. Overall, the Blue Angel eco-label's risk management approach is focused on preventing harm to the environment and human health by addressing potential hazards at every stage of a product's lifecycle.
Cost of certification	The certification cost includes a one-off fee of 400 EUR (plus the statutory level of VAT) for processing the application, plus an annual fee which depends on the total annual turnover of the products (goods and services). The annual fee varies between 320 EUR-10,500 EUR depending on the total annual turnover of the products per Basic Criteria for the Award of the Environmental Label. If no annual turnover is generated the

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

	applicant shall pay at least the lowest annual fee category). A processing fee of €200 (plus the statutory level of VAT) must be paid to RAL gGmbH by the applicant for the conclusion of each contract extension. More detailed and updated fee information can be reviewed at: https://www.blauer-engel.de/en/certification/costs-applying-label
Sustainability Principles and Criteria	
Reference Document	There is not a single document summarizing and describing the sustainability principles and criteria requirements for all products or product categories. However, the Blue Angel considers in the award criteria the following aspects: resource-saving production, sustainable production of resources, avoidance of harmful substances in the product, reduced emissions of harmful substances in the ground, air, water and indoors, reduced noise and electromagnetic radiation, efficient use, energy or water, longevity, ability to repair and recycle the product, compliance with international occupational safety standards, take-back systems and shared-use services, e.g. car sharing. General information on the guiding environmental principle can be found at: https://www.blauer-engel.de/en/publications/detail/brief-information-guiding-principles-behind-blue-angel-environmental-label-0
Major Must and Minor Must	n/a
Environmental	
General information	The Blue Angel sets environmental requirements for each product group taking a holistic view of the life cycle of the product – from its production and use through to its disposal and recycling. Relevant information found related to these environmental aspects are provided below. This includes criteria on low energy consumption, low emissions to water, air and soil and the preservation of resources. It also takes into account aspects, such as low levels of pollutants and restriction on hazardous materials. There is specific consideration on the use of sustainable and renewable raw materials in some product categories. To ensure that biological raw materials are sustainably sourced, the Blue Angel assesses and accepts credible third-party standards and certification schemes e.g., FSC and PEFC for sustainable forestry in products which include fibre raw materials. For agricultural products the following certification systems are considered suitable to verify sustainable cultivation: RSPO (Roundtable on Sustainable Palmoil), ISCC (International Sustainable & Carbon Certification), RSB (Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterial), Roundtable Responsible Soy (RTRS) und ProTerra (ProTerra Foundation) or a comparable certification system whose scope and requirement standards are equivalent to one of the named certification systems. If not explicitly included in Blue Angel criteria, the criteria below may be covered indirectly through recognition of these sustainability certification schemes. Additionally, In the project "Implementation of sustainability criteria for the material use of biomass in the context of the Blue Angel" concrete sustainability requirements for individual bio-based products will be developed where three product groups are considered: biobased plastics (as material grade), biobased lubricating oils and hydraulic fluids (as final product) and biobased detergents and cleaners (as final product).
Reduce GHG emissions	The Blue Angel focuses on preventing and reducing and as far as possible eliminate pollution to air arising from industrial activities. The Blue Angel requests for some products related to construction materials a product-specific environmental product declaration (EPD) pursuant to DIN EN 15804 which includes parameter for GHG emission reporting as Global warming potential (GWP).
Protection of land with high carbon stock	Indirectly covered by setting restrictions on the use of certain raw materials that are not produced or sourced in a sustainable way and by accepting certification for sustainable forest and agricultural feedstocks that are listed above.
Protection of peatland	Indirectly covered through accepting recognized sustainability certification standards such as ISCC, RSB where this criterion is covered.
Promote sustainable forest management	The Blue Angel requires that wood raw materials used in Blue Angel ecolabelled products must come from legal sources. Moreover, at least 50 percent of the total amount of wood used for wood-based materials shall be sourced from sustainable forests. Compliance with the requirement for using wood from sustainable forestry can be verified according to the FSC or PEFC certification. For some product groups 100 percent certification is required e.g., nappies, thermal paper.
Protection of land with a high biodiversity value	The Blue Angel indirectly promotes conservation of biodiversity and sustainable use of natural resources. The Blue Angel eco-label has specific criteria to protect biodiversity in various product categories such as paper, cleaning products, and textiles, among others. These criteria aim to promote the sustainable use of natural resources, reduce negative impacts on biodiversity, and support the conservation of species and ecosystems. For this, the Blue Angel uses recognized sustainable certification schemes to prevent the increased risk of deforestation and which are associated with a serious loss of biodiversity and losses to ecosystem services. Materials sourced from animal, plant or wood species listed either in CITES23 in Annexes I, II or III24 or which originate from a region included on the IUCN Red List25 and are classified in the categories "critically endangered", "endangered" or "vulnerable" are excluded from the scope of these Basic Award Criteria
Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity	The Blue Angel has taken measures to protect and strength biodiversity, for example: genetically modified organisms (GMOs) in certain agricultural products like cotton production and the use of recycle paper.

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Sustainable use of water	For selected product groups the ecolabel sets requirements for sustainable water consumption and demands that measures be taken to reduce the amount of unwanted chemicals in water. An important area covered by the Blue Angel is resource-conserving and the efficient use of water. The Ecolabel has strict requirements for the use of pesticides in cultivation of cotton and other raw materials. Other requirements limit the use of unwanted dyes and other chemical substances in the manufacturing of, for example, textiles and paper.
Maintaining and enhancing water quality	The Blue Angel takes measurements to reduce the amount of unwanted chemicals to water bodies and sets requirements for treatment of wastewater. The Ecolabel has strict requirements for the use of pesticides in cultivation of cotton and other raw materials. Other requirements limit the use of unwanted dyes and other chemical substances in the manufacturing of, for example, textiles and paper. For some product groups related to construction materials it is also required to report Eutrophication potential (EP), according to EN 15804.
Maintaining and enhancing soil quality and productivity	The Blue Angel eco-label maintains and enhances soil quality and productivity by considering soil management practices, organic production, reduced use of hazardous substances to the soil, life cycle assessment. This approach ensures that the products certified do not have significant negative impacts on soil quality and productivity, such as erosion, soil contamination, or the depletion of natural resources.
Soil quality consideration for use of residual flows	Indirectly covered through accepting recognized sustainability certification standards such as ISCC, RSB where this criterion is covered.
Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals	Compliance with the German and European chemicals legislation as well as with the industry-related regulations is considered a matter of course for Blue Angel ecolabelled products (this includes above all REACH Regulation, Annex XVII, Persistent Organic Pollutant Regulation (POP) Annex I, CLP Regulation, ChemVerbotsV (Chemicals Prohibition Ordinance), Decopaint Directive, GefStoffV (Ordinance on Hazardous Substances), VDL-RL 01, Council Directive 92/112/EEC, 25. BImSchV (25th Federal Immission Protection Ordinance), Biocidal Products Regulation (BPR), VerpackG (German Packaging Act), etc. The ecolabel helps reducing the amount of hazardous substances in the products and that pollute air, soil, water and indoor spaces e.g., the use of chlorine, halogenated bleaching agents and not readily biodegradable complexing agents is also prohibited during the production process of recycled paper.
Implement best practices for the use of (agro)chemicals	Indirectly covered through accepting recognized sustainability certification standards such as ISCC, RSB where this criterion is covered.
Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality	The Blue Angel has explicit requirement for indoor air quality limiting the emission volatile organic substances as well as other type of sulfur, nitrogen oxide and dust emissions that may arise from processing.
Limit the risk of Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC)	Indirectly covered through accepting recognized sustainability certification standards such as RSB which also has an add-on to address ILUC.
Circularity	
General information	The Blue Angel promotes circular economy by promoting durability, reparability and recyclability in products. Requirements exist for efficient use of products and use of low level of energy or water.
Promote waste reduction and responsible waste management	Waste reduction and waste management is an explicit criterion covered by some product groups, otherwise also covered by accepting recognized sustainability certification schemes. The Blue Angel strives to reduce waste, also by promoting reuse and recyclability of materials e.g., paper and plastic.
Raw material efficiency	The Blue Angel emphasizes resource efficiency both for products and services and strive to make producers shift towards more renewable resources and sustainable types of technology.
Efficient use of energy	The Blue Angel promotes the efficient energy use and promotes less use of fossil fuels. For some product groups limits are set in the energy consumption in the production process
Promote use of renewable sources	The Blue Angel promotes and stimulates the use of renewable resources in different product criteria (e.g., lubricant, surfactant, plastics used in nappies, colorants used in paper products). In some product group criteria (e.g., thermal and sanitary paper) it is explicitly required that the consumed electricity should be sourced from renewable energies.
Promote material circularity	The requirements placed on the products themselves and their packages and containers are designed to promote the use of post-consumer recycled materials and thus support the goal of a circular economy. Also, criteria exist on the fitness for use, durability and not allowing hazardous substances that may well impede recycling. The Blue Angel follows the perspective reflected in the environmental policy targets at EU level within the scope of the EU Commission circular economy activities. The Blue Angel is part of the Circular Economy Labels and Information Schemes (CELIS) which is composed by the group of labels, certifications, standards of information schemes that fully or partially address one or more resource efficiency or circular economy elements.

Social

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

General information	The Blue Angel is at its core an environmental label, but it increasingly focuses on other aspects such as working conditions during the production process. The Blue Angel criteria for some product groups also include some social requirements such as textiles and leather. For textiles the social and human rights requirements for the recognition of certification labels are according to the Green Button 2.0 and for leather, the applicant undertakes to comply with the Code of Conduct for the Leather Industry. Relevant information found related to these social aspects are provided below. Social criteria are still rare in the Blue Angel, especially when it comes to social aspects during raw material extraction. However, the German Federal Environment Agency (UBA) commissioned the project "Extended integration of social aspects in the Blue Angel eco-label" to analyse the expectations and interests of consumers and enterprises regarding the integration of social criteria.
Compliance with labour rights	Basic Award Criteria updates for some product groups also includes social aspects related to manufacturing conditions e.g., observance of the International Labour Organization (ILO) core conventions. That means, for example, that there is no child labour, no forced labour, no discrimination, and there is freedom of association and fair salary.
Respect wellbeing of workers	This aspect is indirectly covered through recognition of voluntary sustainability certification schemes. Additionally, the Blue Angel has requirements set for substances that are hazardous to health and the environment in products and manufacturing. This helps to prevent both users and factory workers from being exposed to harmful chemicals. The Blue Angel also has for some product groups requirement on the reduction in noise and electromagnetic radiation during the production.
Respect property and usage rights	This aspect is indirectly covered through recognition of voluntary sustainability certification schemes where this requirement is covered.
Respect wellbeing of the local population	This aspect is indirectly covered through recognition of voluntary sustainability certification schemes. Additionally, the Blue Angel lends itself for the labelling of products that are low-emission and thus non-hazardous to health.
Food security	This aspect is indirectly covered through recognition of voluntary sustainability certification schemes.
Economic	
General information	The Blue Angel criteria focuses mainly on environmental aspects, health aspects and some social aspect of concern in a few product groups. Economic aspects are outside scope. Relevant information found related to economic aspects are provided below.
Financial and economic viability	The Blue Angel is reacting to new challenges and helping shape the change in the economy towards a more sustainable growth by providing market benefits to products and services that are environmentally sustainable. Also related to use of wood it is required that it is sourced from sustainable forests which are managed in a verifiably economically viable, environmentally sound and socially responsible way.
Fair business practices, Integrity	-
Promote local development, Inclusive economic growth	-
Use of knowledge and technology	-
Fair trade and market practices	-
Risk assessment and management	-

Date completed: 13 April 2023

Sources:

- Blue Angel products and services <https://www.blauer-engel.de/en/products> (Last visited: April 2023)
- General information and objective. <https://www.blauer-engel.de/en/blue-angel/our-label-environment> (Last visited: April 2023)
- Cooperation partners <https://www.blauer-engel.de/en/blue-angel/our-label-environment/cooperation-partners> (Last visited: April 2023)
- Blue Angel Actors and Structure. <https://www.blauer-engel.de/en/blue-angel/actors> (Last visited: April 2023)
- Blue Angel Logo <https://www.blauer-engel.de/en/certification/certification-your-products/use-of-the-logo> (Last visited: April 2023)
- Developed on a scientific basis. <https://www.blauer-engel.de/en/blue-angel/our-label-environment/developed-scientific-basis> (Last visited: April 2023)
- Application process <https://www.blauer-engel.de/en/certification/certification-your-product/application-process> (Last visited: April 2023)

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

- Guiding principles behind Blue Angel environmental label. <https://www.blauer-engel.de/en/publications/detail/brief-information-guiding-principles-behind-blue-angel-environmental-label-0> (Last visited: April 2023)
- Frequent questions for companies <https://www.blauer-engel.de/en/certification/certification-your-product/faqs-companies>. (Last visited: April 2023)
- OECD Environment Working Paper No. 183. Labelling and Information Schemes for the Circular Economy (2021). [https://one.oecd.org/document/ENV/WKP\(2021\)15/En/pdf](https://one.oecd.org/document/ENV/WKP(2021)15/En/pdf) . (Last visited: April 2023)
- Rubik F, et al., Integration of social aspects in the German Blue Angel scheme – Views from manufacturers and consumers, Sustainable Production and Consumption, Volume 33, 2022, ISSN 2352-5509, (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2022.07.018>)
- Blue Angel criteria for Low-emission material Panel Shaped Materials (Construction and Furnishing Panels for Interior Construction) DE-UZ 76. Version 10, February 2016.
- Blue Angel Hand Dishwashing Detergents, All-Purpose Cleaners, Sanitary Cleaners and Glass Cleaners product criteria DE-UZ 194. Version 1, Edition January 2015.
- Blue Angel criteria for Textiles DE-UZ 154. Version 1, January 2023.
- Blue Angel criteria for products made from recycled Plastics DE-UZ 30. Version 8, Edition January 2019
- Blue Angel criteria for Graphic paper and cardboard made from 100% recovered paper DE-UZ 14a. Version 5, January 2020
- Blue Angel criteria for Low-emission and low-pollutant paints and varnishes DE-UZ 12a. Version 8, January 2019
- Blue Angel criteria for Laundry detergent DE-UZ 202. Version 1, Edition January 2022.
- Blue Angel criteria for Sanitary paper DE-UZ 5. Version 1, Edition January 2022.
- Blue Angel criteria for Biodegradable Lubricants and Hydraulic Fluids DE-UZ 178. Version 2, Edition January 2022.
- Blue Angel criteria for Nappies, feminine hygiene and incontinence products (absorbent hygiene products, AHP) DE-UZ 208. Version 3, Edition January 2021.
- Blue Angel criteria for Low-emission Flooring Adhesives and other Installation Materials DE-UZ 113. Version 7, Edition January 2019.
- Blue Angel criteria for Thermal Paper DE-UZ 223. Version 2, Edition January 2022.
- Blue Angel criteria for Flushing Water Additives Compatible with Wastewater Treatment Plants. DE-UZ 84b, Version 2, March 2013

6.11 Factsheet Nordic Swan Ecolabel

This factsheet aims to provide accessible and factual information on the Nordic Swan Ecolabel. This factsheet presents the actual status of the ecolabel in April 2023. For more detailed information on the system, the reader may visit the website of the certification scheme or contact Nordic Ecolabelling.

Disclaimer: The information contained in this factsheet is for informational purpose only and cannot be used in replacement of the official Nordic Swan Ecolabel standards and procedures

Table 19 Factsheet Nordic Swan Ecolabel

Scheme Feature	Description
General	
Name of scheme	Nordic Swan Ecolabel
Scheme owner	The Nordic Council of Ministers which is the official body for inter-governmental co-operation in the Nordic Region. The label is administered and managed by Nordic Ecolabelling, a joint organisation. Nordic Ecolabelling consists of five local organisations / companies in Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway and Sweden appointed by the respective governments. They work tightly in fulfilling the goals of the Nordic Council of Ministers.
Website	https://www.nordic-swan-ecolabel.org/
Label provided	
Operational since	1989
Number of active certificates	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel has 56 different product groups and more than 200 different product types. Around 25,000 different products are sold with the Nordic Swan ecolabel.
Standard ownership	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel is a voluntary ecolabelling scheme primarily for the markets in Nordic countries.
General objective	Nordic Ecolabelling works to reduce the environmental impact from production and consumption of goods. The Nordic Swan Ecolabel is an effective tool to help companies that want to go ahead with sustainable solutions – and thereby enable consumers and professional buyers to choose the environmentally best goods and services.
Scope	
Biomass feedstock coverage	A wide range of biomass is covered by the Nordic Swan Ecolabel. There are restrictions on the use of certain raw materials that are not produced or sourced in a sustainable way. The label is provided on the products not on the raw materials
Sector/Product group coverage	The ecolabel covers a wide spectrum of products and services. 56 different product areas are covered, including: textiles, personal care products (cosmetics, sanitary products etc.), construction/building materials, chemicals (cleaning products, chemical building products, paint and varnishes), wood products, paper, plastic products etc. which are relevant for the industrial biobased systems.
Supply chain coverage	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel covers the whole supply chain. There is also a Supply Chain Declaration portal which is used by suppliers and secondary manufacturers helping their customers to obtain the Nordic Swan Ecolabel by declaring the properties of their items, i.e., chemicals, raw materials, goods, products, services and processes specified in the product group criteria.
Geographic focus of the standard	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel was set up as an official label for the countries in the Region (Norway, Sweden, Denmark, Finland, and Iceland). However, this ecolabel has an international recognition and preference and when a product is licensed, the ecolabel's validity is not subject to geographical limitations, and production site audits are performed worldwide.
Governance, Standard Development and Certification Requirements	

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Scheme governance	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel is governed by decisions of the Nordic Council of Ministers (NCM). The NCM determines the overall rules for the scheme and the fundamental rules of procedure for the Nordic Ecolabelling Board. The certification criteria for each product group are approved by the Nordic Ecolabelling Board, which also decides validity time and sets the rules for the companies that apply for or have a licence for the Nordic Swan Ecolabel. The board is independent and represents national boards consisting of organisations representing trade, industry, environmental and consumer interests. Nordic Ecolabelling is a non-profit organisation, independent from specific industry interests. Additionally, each country (Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway and Sweden) has its own National ecolabelling bodies (secretariats) mandated by the national authorities to manage the schemes on a national level. Each secretariat handles licence applications, inspection visits and marketing in their respective countries.
Standard documents	Nordic Swan Ecolabel provides for each product area/group the criteria documents needed, an application guide to help through the application process and information about fees. Information on the regulations that apply to the companies that apply for or hold a license to use Nordic Swan Ecolabel can be found in the document 'Regulations for the Nordic Ecolabelling of Products'. Additional guidelines e.g., regarding use of logo are also available.
Transparency and accessibility of standard documents	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel sets absolute requirements that all certified products must comply with. At the same time, the requirements are 100% transparent and are publicly and freely accessible.
Multi-stakeholder participation in standard development	Nordic Swan Ecolabel has a multistakeholder participation. The criteria-development work is done at Nordic level by the national ecolabelling organisations, however external experts can be used as required. Stakeholders from affected industries, official agencies, civil society and other relevant parties must be provided with opportunities to participate in the criteria-development process. All proposals for criteria remain open for consultation for 60 days, so that all stakeholders can submit written comments. Information is publicly available about the criteria adopted, proposals submitted, and responses received, as well as the status of the ongoing process.
Compliance with ISEAL's Standards-Setting, Impacts and Assurance Codes of Good Practice	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel is an ISO 14024 (2018) Type 1 Ecolabel and conforms to the requirements of this international standard along with the more general ISO 14020 (2022). The Nordic Swan Ecolabel does not refer to ISEAL codes. However, certification schemes that the Nordic Swan Ecolabel accepts as documentation for responsibly sourced raw materials, must comply with ISEAL codes.
Compliance with regional, national, international laws	The stringency of the Nordic Swan Ecolabel requirements is related to the Nordic countries' official environmental regulations based on EU legislation and all the product group criteria require compliance with national laws and regulations including for the manufacturing sites. National regulations in the Nordic countries can be found on the website of the local ecolabelling organisations.
Reference to standards and policies	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel is an ISO 14024 Type 1 ecolabel. The Nordic Swan Ecolabel is one of the founders of the international network for ISO 14024 Type 1 ecolabels, the Global Ecolabelling Network. Depending on the product criteria other standards (ISO and European standards) for testing, quality and alike may apply. This information can be found in the product criteria documents.
Obligation for certification	As a main rule, it is the manufacturer of a product or service who can apply for a Nordic Swan Ecolabel licence. Other companies, such as, importers, dealers, distributors or similar can also apply for the licence for a product, provided that said company is responsible for the sale on the Nordic market and that the manufacturer signs the application.
Certification process	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel application process has the following steps: 1) Start by locating your set of criteria, 2) Learn about the application process, 3) Find out what it will cost, 4) Read the regulations and study the marketing and graphical guidelines carefully, 5) Fill in the Power of Attorney form to get your login credentials, 6) Enter the Nordic Ecolabelling Portal and start your application, 7) Before the application is approved, Nordic Ecolabelling performs an inspection visit at the production site.
Traceability and Chain of custody	The manufacturer of the Nordic Swan Ecolabelled product must show that by raw material suppliers are certified and provide information about traceability system. The applicable chain of custody system is provided per product group, e.g., Mass Balance, Segregated or Identity Preserved are accepted as traceability systems for palm oil palm kernel oil and their derivatives; Mass Balance is used for sugar cane, biobased plastics and cardboard packing. The supplier of wood raw materials must have a valid Chain of Custody (CoC) certification under the FSC / PEFC schemes.
Verification of compliance	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel is a Type 1 Ecolabel and requires independent third-party certification.
Accreditation of Certification Bodies	The national ecolabelling organisations are responsible for the licensing of individual products using set criteria, in accordance with the requirement for certification stipulated by international standard ISO 17065.
Training of auditors and staff and qualification and evaluation of competencies	Not explicitly provided in public documents (but described in written internal quality routines).

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Audit process	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel has three different types of inspections. 1) On-site application inspection, 2) Annual inspection and 3) Follow-up inspection. More information can be found in the document 'Regulations for the Nordic Ecolabelling of Products'.
Frequency of audit	The licensee is obliged to prepare and submit annual reports to the Nordic Ecolabeling organizations as indicated in the criteria for the relevant product group. Follow-up inspections may be required to ensure that the licensed product fulfil the specific requirements. Such inspection may be made to the licensee, manufacturer, supplier, importer, wholesaler, or retailer without prior notice. The ecolabel licence is valid provided that the criteria are fulfilled and until the criteria expire. The validity period of the criteria may be extended or adjusted, in which case the licence is automatically extended, and the licensee informed. Specific information is provided on license validity in each product group criteria document.
Internal audit	No requirement on self-assessment or internal audit provided in the document 'Regulations for the Nordic Ecolabelling of Products'.
Certification claims and labels	Nordic Ecolabelling's "Nordic Swan Ecolabel" logo is a registered trademark, protected nationally and internationally through the World Intellectual Property Organisation (WIPO). The rules for use of the label are set out in "Regulations for the Nordic Ecolabelling of Products" in section Regulations governing the use of the Nordic Ecolabel. Additional guidance is provided in the document "Guidelines for using the Nordic Swan Ecolabel".
Sanctions, non-conformities and suspension	The licensee is obliged to prepare and submit annual reports to the Nordic Ecolabeling organizations as indicated in the criteria for the relevant product group. Follow-up inspections may be required to ensure that the licensed product fulfil the specific requirements. Such inspection may be made to the licensee, manufacturer, supplier, importer, wholesaler, or retailer without prior notice. The ecolabel licence is valid provided that the criteria are fulfilled and until the criteria expire. The validity period of the criteria may be extended or adjusted, in which case the licence is automatically extended, and the licensee informed. Specific information is provided on license validity in each product group criteria document.
Complaint and appeal mechanisms	Appeals against the rejection of an application or the revocation of a license/registration may be addressed to the Nordic Ecolabelling organization that made the decision. The procedures for appeals and complaints are documented in "Regulations for the Nordic Ecolabel of product".
Guarantee smallholder inclusiveness of the standard	Not explicitly provided in public documents. In the public consultation of draft criteria, anyone can provide comments for consideration.
Promote continuous improvement	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel is a Type 1 Ecolabel according to the standard ISO 14024 which requires a development through continuous improvements and regular evaluation, review of the requirements and tightening of the requirements based on the latest environmental knowledge and market developments. When the requirements are revised, all ecolabelled products are reassessed as companies must re-certify and document that their products comply with the new requirements. A new inspection of production sites is also performed by Nordic Ecolabelling. As a member of GEN, the scheme is evaluated against ISO 14024 regularly within every five-six years in the GENICES process by colleagues under the auspices of the GEN board.
Assurance of quality	Aspect of quality management is considered in the requirements for product properties that ensure quality and durability.
Impact assessment	Nordic Ecolabelling has developed a tool called RPS to set strong requirements and achieve environmental change. For each criteria group, this tool is used for setting the requirements with the greatest positive environmental impact throughout the life cycle. To set a requirement all three of these parameters, R (relevance), P (potential) and S (steerability) must be considered and found to be high. The environmental problem must be relevant for the product type, there must be a potential in the market to reduce the problem and the Nordic Swan Ecolabel must be able to contribute to a positive change by verifying a positive environmental change. The Nordic Ecolabelling Board (NMN) publishes the 'Nordic Ecolabelling Annual Report'. In these documents, information about the Nordic Swan Ecolabel's strategy, the valid criteria and criteria development, the marketing and communications strategies is presented.
Risk management	Aspect of risk management is considered in the Precautionary Principle used where Nordic Ecolabelling wants to exclude or limit certain substances that are suspected of having undesirable properties, even though these are neither hazardously classified nor on an authority-regulated list.
Cost of certification	The certification cost includes: 1) Application fee: 3,114 euros + VAT and can normally cover several products manufactured at the same production site. The application fee covers the time the national ecolabelling organisation spends processing your application including one inspection visit to a production site in the Nordic region. 2) Annual license fee: based on your annual revenue from your Nordic Swan Ecolabel goods and/or services, fees for extension /alteration to the licence (minimum 2,076 euros + VAT). More detailed and updated fee information can be reviewed at: https://www.nordic-swan-ecolabel.org/how-to-apply/costs/ .

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Reference Document	There is not a single document summarizing and describing the sustainability principles and criteria requirements for all products or product categories. However, the background information, environmental and quality criteria, chain of custody and references of each of the 56 different product groups can be found in individual documents per product area. General information on environmental aspects is provided on the Nordic Ecolabelling website https://www.nordic-swan-ecolabel.org/nordic-ecolabelling/environmental-aspects/ .
Major Must and Minor Must	n/a
Environmental	
General information	Nordic Ecolabelling sets ambitious and absolute environmental requirements that are unique for each set of criteria published. The environmental impact through a product's life cycle is assessed from a holistic perspective. There is special focus on climate, circular economy, chemicals and biodiversity in combination with a focus on health and quality. Relevant information found related to these environmental aspects are provided below. To ensure that biobased raw materials are sustainably sourced, Nordic Ecolabelling assesses and accepts credible third-party standards and certification schemes e.g., FSC and PEFC for sustainable forestry in products which include fibre raw materials and some agricultural products via the certification of palm (RSPO), soy (RTRS) and sugarcane (Bonsucro). If not explicitly included in Nordic Ecolabelling criteria, the criteria below may be covered indirectly through recognition of these sustainability certification schemes.
Reduce GHG emissions	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel may require greenhouse gas calculations to help companies to identify hotspots or show fulfilment of a requirement for limited climate impact. Greenhouse gas emissions calculations are required in some of the product group's criteria, the calculation must as a minimum be made according to the GHG Protocol methodology, but other specific standards can be required for specific product groups.
Protection of land with high carbon stock	Indirectly covered by setting restrictions on the use of certain raw materials that are not produced or sourced in a sustainable way and by accepting certification such as: FSC and PEFC for forestry standards, or other standards that can be accepted in certain product groups are standards for palm (RSPO), soy (RTRS) and sugar cane (Bonsucro). The Nordic Swan Ecolabel supports the conservation of natural areas that counteract climate change by requiring that a high proportion of virgin wood in for example buildings and furniture be sourced from certified forestry, where protecting nature is important.
Protection of peatland	Indirectly covered through accepting recognized sustainability certification standards such as palm oil (RSPO), soy (RTRS) and sugar cane (Bonsucro) where this criterion is covered.
Promote sustainable forest management	Nordic Ecolabelling requires that wood raw materials used in Nordic Swan Ecolabelled products must come from sustainably managed forests. A minimum of 70% by weight of all wood raw material must originate from forest managed according to sustainable forestry management principles that meet the requirements set out by FSC or PEFC chain of custody schemes and/or originate from recycled material. Remaining wood raw material must be either controlled wood (FSC) or come from controlled sources (PEFC). Certification systems protect forests from illegal logging and fulfil a number of different environmental criteria.
Protection of land with a high biodiversity value	The Nordic Ecolabelling promotes conservation of biodiversity and sustainable use of natural resources. For this, the Nordic Swan Ecolabel sets requirements based on recognized sustainable certification schemes. A number of tree species are restricted or not permitted for use in Nordic Swan Ecolabelled products. The restricted tree species origin mostly from tropical forests and the reason for restriction is either that they are endangered or that they are key species in Intact Forest Landscape (IFL) areas.
Restoration, preservation and strengthening of biodiversity	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel has taken important measures to protect and strengthen biodiversity, for example: endangered fish species are banned in restaurants, certain wood species in wood-based products and genetically modified organisms (GMOs) in certain agricultural products. Nordic Ecolabelling also have started to look for new possibilities to further reward practices that promote biodiversity, for example close-to-nature forestry, agroforestry and agroecology. For new buildings measures must be taken to protect biodiversity at the building plot.
Sustainable use of water	For selected product groups the ecolabel sets requirements for sustainable water consumption and demands that measures be taken to reduce the amount of unwanted chemicals in wastewater. For example, the Nordic Swan Ecolabel has strict requirements for the use of pesticides in cultivation of cotton and other raw materials. Other requirements limit the use of unwanted dyes and other chemical substances in the manufacturing of, for example, textiles and paper.
Maintaining and enhancing water quality	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel takes measures to reduce the amount of unwanted chemicals released to water bodies and also sets requirements for treatment of wastewater.
Maintaining and enhancing soil quality and productivity	Indirectly covered through accepting recognized sustainability certification schemes such as palm oil (RSPO), soy (RTRS) and sugar cane (Bonsucro) in addition to certifications for organic agriculture. Additionally, the Nordic Swan Ecolabel is a strong instrument for phasing out substances that are hazardous to health and the environment in products and manufacturing, helping to reduce contamination of soil.

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Soil quality consideration for use of residual flows	Indirectly covered through accepting recognized sustainability certification standards such as RSB.
Prohibition on the use of hazardous/toxic chemicals	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel has stringent requirements on chemicals harmful to health and the environment. The Nordic Swan Ecolabel helps reducing the amount of hazardous substances and promoting healthy lives for all. This applies to substances that come into direct contact with humans as well as substances that pollute air, soil and water. Based on precautionary considerations, the Nordic Ecolabelling excludes or limits both ingoing and process substances that are proven to be harmful and those that are suspected to be harmful, even though they are not yet classified or on an authority-regulated list. Nano materials and microplastic sources are also regulated and banned where appropriate. For example, when growing bamboo, flax and other bast fibres the only pesticides which may be used are those permitted under the European Pesticides Regulation (1107/2009/EC) and after felling, the timber or bamboo must not have been treated with pesticides classified as type IA and type IB by World Health Organization (WHO).
Implement best practices for the use of (agro)chemicals	Indirectly covered through accepting recognized sustainability certification standards such as palm oil (RSPO), soy (RTRS) and sugar cane (Bonsucro) where this criterion is covered.
Restrict air pollution, promote good air quality	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel is a strong instrument for phasing out substances that are hazardous to health and the environment in products and manufacturing, helping to reduce contamination of air. Some product groups (e.g., paints and varnishes) have environmental criteria to promote good air quality by reducing volatile organic compounds. Regarding particle pollution, emissions from ecolabelled combustion and pellet furnaces must meet strict requirements, and wood pellets must have good combustion properties.
Limit the risk of Indirect Land Use Change (ILUC)	Indirectly covered through accepting recognized sustainability certification standards such as RSB which also has an add-on to address ILUC.
Circularity	
General information	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel promotes circular economy. This is primarily done on the basis of the following six parameters: Requirements for renewable, recycled and sustainable raw materials; Strict chemical requirements; Requirements for reduced use of resources and energy; Quality requirements and lifetime; Requirements for product design, dismantling and repairability; and Requirements for optimum waste and resource handling.
Promote waste reduction and responsible waste management	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel strives to reduce waste, for example by promoting reuse of materials and setting strict requirements that allow the materials to be recycled. The Nordic Swan Ecolabel supports circular business models and takes into account regional characteristics, such as waste management systems and the possibilities of reusing and recycling different product and material types. Waste generated shall be separated and the various fractions reused as far as this is possible.
Raw material efficiency	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel emphasizes resource efficiency both for products and services and strive to make producers shift towards more sustainable types of resources and technology.
Efficient use of energy	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel is a tool for reduced total energy consumption and promotes less use of fossil fuels and more locally produced energy in products and services. The requirements on reduced energy use focus on: Production of materials and products, energy performance in the use stage, calculation of reduced energy use for several life cycle stages. The ecolabel requires to manufacturers the certification ISO 50001/ISO 50002 or EN 16247-1 on energy management. e.g., production plants of polymers, paints and varnishes, chemicals, pulp and paper.
Promote use of renewable sources	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel promotes and stimulates the use of renewable resources in different product criteria to replace the present fossil-based product e.g., new buildings (use of renewable insulation material or facades), Pulp and paper mills (use of renewable by-products for chemicals production). Nordic Swan ecolabelled investment funds exclude investments in extraction of fossil fuels and promote investments in renewable energy based on sustainable raw materials.
Promote material circularity	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel supports circularity by promoting design for recyclability of product and the packaging of the products. It provides user information on how materials are to be recycled. The Nordic Swan Ecolabel puts emphasis on quality and thus longevity, as well as design for disassembly and reuse. Recycled material is defined according to ISO 14021 in the categories of pre-consumer and post-consumer. Nordic Ecolabelling promotes recycling of plastic by setting requirements for replacing virgin plastics with recycled material in different ways.
Social	
General information	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel contributes to accomplishing several of the sustainable development goals and puts most emphasis on environmental aspects to achieve real environmental improvements. The Nordic Ecolabelling criteria also include some social requirements of concern/relevance. Relevant information found related to these social aspects are provided below.

D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

Compliance with labour rights	Some ecolabelled products are often produced in low-cost countries outside the EU. For these product groups the Nordic Swan Ecolabel requires that the factory comply with International Labour Organization core conventions. That means, for example, that there is no child labour, no forced labour, no discrimination and there is freedom of association and fair salary.
Respect wellbeing of workers	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel is a strong instrument for phasing out substances that are hazardous to health and the environment in products and manufacturing. This helps to prevent both users and factory workers from being exposed to harmful chemicals.
Respect property and usage rights	This aspect is indirectly covered through recognition of voluntary sustainability certification schemes where this requirement is covered.
Respect wellbeing of the local population	This aspect is indirectly covered through recognition of voluntary sustainability certification schemes where this requirement is covered. For example, through credible forest management certification, Nordic Ecolabel contributes to a more sustainable forest conservation that also provide economic and social benefits for local communities. Additionally, the Nordic Ecolabel promotes well-being of all through strict requirements for chemicals and the reduction of the amount of hazardous substances in all products.
Food security	For biobased feedstock, use of secondary raw materials such as residuals from other productions (e.g., bagasse from sugar cane) and recycled raw materials are in general promoted over primary raw materials. The requirements are often related to a specific raw material and product group in question. For fuels (outside the scope of this project), Nordic Ecolabelling would like to limit the use of biofuels from food- and feed crops and are therefore proposing to ban the use of food- and feed crops in the production of liquid and gaseous fuels. This means that Ecolabelled liquid and gaseous fuels should be produced from e.g., lignocellulosic material, non-food cellulosic materials or residues and waste.
Economic	
General information	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel criteria focus mainly on environmental aspects, health aspects and some social aspects of concern. Economic aspects are outside scope. Relevant information found related to economic aspects are provided below.
Financial and economic viability	The Nordic Swan Ecolabel contributes to sustainable economic growth by providing market benefits to products and services that are environmentally sustainable. The Nordic Swan Ecolabel is a tool for promoting circular economy by enhancing business competitiveness, promoting resource efficiency and helping to create new business models and innovative solutions.
Fair business practices, Integrity	-
Promote local development, Inclusive economic growth	-
Use of knowledge and technology	-
Fair trade and market practices	-
Risk assessment and management	-

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D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certifications schemes and labels, 30/04/2023

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About SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is an EU funded (Horizon Europe) project aiming at defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for industrial biobased systems to support tracing the sustainability (environmental, social, economic) of biobased products along the value chains and trades within the EU and globally for responsible production and consumption. This objective is realised by the development of a monitoring system, mapping of the current situation in global trade flows of biological resources and biobased products, and feasibility assessment from the adoption of certification schemes and labels considering actual economic as well as internalized environmental and social costs and benefits. The results of the project are leveraged to provide recommendations to four key target groups: policy makers, sustainability system community, industrial biobased value chain actors, and regional bioeconomy stakeholders. These ambitions are addressed by a strong, well-balanced and multi-disciplinary consortium comprised of 5 complementary partners. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED thereby supports the development of harmonized system requirements, continuous improvement of sustainability certification schemes and labels and contributes towards establishing a circular, climate-neutral and sustainable biobased industry.

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